

ENRICH IN AFRICA

Investing for Innovation in Africa

A review of the African business and entrepreneurial innovation landscape and its key actors.

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Abbreviations

ABAN- African Business Angel Network

AfCFTA- African Continental Free Trade Area

AfDB- African Development Bank

ASTII- African Science Technology and Innovation Indicators

AU- African Union

AUC- African Union Commission

AUDA- African Union Development Agency

BRI- Belt and Road Initiative (China)

BUILD - Better Utilization of Investments Leading to Development Act (BUILD Act, US)

CCHub- Co-Creation Hub

CESA- Continental Education Strategy for Africa

CVC- Corporate Venture Capital

DE4A- Digital Economy for Africa Initiative

DER/FJ- Délégation générale à l'Entrepreneuriat Rapide des Femmes et des Jeunes (General Delegation for the Rapid Entrepreneurship of Women and Youth)

DFC- U.S. International Development Finance Corporation (US)

EC- European Commission

EiA- ENRICH in Africa

EU- European Union

e-VBAB- e-Vidyabharati and e-Aarogyabharati (India)

EY- Ernst & Young

GCRF- Global Challenges Research Fund (UK)

FDI- Foreign Direct Investment

FOCAC- Forum on China-Africa Cooperation

GDP- Gross Domestic Product

GERD- Gross Expenditure on Research & Development

GII- Global Innovation Index

GIL- Gender Innovation Lab

GOVERD- Government Expenditure on Research & Development

HDIF- Human Development Innovation Fund (UK)

HLPD- High Level Policy Dialogue

IAFS- India–Africa Forum Summit

ICANN- Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers

ICT- Information and Communication Technology

ID- Identity Document

IDA- International Development Association

IFC- International Finance Corporation

INAFEC- India Africa Economic Cooperation Fund (India)

IP- Intellectual Property

IPO- Initial public offering

IsDB- Islamic Development Bank

ITEC- Indian Technical and Economic Cooperation (India)

ITU- International Telecommunications Union

KTN- Knowledge Transfer Network (UK)

LOC- Lines of Credit

LP- Limited Partner

M&A- Mergers and Acquisitions

MCC- Millennium Challenge Corporation (US)

MEST- Meltwater Entrepreneurial School of Technology

MET- Methys Consulting Group

MIIA- Millennium Impact for Infrastructure Accelerator

NEPAD- New Partnership for Africa's Development

ODI- Overseas Development Institute (UK)

OPIC- Overseas Private Investment Corporation

PACE- Partnering to Accelerate Entrepreneurship (US)

PANEP- Pan African E-network Project

PCT- Patent Corporation Treaty

PIDA- Programme for Infrastructure Development in Africa

PoC- Proof-of-Concept

PPP- Purchasing Power Parity

R&D- Research and Development

R&I- Research and Innovation

REC- Regional Economic Community

RLC- Regional Leadership Centres

RTO- Research Technology Organisation

S&T- Science and Technology

S2i- Steinbeis 2i GmbH

SBA- Small Business Act

SDG- Sustainable Development Goals

SIN- Science and Innovation Network (UK)

SME - Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

SOE- State-Owned Enterprise

SRIA- Strengthening Research Institutions in Africa (UK)

STI- Science, Technology and Innovation

STISA- Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa

TAM- Total Addressable Market

TMT- Technology, Media, and Telecommunications (sector)

UNECA- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa

UAE- United Arab Emirates

UK- United Kingdom

UN- United Nations

UNDP- United Nations Development Programme

UNESCO- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

US- United States of America

USADF- United States African Development Foundation (US)

VC- Venture Capital

YALI- Young African Leaders Initiative (US)

Chapter 1

Introduction and Context for
the Report

Steinbeis 2i GmbH

1. Introduction to the Report

Innovation is an increasingly important area of international collaboration, which is bringing in new public and private actors into the Science Technology and Innovation (STI)-collaboration domain. Over the past decade, we have seen a revolution in the innovation sectors of both Africa and Europe. New actors, such as tech hubs (incubators, accelerators, fab-labs etc.), tech entrepreneurs, venture capital (VC) investors, corporate innovators, regional innovation clusters etc., have become key players in the African innovation landscapes (chapter 3). Existing research actors, such as Research Technology Organisations (RTOs) and Universities have set up Technology Transfer Organisations and are exploring new models of technology management and exchange to stimulate the utilization of scientific research for the public (AU-EU High Level Policy Dialogue, 2020). It is, therefore, more important now than ever, that Europe and Africa find common areas for support, collaboration, and action if they are to maximise the benefits to both areas.

Africa has, up until now, struggled to compete with larger, more economically powerful countries where innovation inputs have been balanced to provide greater innovation outputs (chapter 2). In recent years, however, innovation success in Africa has been growing dramatically, with the continent providing a great impact on global markets as it increases inputs and strategies to a point where innovation outputs can excel.

Innovation is an important factor for the development of African countries considering the predicted increase in population and gross domestic product (GDP) to occur in the coming years (chapter 2). Such socio-economic pressure is resulting in increased challenges, which is, on the other hand, also providing incredible opportunities for African innovation to respond (chapter 3). The growth in venture capital investment and success as well as the explosion in the number of tech hubs indicates a direction of travel, which is expected to bring about a greater balance and degree of maturity to many of the countries. Mauritius and South Africa are already demonstrating great success in producing innovation environments that can support an increasing volume of innovative products and services (chapter 2). The African spirit of innovation has already seen mobile platforms become highly established in the African continent and FinTech dominating the technology sector (chapter 3). This success demonstrates the points of challenge for the countries, with innovation responding to bring about societal impact.

What is known, is the importance of each African country taking responsibility and affectively implementing new strategies for increasing innovation (chapter 2). With fifty-four African countries and fifty-four different business environments, each with their own characteristics and distinct routes to market, however, there is a need for combined priorities and activities, viewing a pan-African level (chapter 3).

Report Context and Guidance for Reading

This report has been generated in response to a request from the European Commission (EC) to provide them with supporting data to understand the overall landscape of innovation in and across Africa. This report will provide information that will be used in the context of the EC and African Union (AU) High-level Policy Dialogue group, and the current development of the EU-AU Innovation Strategy.

The report has been designed to provide a current snapshot of the status of innovation activities across Africa at the time of writing, with Chapter 2 providing the big-picture story of innovation in Africa through evaluating success as seen from a data-driven perspective, conducted by Steinbeis 2i GmbH (S2i), coordinators of the ENRICH in Africa project. This is broken down over three distinct areas. Firstly, an analysis of Africa across seventeen individual global indexes, focusing on innovation indicators, which reveals a new ranking list for African countries providing and producing innovation (2.1). From here, an analysis of Africa from a focused Research and Development (R&D) indicator perspective has been conducted (2.2). Finally, a deep dive analysis of the top five countries ranked as per the new listing generated through the research associated to 2.1 has been conducted within the Global Innovation Index (GII) 2021 (2.3), with a summary (see orange boxes) provided at the end of each sub-chapter, where required.

Chapter 3 then provides both a data-driven and more field-based evaluation of the ecosystem. The Methys Consulting Pty (MET) team who have provided the insights in section 3.1 and 3.3, are experts in the innovation and tech landscape in Africa, being based in South Africa, a key agency researching, reporting, and delivering activities on the ground across Africa, and one of the ENRICH in Africa project partners. Section 3.1, therefore, provides an overview of the innovation landscape of Africa, focusing on the start-up and tech ecosystems, the activities, key actors, main challenges, and opportunities occurring currently. Following this, section 3.2 provides insights into the public sector support being implemented within and towards African countries, focusing on national, intra-African and external initiatives and policies. The final section of this chapter, 3.3, then provides an overview of the private sector support offered by business support organisations, funding bodies and corporations. Again, summary sections have been provided at the end of each sub-chapter to support the reader, and here, hyperlinks to relevant website sources have also been included to support the reader in connecting to relevant information.

The final section of this report (section 4) then draws together the learnings from across the previous chapters, to demonstrate overall learnings, key insights, and potential opportunities for further developments to the African innovation ecosystem. It is the intention of the

authors of this report, that the information provided here be used to support an increased knowledge of, and engagement with, the African innovation landscape.

Methodology

The data-driven research has mainly been conducted through desk-based activities, evaluating indexes based on data gathered from and by key agencies and organisations who provide data analysis of innovation and economic trends globally, with Africa data extrapolated from the overall data provided. Where the data relating to Africa has separated the continent into multiple regions, this report has drawn the data together to provide an overall picture of the African ecosystem (North and sub-Saharan).

The more field-based research and insights have been conducted through a range of activities. This includes a survey undertaken within the consortium and advisory board of the ENRICH in Africa (EiA) project, which has produced guiding insights based on expert experience and opinion, as well as further research activities undertaken by the AfricArena team in the creation of their upcoming State of Tech in Africa 2021 report, which includes desk-based research, interviews conducted at the AfricArena events over the past couple of years, and outcomes from previous versions of the State of Tech in Africa report series.

Chapter 2

Africa's National Research &
Innovation Advancements

Steinbeis 2i GmbH

2. Africa's National Research & Innovation Advancements

2.1. Africa within the Index and Ranking Landscape

The intention of this section is to provide data-based information on the performance of African regions in the innovation realm, as well as, and even more importantly, to become aware of the countries, which play a major role when it comes to innovation on a general basis as well as within specific innovation-relevant areas. Specifically, the following two questions shall be explored:

- Which African regions and countries can be seen as the key African innovation regions/countries?
- Which African regions and countries rank highly within specific innovation-relevant categories?

To be able to answer both questions properly, an analysis of seventeen indexes and rankings (referred to cumulatively as 'indexes') was conducted. These indexes were found from within the global and regional landscape and contain data points relevant to providing a valuable overview of the innovation landscape in Africa.

2.1.1. Methodology

To successfully measure innovation in a specific region, it is necessary to review a wide range of data indicators and indexes, which provides a substantial amount of information and data for this analysis. As a result, it has been necessary to approach innovation by collating only the various indicators that influence it, such as the economy, regulation, policy, human capital, Information Communication Technology (ICT), and infrastructure. These indicators have then been mapped within common groupings to provide comparisons and insights for innovation across Africa.

The seventeen analysed indexes have been categorised into on six innovation-relevant groups (Innovation (in general), Start-up, Economy, Investment, ICT, Human Capital) generated for the purposes of this report, as shown in Table 1 below. While the first category 'Innovation' is obviously focused on specific indicators of innovation, the other five categories are all regarded as 'innovation-relevant' and play an important role in an innovation ecosystem. Within each of the six categories, between one to four indexes were collated. While it was the objective to analyse three to four indexes in each category, for two categories (Innovation, Human Capital) it was only possible to analyse one and two respectively. The reason for the inclusion of fewer indexes in these two categories, is the lack of suitable indexes found in the

global and regional landscape. Overall, this categorisation allows for a comprehensive mapping of African innovation leaders per category and overall. More details on each of the analysed indexes is available in Appendix 1 – Indexes and rankings used for analysis- section 2.1.

Table 1: Categorization of the analysed 17 innovation-relevant indexes

Category ¹	Number of indexes	Average publication year	Category content description
Innovation (Innovation)	1 index	2021	Measuring countries according to their capacity for, and success in, innovation.
Start-up Ecosystems & Entrepreneurship (Start-up)	3 indexes	2019-2021	Measuring start-up/entrepreneurship ecosystems, their health and potential moving forward.
Economic & Regulatory Environment (Economy)	4 indexes	2019-2021	Measuring the regulations, set of institutions, policies, and factors that influence the competitive sustainability and economic prosperity of a country as well as the degree of economic freedom.
Investment Attractiveness (Investment)	3 indexes	2020-2021	Measuring the attractiveness of a country for investors using a combination of economic, financial, institutional, and regulatory factors.
ICT & Connectivity (ICT)	4 indexes	2017-2020	Measuring how well-prepared countries are for technological change and a digital economy, and to exploit the opportunities offered by ICT.
Human Capital & Talent (Human Capital)	2 indexes	2017-2020	Measuring countries based on their ability to grow/develop, attract, and retain talent.
TOTAL	17 indexes		

¹ Including shortened term stated in brackets, which are used within the report.

While this categorisation facilitates the analysis of the innovation landscape in Africa, it must be acknowledged here that the categories themselves (due to the underlying data points and indicators of the individual indexes) are at times overlapping when it comes to the aspects that are being measured. Hence, the categories themselves should not be perceived as having precise boundaries, but rather permeable data sets. For both the index as well as the category weighting, an average was taken, with all indexes and categories weighted equally. The reason for not changing the weighting numbers is that both the indexes as well as the categories are important for innovation and there is no reason given as to why some indexes/categories should be under/overweighted.

In total, forty-nine African countries were analysed (omitting five African countries with a population below 1 million). To come up with a rank for each country within each of the six categories, an overall African ranking for each index was created. For each country, the individual index results within a category were then used to calculate an overall category average for each country. This was carried out for each of the six categories and for each of the forty-nine analysed countries. To receive an overall country rank, the average of all individual categories was then calculated. The result of this is one overall score and six individual category scores for each country. In this regard, it should also be noted here that some countries were not ranked in all the seventeen analysed indexes. This affected specifically countries with a low GDP and/or a small population, such as Botswana, Gabon, or Mauritius.

In the following sections, a focus is put on the five African regions (North, East, South, West, Central) as well as on the individual African countries, which achieve the highest results in the analysed categories (across and within). The fifteen highest ranked countries are then explored in more depth.

2.1.2. Regional Results

A comparison of the five different regions of Africa is important to understand where the key innovation regions in Africa can be located. To compare the regions between each other, the country-grouping of the AU was applied, which divides Africa into the following five separate regions (Figure 1): East Africa (green), Southern Africa (blue), West Africa (red), North Africa (orange), Central Africa (purple).

Using this grouping as a basis, the individual rankings of the top fifteen countries (overall and per category) were reviewed. The full results of this review are available in Appendix 2 – Country ranking according to the African regions, where the table also shows how the different countries in Africa perform when it comes each of the six innovation-relevant categories (Innovation, Start-up, Economy, Investment, ICT, Human Capital), displaying the

amount of countries of each region in the top five, top ten as well as the top fifteen countries for each category. An average number of countries of each region across all categories has also been produced.

Figure 1: Five African regions according to the African Union ²

When comparing the African regions (see Figure 2), it **becomes apparent that a huge gap exists between Central African countries and the other regions**. Central African countries receive generally very poor results in the top fifteen analysis and only appear in one of six categories. Moreover, in the overall top five countries (across all six categories), a huge gap becomes apparent between East, North and Southern African countries in comparison to West African countries. This is visible in that West African countries appear around five times less than East African and North African countries. In the top ten, this gap is lowered: here, West African countries appear around two-times less than North African countries. This gap is lowered even more in the top fifteen. **Overall, East, and North African countries achieve the best results in the top five, ten and fifteen.**

Considering the difference in the total number of countries belonging to a specific African region (only countries with a population above 1 million considered), these results can be seen in a different light. Considering this aspect, **Northern African countries perform well** since only six Northern African countries exist, as compared to ten Southern, eleven Eastern and

² Screenshot taken of the regions of the African Union (mapped by Fazal in 2014), on 11th November 2021, : https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regions_of_the_African_Union#/media/File:Regions_of_the_African_Union.png

fourteen Western African countries (population above 1 million, see Figure 2). **Particularly the performance of West African countries, being the region with the largest number of countries overall, appears even more inferior in this context.**

Figure 2: Number of countries appearing in top 5, 10, 15 and overall number of countries per region³

Figure 3 shows how the African regions perform within each of the six categories. The underlying data is based on each category's top fifteen best-performing countries. This figure shall provide information on how far an African region is overperforming or underperforming in each of the six categories i.e., achieving a result above or below 0% respectively, whereby 0% indicates the result where a region would be neither under nor overperforming. 'Overperforming' in this sense means that, based on the number of countries in a region, more countries appear in the top fifteen countries than expected. For instance, for the Start-up category, North African countries achieve a 113% result, meaning that more than double the amount of North African countries appear in the top fifteen countries (in this case 4 countries) than expected, when compared to an average result (neither under- nor overperforming). On the other hand, 'underperforming' means that, based on the number of countries in a region, on average fewer countries appear in the top fifteen countries than expected. An average rank means that a region would be neither under nor overperforming, achieving exactly 0%.

³ Based on the index mapping conducted for this report, displayed according to the five African regions of the African Union

Figure 3: Performance (over or under) of African regions in the six innovation-relevant categories⁴

On this basis, it becomes apparent that **North African countries score very high in five categories** (above 60% overperforming in each) – specifically in ICT, Investment as well as Start-up (all above 100%). Only for the category Human capital do they achieve an average rank. **Southern African countries rank particularly high in Innovation** (63% overperforming), but fairly average for the remaining categories, except for the Start-up category, where they underperform slightly (-35%). **East African countries overperform in all categories**, with ranges from ca. 20 to 50%. Particularly for Start-up, Innovation as well as Investment, they overperform by around 50% each. **West African as well as Central African countries underperform in all categories** (except for the category Economy, where West African countries overperform slightly at 17%). West African countries show particular underperformance when it comes to Innovation (-53%), Human capital (-34%) as well as Investment and ICT (both -30% each). **Central African countries underperform heavily (-100%) in five of the categories** because no Central African country appears here. The single category where they underperform slightly is Human capital (by -23%).

⁴ Based on the index mapping conducted for this report, displayed according to the five African regions of the African Union

Summary:

- **North Africa: Good performance in top five, ten and fifteen,**
 - **Overperformance: Start-up, Innovation, Economy, Investment, ICT,**
 - **Average performance: Human Capital**
 - **Underperformance: None**
- **Southern Africa: Good performance in top five, ten and fifteen,**
 - **Overperformance: Innovation, Human-capital**
 - **Average performance: Economy, Investment, ICT**
 - **Underperformance: Start-up**
- **East Africa: Good performance in top five, ten and fifteen,**
 - **Overperformance: Start-up, Innovation, Economy, Investment, ICT, Human-capital**
 - **Average performance: None**
 - **Underperformance: None**
- **West Africa: Poor performance in top five. Good performance in top ten and fifteen,**
 - **Overperformance: Economy**
 - **Average performance: Start-up**
 - **Underperformance: Innovation, Investment, ICT, Human-Capital**
- **Central Africa: Not ranked in top five and poor performance in top ten and fifteen,**
 - **Overperformance: None**
 - **Average performance: None**
 - **Underperformance: Start-up, Innovation, Economy, Investment, ICT, Human-capital**

2.1.3. Country Results

Based on the overall regional results of the previous sub-chapter, this section provides more in-depth knowledge on the individual high-performing African countries, showing which fifteen can be seen as the key African innovation countries. Figure 4 demonstrates these top fifteen African countries and how they rank on average across all six categories. Each country's regional location on the continent is provided in brackets following each country name. Central African countries are not included in this overview as no country of this region appears in the top fifteen.

Figure 4: Top 15 African countries ranked according to their score across all categories⁵

As is visible, Mauritius and South Africa score particularly high overall. Both can be categorized as 'very high performers' (blue), which set themselves apart from the rest of Africa. Following these, the three North African countries Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt, all achieve similar scores among themselves. These are complemented by Kenya, Rwanda, Botswana, and Ghana. All of these seven countries can be seen as 'high performers' (yellow). The third and last category are the 'good performers' (red) which are composed of Namibia, Nigeria, Tanzania, Algeria, Cote d' Ivoire and Senegal. As became apparent in chapter 2.1.2, North African countries rank highest, followed by East and Southern African countries, while West and Central African countries rank lower overall. **The regional outcomes can, therefore, be confirmed on a country level as well.** To visualise the positioning of each country, Figure 5 offers a mapping of the scores for each country within the six analysed categories, moving from highest-ranked countries (left) to lowest-ranking (right).

⁵ Based on the index mapping conducted for this report. For full information please refer back to Appendix 3 – Overall country rankings according to six categories

Figure 5: Top 15 African countries according to their rank within each category⁶

⁶ Based on the index mapping conducted for this report. For full information please refer to Appendix 3 – Overall country rankings according to six categories. The amount of categories (maximum six) in which a country achieves a Top 15 ranking appears after each country's name in brackets.

In Figure 6, economic data (GDP and GDP per capita⁷) has been plotted for each of the top fifteen countries, which are ranked in this figure according to their score. It is clear to see that the GDP of these countries is generally low, i.e., ten countries have a GDP of below \$100 Bil., six of these are even below \$50 Bil., with only 3 countries reaching a GDP above \$200 Bil.. For the GDP per capita, 2/3 of the countries do not achieve results above \$3,500. Moreover, 4 countries are even below \$2,000 and only three countries accomplish results above \$4,000. Overall, **when analysing the countries' economic data, no significant correlation between the data indicators and the position of the countries in the top fifteen ranking is seen**, highlighting that the higher-ranking countries (top five) do not, in fact, also achieve a higher GDP and/or GDP per capita result. A detailed overview of the data for each individual country, including population, location and GDP can be found in Appendix 4 – Country performance: Population, location, and GDP data.

Figure 6: GDP and GDP per capita for the top 15 ranked countries

The fact that there is no significant correlation for the economic GDP data could possibly be explained by insights from a report called 'African Innovation Report - Understanding Market-Creating Innovation Across Africa' which was published by The Africa Foresight Group in 2020⁸.

⁷ [World Bank: GDP data \(2020\)](#)

⁸ [Harambeans: African Innovation Report \(2020\)](#)

In this report, four types of African innovation ecosystem classifications have been identified: Autopilots, Rising economies, Innovation engineers and Fertile grounds. The classification of these innovation ecosystems is based on the strength of local economy, as well as the strength of innovation environment. A strong economy in this regard, is based on data sets such as Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), GDP per capita, inflation, as well as unemployment data sets, among others. A strong innovation environment is calculated based on data sets such as internet penetration, access to electricity, the procedures to register a business etc.

For Autopilots, both the economic and innovation environments are currently rather challenging. Rising Economies show high economic growth rates in that their economy has only recently started to gather pace. They have the intention to diversify and grow their local economies and are oftentimes attracting significant amounts of FDI. However, they do not (yet) possess an enabling environment for innovation. Innovation Engineer countries in contrast have seen a recent decline in their economic growth but were able to build an enabling environment for innovation, which is strongly backed by the government. Fertile Grounds can be seen as economies that not only have a strong economy but can combine this with an enabling environment for innovation, allowing innovations to flourish and scale (Africa Foresight Group; Harambeans, 2020).

Table 2 is therefore able to demonstrate how eleven of the top fifteen countries are categorised according to these four types of innovation ecosystems. At least one country of the top fifteen can be found in each of the four categories. However, while there is only **one Autopilot (Nigeria)** and **two Rising Economy countries (Ghana, Tanzania)**, **four countries can be seen as Fertile Grounds (South Africa, Egypt, Cote d' Ivoire, Senegal)** and **four as Innovation Engineers (Kenya, Morocco, Tunisia, Algeria)**.

Table 2: Types of African innovation ecosystems according to The African Foresight Group

Innovation Ecosystem	Countries and Rank in Top 15	Indicators
Fertile Ground	South Africa (2 nd), Egypt (5 th), Cote d' Ivoire (14 th), Senegal (15 th)	Strong economic growth, enabling innovation environment
Innovation Engineer	Morocco (3 rd), Tunisia (4 th), Kenya (6 th), Algeria (13 th)	Declining economic growth, enabling innovation environment
Rising Economy	Ghana (9 th), Tanzania (12 th)	Strong economic growth, less enabling innovation environment
Autopilot	Nigeria (11 th)	Declining economic growth, less enabling innovation environment
Not ranked	Mauritius (1 st), Rwanda (7 th), Botswana (8 th), Namibia (10 th)	-

When comparing the average top fifteen position within each of the four categories, it becomes apparent that two of the four Fertile Grounds countries, South Africa, and Egypt, also achieve the highest ranking in the top fifteen. Innovation Engineers Kenya, Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria are ranked higher than the Rising Economies countries, Ghana, and Tanzania, which are backed by a strong and fast-growing economy but do not possess such an enabling innovation environment. It is worth highlighting here, that some countries can, in fact, be located within different categories due to the different data sets used, such as with regards to Kenya: positioned within Autopilot and Innovation Engineer; South Africa: within all categories, and Egypt: within Fertile Ground and Innovation Engineer. In these cases, therefore, the country was listed within the category where its majority share value was located.

The fact that Innovation Engineers perform higher in the top fifteen than Rising Economies begs the question, if innovation-relevant aspects are of more importance than economic characteristics? What becomes clear, though, is that **countries that cannot count on strong economic data, can still be positioned as an innovative country**. These countries possibly rely on tangible, innovation-relevant aspects, such as a strong internet penetration, the procedures to register a business, etc., but possibly also on other more intangible factors, which contribute to their innovativeness. Both tangible and intangible factors will be discussed within chapter 2.3, where a review of the top five is conducted through the pillars, sub-pillars, and indicators of the GII.

Summary:

- **The regional outcomes can be confirmed on a country level as well,**
- **No significant correlation between the economic data indicators and the position of the countries in the top fifteen ranking is seen,**
- **Mauritius, South Africa, Tunisia, Morocco, Egypt, Kenya, Rwanda, Botswana, Ghana and Namibia achieve the highest results (in that order), with Mauritius and South Africa setting themselves apart from the rest,**
- **Innovation ecosystem types:**
 - **Autopilot: Nigeria,**
 - **Rising Economies: Ghana, Tanzania,**
 - **Fertile Grounds: South Africa, Egypt, Cote d' Ivoire, Senegal,**
 - **Innovation Engineers: Kenya, Morocco, Tunisia, Algeria,**
- **Countries that cannot count on strong economic data, can still be positioned as an innovative country.**

2.2. Research and Development in Africa

2.2.1. Research and Development Expenditure

To set a good foundation for an analysis of R&D success, the R&D expenditure of the African continent has been first analysed, followed by a review of the individual countries. In total, six indicators were used to see how the different African regions and countries rank in this regard. This chapter shall specifically allow a comparison of Gross General Expenditure on R&D (GERD) as a percentage of GDP and Government Expenditure on R&D (GOVERD) also as a percentage of GDP, with three indicators assessed for each. While GERD covers all expenditure sources for R&D (business, government, private non-profit, etc.), GOVERD is just focused on the GDP expenditures for R&D from the government itself. Table 3 provides an overview of these indicators. Within these indicators, the African continent has been split over two separate regions: sub-Saharan Africa and Arab States, which includes North Africa.

Table 3: Gross Research and Development Expenditure (GERD) & Government Expenditure (GOVERD) indicators covered

Nr.	Indicator	Source	Year(s)
1	Gross Expenditure in Research and Development (GERD) as % of GDP	World Bank (country level) ⁹ , UNESCO Institute for Statistics (regional level) ¹⁰	2005-2018
2	Gross Expenditure in Research and Development (GERD) in constant \$Bil.	UNESCO Institute for Statistics (regional level) ¹¹	2013
3	Gross Expenditure in Research and Development (GERD) by Source of Funds	UNESCO Institute for Statistics ¹²	2007- 2017
4	Government Expenditure on R&D (GOVERD) as % of GDP	African Innovation Outlook III ¹³	2013-2015
5	Government Expenditure on R&D (GOVERD) in PPP \$ Mil.	African Innovation Outlook III ¹⁴	2013-2015
6	Government Expenditure on R&D (GOVERD) per Capita	African Innovation Outlook III ¹⁵	2013-2015

⁹ [World Bank: Research and development expenditure \(% of GDP\) - Sub-Saharan Africa, Middle East & North Africa](#)

¹⁰ [UNESCO: 'Global Investments in R&D Factsheet' \(June 2020\)](#)

¹¹ [UNESCO: 'How much does your country invest in R&D?'](#)

¹² [UNESCO: 'Global Investments in R&D Factsheet' \(June 2020\)](#)

¹³ [African Union: African Innovation Outlook III \(2015\)](#)

¹⁴ [African Union: African Innovation Outlook III \(2015\)](#)

¹⁵ [African Union: African Innovation Outlook III \(2015\)](#)

Regional Level Review

Figure 7 visualises the data relating to the GERD spend as well as the percentage of GDP that is dedicated to R&D across the global regions, providing an insight into how sub-Saharan Africa and the Arab States (incl. North African countries) compared to other regions worldwide. As is visible in the figures, there is a clear correlation between R&D investment (GDP dedicated to R&D) and R&D outputs (R&D as % of GDP), proving that **regions investing a large amount on R&D also have a large percentage of GDP coming from R&D activities and vice versa.**

Figure 7: GDP (US \$ Billion) dedicated to R&D as compared to R&D as Percentage of GDP

The results show that North America & Western Europe as well as East Asia & the Pacific perform very well in both indicators. Both regions spend around \$700 Bil. and \$560 Bil. respectively on R&D and dedicate between 2.5% and 2.1% respectively of their GDP to R&D. In comparison, sub-Saharan Africa dedicates only \$10 Bil. to R&D. Hence, North America & Western Europe invest around seventy times and East Asia & Pacific around fifty-five times as much as sub-Saharan Africa. Also, they dedicate around five to six times as much of their GDP on R&D, as compared to sub-Saharan Africa, which only dedicates 0.4% of GDP to R&D. Only one region is ranking lower in both indicators than sub-Saharan Africa, which is Central Asia (0.2% of GDP and \$1 Bil.). It should be noted in this regard, that the population of sub-Saharan Africa is similar to North America & Western Europe (around one billion for each region), however, it has a much larger population in comparison to the Arab States (360 million),

Central & Eastern Europe (240 million) or Latin America & the Caribbean (650 million). Based on this, the amount of GDP spent on R&D seems even lower (as per capita basis).

In comparison, the Arab States perform slightly better than sub-Saharan Africa, with \$30 Bil. invested in R&D and 0.6% of GDP dedicated to R&D (with individual data from the database of the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, detailing that North Africa, specifically, dedicates 0.63% of GDP to R&D).¹⁶ The Arab States show similar results when compared to other regions, such as South & West Asia and Latin America & the Caribbean when it comes to the GDP dedicated to R&D (both regions spend 0.6 and 0.7% of GDP on R&D respectively). However, the overall GDP amount spent in the South & West Asia and Latin America & the Caribbean regions, amounts to \$50 Bil. for each, nearly double the amount of the Arab States (\$30 Bil.). **Africa as a combined region is, therefore, responsible for only 1% of research spending worldwide** (African Export-Import Bank, 2021).

Country Level Review

A further analysis has also been conducted into the GERD and GOVERD, both as percentage of GDP, within individual African countries (see Appendix 5 – Gross Expenditure on R&D (GERD) and Government Expenditure on R&D indicators). The results for GERD of thirty-three countries are shown in Figure 8. As is visible, **there are vast differences between African countries when it comes to GERD**, ranging from 0.83% (South Africa) to 0.01% (Madagascar and Mauritania). While some countries, such as South Africa, Kenya and Egypt as well as Morocco and Burkina Faso (all above 0.7%) achieve very high scores, around half of the analysed African countries achieve scores of 0.3% or below. In total, twelve of the countries that are in the top fifteen, as discussed in chapter 2.1, can be found in the highest 50% of countries concerning GERD. Eight of these fifteen countries are even included in the highest ten ranked countries. Just Nigeria (0.13) and Cote d' Ivoire (0.08) can be found in the lowest 25% of the analysed countries when it comes to GERD. Overall, the average GERD of all analysed countries is 0.37%.

In comparison, for GOVERD, less data is available for the African countries (only eighteen countries can be included and analysed). For this indicator, Tanzania scores the highest with 0.27%, followed by Egypt (0.29%), Senegal (0.23%) and Mali (0.19%). Half of the countries score above 0.1%. Of all the countries in the top fifteen, eight of them are included. Overall, the average GOVERD of all analysed countries is 0.12%. GOVERD, therefore, makes up around 32% of the GERD (% of GDP). This indicates that R&D investment in African countries still depends, to a certain degree, on governmental spending.

¹⁶ [according to UNESCO Institute for Statistics database](#)

Figure 8: GERD and GOVERD, both as percentage of GDP

Further analysis has also been undertaken to explore the GOVERD in purchasing power parity (PPP) \$ M alongside GOVERD per capita, as shown in Figure 9. In total, nineteen countries were analysed. For the GOVERD in PPP\$ M, Egypt and South Africa show very high results, setting themselves apart from the other countries. Tanzania, Ethiopia, Ghana and Senegal also show relatively high numbers, especially when comparing their figures to the median value of all nineteen analysed African countries, which is \$40.8 (average of \$237). The GOVERD per capita indicator shows that some countries achieve a high per capita value, when compared to the overall PPP\$ amount. While Egypt and South Africa show the highest figures (both per capita and in PPP\$ M), four African countries show high per capita values even though their overall PPP\$ M is rather low: Namibia, Botswana, Eswatini and Senegal. These are specifically high, when compared to the median value, which is \$1.91 per capita and an average of \$5.6.

Figure 9: GOVERD in PPP\$ M and PPP\$ per capita

In Figure 10, the GERD source of funds (governmental vs. non-governmental) of sixteen African countries, five high-income countries and seven other countries (mix of low, lower-middle, and upper-middle income) are included. When comparing only the African countries to each other, a large difference can be perceived between them, in that the governmental funding ranges from 24% to 97%, while the average of all sixteen countries is 67%. While countries such as Morocco, Kenya, and Uganda (below 30% of governmental funding) as well as Mozambique and South Africa (both below 50% of governmental spending) do not, to a high degree, rely on governmental funding when it comes to R&D, countries, such as Nigeria, Zambia, Egypt and Togo (all above 90% of governmental funding) very much depend on governmental R&D funding. In comparison, the average of five highly developed countries (from Europe and North America, as well as Japan) is around 26%, a significant amount less than the 67% average of the African countries. However, the average of the low and lower-middle income as well as upper-middle income countries (from Asia, Europe and Latin

America) is 54%. These countries on average show slightly better results to Africa as a whole. Overall, the results indicate that **high-income countries depend less on governmental and more on non-governmental funding, while the low and lower-middle income countries depend more on governmental spending.**

Figure 10: GERD by source of funds

2.2.2. Distribution and Amount of Researchers

In this chapter, two relevant R&D indicators, which focus on the worldwide percentage distribution and number of researchers, are reviewed, shown below in Table 4:

Table 4: Indicators focused on R&D Researchers Covered

Nr.	Indicator	Source	Year(s)
1	Percentage Distribution of Researchers worldwide	UNESCO Institute for Statistics ¹⁷	2013
2	Number of Researchers in R&D (per million people)	World Bank ¹⁸	2005-2018

When looking at the regional averages for the percentage of researchers worldwide (see Figure 11), one can observe that nearly 80% of all researchers are located in North America & Western Europe or in East Asia & the Pacific (both around 40% each), while around 10% are occupied in Central & Eastern Europe. Hence, only around 10% of the researchers work in the other regions of the world covering South & West Asia, Latin America & the Caribbean, Arab States, sub-Saharan Africa and Central Asia. In the Arab States and sub-Saharan Africa, only a combined 3% of the researchers of the world can be found (1.9% in Arab States and **1.1% in sub-Saharan Africa**). When taking into account that the Arab States region also includes other countries besides North African ones, the overall number of researchers for Africa decreases to below 3%. Since Africa's population amounts to around 17.2% of the world's population, a large difference can be perceived between the researchers per capita in Africa, in comparison to other regions worldwide. **The number of researchers in Africa (sub-Saharan and North Africa) is, therefore, a lot lower than is seen within almost all the other regions.**

Figure 11: Percentage distribution of researchers worldwide

¹⁷ [UNESCO: 'How much does your country invest in R&D?'](#)

¹⁸ [World Bank: Researchers in R&D \(per million people\) - sub-Saharan Africa, Middle East & North Africa](#)

Comparing the number of researchers in R&D (per million people) of fifteen African countries (selected due to availability of data), as shown in Figure 12, a vast difference between North African and sub-Saharan African countries becomes apparent, in that all four North African countries can be found in the top positions: Tunisia (1,772) and Morocco (1,074) rank very high, while Algeria (819) and Egypt (687) are still way ahead of most sub-Saharan African countries. The average of these four North African countries is 1,088. As a point of comparison, the best performing countries worldwide, such as South Korea and Denmark, had between 7,000-8,000 scientists and researchers per million people.

The sub-Saharan countries (eleven analysed) with the highest number of researchers in R&D are Senegal (564), South Africa (518) and Mauritius (474), while Namibia (149), Ghana (89) and Cote d' Ivoire (69) score very low, particularly when comparing them to the North African or highest-ranking sub-Saharan countries. The average of these eleven sub-Saharan countries is 237, way lower than the 1,088 of the North African countries. However, the lowest-scoring countries in Africa, by contrast, achieve even only 11 researchers per million people.

Figure 12: Researchers in R&D (per 1. Mio. People)

Reflecting on the data presented, Africa is responsible for only 2% of the world's research output, with only 0.1% of all patent applications registered in Africa, compared to 65% in Asia and 25% in North America. To become more competitive within the global innovation ecosystem, Africa appears to have many challenges and much to do to raise its contributions to, and the impact from, innovation.

Summary:

- Regions investing a large amount on R&D also have a large percentage of GDP coming from R&D activities and vice versa,
- Africa as a combined region is responsible for only 1% of research spending,
- There exist large differences between African countries regarding GERD,
- High-income countries depend less on governmental and more on non-governmental funding, while the low and lower-middle income countries depend more on governmental spending,
- Only 1.1% of all researchers are located in sub-Saharan Africa. Comparing the number of researchers in R&D (per million people), a vast difference between North African (1,088 researchers) and sub-Saharan African becomes visible (237 researchers). The number of researchers in Africa (sub-Saharan and North Africa) is, therefore, a lot lower than is seen within almost all the other regions.

2.3. African Developments within the Global Innovation Index 2021 (GII)

2.3.1. Methodology of the GII and Data Contextualisation

The GII (World Intellectual Property Organisation, 2021) is one of the most globally renowned and respected indexes used by both industry and governments to understand and explore innovation potential. The 2021 GII evaluates one-hundred-and-thirty-two countries of which thirty-one are African. Within the GII, the continent of Africa has been separated into two different regions: North Africa & West Asia and sub-Saharan Africa. For the purposes of this chapter, all African countries have been regrouped and are evaluated alongside each other as a continent.

The GII uses a wide range of pillars and indicators to measure innovation performance within regions around the globe, including R&D and non-R&D measures (Figure 13). The structure of the index consists of two sub-indexes: the innovation input sub-index seeks to capture elements of the economy that enable and facilitate innovative activities; the innovation output sub-index seeks to measure the results of innovative activities within the economy. The GII overall ranking is therefore an average of the input and output sub-indexes.

Within each of these sub-indexes are subsequent pillars, which are in turn made up of sub-pillars and their individual data indicators- a total of 81 indicators were used in the 2021 index (the full list of sub-pillars and indicators is provided in Appendix 6 – GII pillars, sub-pillars, and indicators). These data indicators are taken from data points gathered from across quality statistical reference points collected from government and business sources as well as other

indexes, including the World Bank, United Nations (UN), International Monetary Fund. This creates a rounded and overarching impression of innovation within the regions.

The 81 indicators themselves can be sub categorised by data type as follows:

- quantitative/objective/hard data (63 indicators)
- composite indicators/index data (15 indicators)
- survey/qualitative/subjective/soft data (3 indicators).

These indicators enable the regions to be evaluated based on objective data, which can be compared to produce the overall global picture of innovation success and potential, as can be seen through the annual movements of countries within the ranking.

Figure 13- GII Index Structure

The Innovation input pillars and indicators seek to capture the creation of knowledge, exploration of this knowledge and investments into its development, clearly indicating the innovation efforts that are being made to nurture the right conditions for innovation to occur. Such input not only facilitates innovation through providing the right conditions, but also sets a social and cultural marker as to the intentions of the government and their prioritisation of innovation. The Innovation outputs pillars and indicators seek to then assess the rates of production of innovative ideas and technologies that can be applied, exploited, and produce impact for the country and global ecosystem, thus raising the innovative outcomes from the region. Key indicators of scientific publications, research and development expenditures,

international patent filings and venture capital deals for example, are assessed to understand overall innovation performance.

This is not to say, however, that all countries who provide innovation input see equal outputs as a result. In fact, some of the most interesting cases show that innovation output can occur despite a lack of input and vice versa. The questions then remain as to the underlying factors that may contribute to innovation output despite inputs provided, and whether additional measures can be undertaken to increase the likelihood of a strong output.

2.3.2. General Observations- Africa

A quick overview of the GII ranking list shows those innovation leading countries, who can be identified clearly through their balanced performance across all pillars and innovation systems. This balance generates a higher overall ranking. The data being returned for these countries demonstrates that they have become adept and efficient at translating innovation inputs into outputs. Across Africa, the ranking results show some surprising leaders, such as Mauritius who rank highest amongst all Africa for innovation (Table 5). However, despite this success within Africa, Mauritius and only one other country appear in the top 50% of countries globally, demonstrating that African countries have a long way to go to fully realise and optimise their innovation potential. A full list of the GII data and rankings for African countries (combining North and sub-Saharan Africa), can be reviewed in Appendix 7 – Country GII Data.

Table 5- African GII Rankings

Ranking in Africa	Country	GI I Ranking
1	Mauritius	52
2	South Africa	61
3	Tunisia	71
4	Morocco	77
5	Kenya	85
6	Cabo Verde	89
7	United Republic of Tanzania	90
8	Egypt	94
9	Namibia	100
10	Rwanda	102

Interestingly, when diving into the data behind the rankings, the data shows that some African countries can provide high levels of innovation output despite low levels of innovation input (performing above expectations for level of development). Countries such as the United Republic of Tanzania, for example, which, despite being in the lower middle-income economies group, is comparable in their innovation outputs with high-income countries such

as Chile and Uruguay. This is also true of countries such as Malawi, Madagascar, Ethiopia, and Guinea who are also producing higher outputs compared to their limited capacity to generate inputs (Figure 14).

Such outcomes indicate their capacity to overperform in the pillars of knowledge creation, impact, and diffusion, as well as the production of intangible assets, creative goods and services and online creativity, despite their economic development not being as robust as would be expected to produce such outcomes.

Within the income level groupings, Mauritius is the only African country allocated to the high-income group, where it is classed as performing in line with level of development¹⁹. In the upper middle-income group, South Africa was the only African country rated as performing above expectations, with Namibia performing in line with expectations. Within the lower middle-income group, Tunisia, Morocco, Kenya, and United Republic of Tanzania are all rated as performing above expectations, with Cabo Verde, Senegal, Ghana, Zimbabwe, and Zambia all performing in line with their level of development (Figure 14).

Rwanda, Malawi, and Madagascar have been ranked as part of the low-income group where they are rated as performing above expectation, with Rwanda and Malawi over-performing consistently for nine years, and Madagascar for five years. Burkina Faso, Uganda, Mozambique, Mali, Togo, and Niger are also ranked within this group as performing in line with their level of development.

Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Madagascar, South Africa, Morocco, Tunisia, United Republic of Tanzania are all deemed to be top innovation achievers, based on, and listed above in order of, performance within their income group coupled with the combined number of years achieving above expectation, with all countries achieving three or more years of high innovation performance for their level (Table 6). Kenya is particularly worth noting here, as it has consistently overperformed relative to their economic development for eleven years, showing consistent efforts for innovation support through scoring above income level in the indicators of Institutions, Market and Business Sophistication, and Knowledge and Technology outputs. It also scored above average within sub-Saharan Africa in the Human Capital and Research, and Creative outputs.

¹⁹ As per GII Database, WIPO, 2021 – performance relative to their predicted performance and level of development

Figure 14- Screenshot- GGI Innovation input to output performance, 2021²⁰

²⁰ GII 2021, P.33- Output and input rankings plotted against fitted line (neither efficient nor inefficient)

Table 6- African Country Innovation Performance (within income levels)

	High-income group	Upper middle-income group	Lower middle-income group	Low-income group
Performance above expectations (for level of development)		South Africa	Tunisia, Morocco, Kenya, Tanzania (United Republic of).	Rwanda, Malawi, Madagascar.
Performance in line with level of development	Mauritius	Namibia	Cabo Verde, Senegal, Ghana, Zimbabwe, Zambia.	Burkina Faso, Uganda, Mozambique, Mali, Togo, Niger.
Performance below expectations for level of development		Botswana	Egypt, Cote d'Ivoire, Nigeria, Algeria, Cameroon, Benin, Angola.	

What is interesting to note, is that, overall, sub-Saharan Africa is the strongest performing global region as per the 2021 index and regional breakdown, with the greatest number of economies performing above expectations (six in total). Combined with North Africa, this number rises to eight; a significant number of overachievers for one continent. However, six sub-Saharan African countries are also performing under expectations for their economic level: Botswana, Angola, Benin, Cote d'Ivoire, Cameroon, and Nigeria. When combined with North Africa, where Egypt and Algeria are also underperforming, this number also rises to eight. Compared to the other regions, however, it is clear that innovation in Africa is improving at a slower rate than other regions, with no sub-Saharan African country showing a steady improvement in their GII rankings year on year (World Intellectual Property Organisation, 2021).

It is also worth noting here that a sign of innovation as noted within the GII, is the existence and development of science and technology (S&T) clusters²¹, where concentrations of innovation output are seen. Despite significant developments in innovation inputs across Africa, no S&T clusters exist within the continent. Where S&T clusters, exist, innovation

²¹ Within the GII, defined through: 'selecting inventors listed in published patent applications under WIPO's Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) spanning the period 2015 to 2019; selecting authors listed in scientific publications in the Web of Science's Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) covering the same period; geocoding inventor and author addresses and then applying the density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) algorithm to the geocoded inventor and author points'

rankings improve significantly, so it could be assumed that the successful development of S&T clusters in Africa could also lead to improved rankings.

Innovation During COVID-19

The GII 2021 report also highlights that governments and companies across the world have been motivated by COVID-19 to scale up their innovation investments, with scientific output, Research and Innovation (R&I) expenditures, Intellectual Property (IP) filings and VC deals growing strongly. Across Africa, VC deals saw a massive 82.7% increase, above the average 5.8 % globally.

World-wide, the strongest sectors for innovation investment (corporate) during pandemic were, understandably, 1- Software and ICT (80% of companies recorded increased R&D spending in 2020), 2- ICT hardware and electrical equipment (65%) and 3- Pharmaceuticals and biotechnology (62%), clearly those sectors whose innovations were leading the pandemic containment efforts. Notably, renewable energy and digital streaming/gaming companies also showed growth in investments, supporting the battle to raise living standards, improve human health and protect the environment (renewable energy) as well as meet the rising levels of demand seen (streaming/gaming).

2.3.3. Individual Country Analyses

General Comments

Based on the findings of the research across all indexes in sections 2.1 and 2.2, which focuses on R&D indicators to drive the understanding of the highest performing countries across Africa, the top five performing countries have been selected, and a deep dive into the rankings of these countries within the GII has been conducted. The countries in focus are therefore South Africa, Mauritius, Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt. This deep dive explores the various successes and challenges of the countries as indicated within the GII ranked positions.

As a first step, these countries have been mapped alongside all countries in the top ten and according to their overall GII ranking as well as each individual pillar. This mapping (Figure 15), clearly demonstrates those key players even within the top ten. Immediate attention is drawn to the status of Mauritius, as not only the leading country across Africa (Overall GII Rank) but also as the leading country in the pillars of Institutions, Infrastructure and Creative Outputs, also performing strongly in Market Sophistication and Human Capital and Research, although less so in this latter pillar.

South Africa also stands out as the leading country in the pillars of Market Sophistication and Business Sophistication, taking second place overall and producing the best result on average across all pillars. Tunisia also stands out at this point as the leading country for Human Capital

& Research and Knowledge & Technology Outputs, also performing relatively well overall and in the Creative Outputs and Infrastructure pillars, however, they are also the lowest scoring country for Business Sophistication and one of the lowest for Market Sophistication.

Figure 15- Individual Country - Pillar Rankings Comparison

Other countries of note include Kenya who demonstrate some strengths in Market Sophistication, Business Sophistication and Knowledge & Technology Outputs. Rwanda also is of interest due to their success in the Institutions and Business Sophistication pillars, although their performance in other pillars is very low. Morocco is another country of note considering their success not only overall, but also across each pillar more consistently than most. Although not in the top few performers in individual pillars, they are consistently in the top half of six of the seven pillars.

Other countries shine in individual pillars (e.g., Namibia in Human Capital & Research and Botswana in Business Sophistication and Institutions), however, all demonstrate very low scores in others (e.g., Namibia in Knowledge & Technology Outputs, Infrastructure and Business Sophistication, and Botswana in Human Capital & Research, Market Sophistication and Creative Outputs)

What is therefore clear from this mapping, is that no one country has achieved successful outcomes across all pillars, with South Africa coming the closest in ensuring all pillars achieve the top, second or third quartile of ranking. All other countries, no matter how strong in any particular pillar, have been ranked in other pillars within the lowest quartile. This indicates the imbalance across both innovation inputs and outputs occurring in Africa, and, as mentioned in section 2.3.1, balance is key to achieving overall innovation success.

2.3.3.1. South Africa

Figure 16- South Africa GII mapping

As mentioned in the introduction to this section, South Africa, placed in the upper-middle economy group, sits in an overall ranking position of 61 and leads for Africa in both the Market Sophistication and Business Sophistication input pillars, also producing the best overall performance across all pillars, with no pillar dipping into the lowest quartile. With an output rank of 68 versus an input rank of 55, South Africa demonstrates a **greater capacity to generate innovation inputs comparable to the subsequent outputs achieved**. However, a drop of one place in the overall ranking between 2020 and 2021 shows that the balance and success of the pillars has not yet been truly realised. The mapping seen in Figure 16 reveals those pillars in which South Africa is most successful, namely Market Sophistication, where South Africa comes within the top quartile of countries, Institutions, Business Sophistication and Knowledge & Technology Outputs, where it achieves third quartile placement.

Pillar and Sub-Pillar Main Take-aways

Inputs:

An initial review of the scores for South Africa show that, despite scoring high in the *Institution* pillar (66.8), there is much global competition here which forces the actual ranking down to 55. When comparing this to the country's top pillar, *Market Sophistication*, competition is not as strong, with a lower score actually producing a higher ranking (score: 57.0, rank: 23). Both of these pillars highlight the highest value of innovation input areas for South Africa and a clear political desire for enhancing development in the business ecosystem defined through *Political Environment (Institutions sub-pillar, score: 60.6, rank: 57)*, *Regulatory Environment* (score: 71.8, rank: 46) and *Business Environment* (score: 67.9, rank: 75), as well as *Credit* (score: 47.3, rank: 42), *Investment* (score: 51.0, rank: 18) and *Trade, Diversification & Market Scale* (score: 72.7, rank: 52) within the *Market Sophistication* pillar.

The *Business Sophistication* pillar ranks reasonably well at 51 despite a score of 29.3, with the strongest sub-pillar being *Knowledge Absorption* (score: 32.5, rank: 51). The *Infrastructure* pillar by contrast scores and is ranked very low for the economic level of this country, achieving only 36.3 and 83 respectively. Within this pillar, the *Ecological Sustainability* sub-pillar scores particularly low, achieving only an overall score of 20.4 and a rank of 97. Considering the GII only covers 132 countries, this score is, indeed, very low especially considering the developed nature of some of the country's other pillars. The *General Infrastructure* and *Information and Communication Technologies (ICT's)* sub-pillars also do not fare well here, with the former only reaching a score of 25.0, resulting in a rank of 82, and the latter scoring 63.6 and a rank of 74.

Outputs:

Regarding innovation outputs (*Knowledge & Technology Outputs* and *Creative Outputs* pillars), South Africa scores low (21.9 and 20.6 respectively) with equally low rankings achieved (61 and 79 respectively). The highest performing sub-pillar is *Knowledge Creation* with a score of 20.5 but a rank of 52, closely followed by *Knowledge Impact*, scoring 32.7 (rank 55). Such rankings suggests that South Africa is working to increase innovation outputs through supporting labour productivity, the development of new businesses and digitalising the market to produce greater impacts, however, with a score of only 6.5 (rank: 97), the *Creative Goods & Services* sub-pillar shows that there is **a disconnect with enabling creative businesses to not only flourish nationally, but also export internationally**. *Online Creativity* (sub-pillar within the Creative Outputs pillar- score: 1.3, rank: 88) and *Knowledge Diffusion* (under the *Knowledge & Technology Outputs* pillar; score: 12.5, rank: 81) also show that **the conversion of innovation inputs to outputs is not being achieved to the extent expected from a country at this economic level**.

Indicator Insights

Inputs:

Within the highest scoring sub-pillar, Trade, Diversification & Market Scale, a significant score of 81.7 has been achieved for the indicator *Domestic Industry Diversification*. However, despite this high score the indicator is given an overall rank of only 73, clearly another point of global competition to receive such a high score compared to its subsequent lower ranking (for reference, Switzerland, ranked 1 overall in the GII, scored 90.5 in the same indicator, but was also ranked reasonably low at 49). However, this score reflects the fact that South Africa is reasonably successful in diversifying its industry, which is a key aspect of economic success.

Within the second highest scoring sub-pillar, Investment (which receives a very successful score of 51.0 and a ranking of 18), South Africa scores incredibly well in the indicator *Market Capitalisation*, achieving position 1 in the global ranking. This shows that South Africa has been very successful in securing significant stock market value for companies, a very strong factor for the increase in economic development of this country over the coming years.

The indicator *Expenditure on Education* (Human Capital & Research pillar, Education sub-pillar; score: 6.5, rank: 8) is also a very good output for South Africa and demonstrates a political strategy of investing significantly in education as a long-term plan for investing in innovation overall. This, coupled with a strong scoring and ranking against the *Domestic Credit to Private Sector* (Credit sub-pillar; score: 139.5, rank: 11) and *Ease of Protecting Minority Investors* (Investment sub-pillar; score: 80.0, rank: 13) indicators, both of which are within the Market Sophistication Pillar, highlights the efforts being made to enhance the investment ecosystem, providing more opportunities for relevant investors and access to capital for innovative companies from the diverse society on which South Africa is built.

The indicator *Ease of Starting a Business* (Institutions pillar, Business Environment sub-pillar; score: 81.2) at first appears to also provide significant influence on the innovation ecosystem, however, with a ranking of 107, it is clear that, **despite conditions within South Africa providing an open national system supporting the creation of companies, on a global scale this is not comparable to the efforts of other countries.** This point is further compounded when considering the *FDI Net Inflow* indicator (Business Sophistication pillar, sub-pillar Knowledge Absorption), which shows a ranking of 105 and proves that **efforts to convert regulatory ease into attracting inward investments has not been successful.** Within the Business Sophistication pillar, the indicators of *Intellectual Property Payments* (score: 1.8, rank: 15) and *High-tech Imports* (score: 10.1, rank: 32) are also worth highlighting as these specific indicators demonstrate other regulatory efforts being made to minimise innovation costs while increasing international trade impacts, which can affect higher output potential for innovative ideas and solutions. This particular low GII outcome, may not, however, be

based on the innovation landscape alone, rather being impacted by societal indicators not evaluated within this index. It is commonly known and assumed, for example, that for inward investors to thrive, the right societal environment is required, which can provide an accessible and easily transferrable ‘home’ for the employees, and, of course, any potential family members. As these aspects are not covered within this index, this evaluation cannot provide direct answers as to the reasons behind these figures. What can be interpreted, is that a global trend for easing the restrictions on the creation of new companies and subsequently new innovations is occurring. Within such a competitive landscape, for any country to be successful, **the regulatory processes need to be fully streamlined and capitalised upon**, to draw in the FDI which is so essential to raising economic and innovation value.

Outputs:

Innovation output indicators for South Africa are considerably low considering the efforts being made to provide supportive inputs. Of all the indicators, the highest ranking is New Businesses (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Impact sub-pillar), which ranks 13th (score: 10.2). This is followed by *Global Brand Value* (Creative Outputs pillar, Intangible Assets sub-pillar; score: 88.3, rank: 23) and *Software Spending* (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Impact sub-pillar; score: 0.4, rank: 24). Each of these indicators demonstrates that South Africa, despite lacking success in innovation development, still retains a solid respect globally as an economy working in the digitalisation and business development. The discrepancy between indicators such as the outward focused *Global Brand Value* (rank 23) and inward focused *FDI Net Inflows* (rank 105), however, show that there is much to be done to develop a supportive innovation ecosystem, which can compete against the more developed economies for international trade and innovation outputs.

Summary:

- South Africa has a greater capacity to provide innovation inputs than produce outputs, with the conversion of inputs to outputs not being achieved to the extent expected from a country at this economic level,
- A disconnect exists with enabling creative businesses to not only flourish nationally, but also export internationally,
- Despite conditions within South Africa providing support for the creation of companies, this is not comparable to the efforts of other countries, with FDI rates not reflecting the investments made into the business economy,
- Economy is more focused on developing innovation through business and digital developments as well as education, seemingly overlooking the importance of creativity as a main driver for innovation outputs,
- Regulatory processes need to be fully streamlined to capitalise on efforts made.

2.3.3.2. Mauritius

Figure 17- Mauritius GII mapping

Mauritius sits within the high economy group and is the top African country ranked within the GII, located in position 52 overall, whilst also ranking in position 58 for output and 48 for input, **demonstrating a greater capacity to provide innovation input than produce outputs** (Figure 17). This position remains steady with Mauritius neither gaining nor losing a ranking position since the 2020 GII. On a pillar level, Mauritius also leads for Africa in the input pillars of Institutions and Infrastructure as well as the output pillar of Creative Outputs. Whilst being strong in these particular areas, Mauritius' performance in the pillar of Business Sophistication is very low, undermining their capacity to reach a higher overall ranking. Despite ranking so highly in Creative Outputs, the low ranking in Knowledge & Technology Outputs demonstrates **an imbalance in the type of innovation being produced, with creative industries achieving a greater impact than more scientific or technical developments.**

Pillar and Sub-Pillar Main Take-aways

Inputs:

Ranking very high in the *Institutions* pillar (score: 81.2, rank: 21), Mauritius' highest ranked pillar overall, this small Island nation is demonstrating a capacity to compete on a global level, not just across Africa, despite a population of only 1.3 million. Within this pillar, the sub-pillars of *Business Environment* (score: 84.1, rank: 21) and *Regulatory Environment* (score 83.2, rank: 24) achieve high recognition, placing within the top 25 countries globally to be providing business and regulatory stability. The sub-pillar of *Investment (Market Sophistication* pillar, score: 56.6, rank: 14) is, however, the strongest sub-pillar for inputs, ranking 14th globally (score: 56.6) and showcasing Mauritius as a country providing competitive access to investment opportunities as well as an active investor community engaging internationally.

Within the *Market Sophistication* pillar, however, the sub-pillar Trade, Diversification & Market Scale score surprisingly low (score: 61.3, rank: 89). The sub-pillar *General Infrastructure (Infrastructure* pillar) also produces a low outcome, although *Information & Communication Technologies* (score: 68.6, rank: 59) and *Ecological Sustainability* (score: 35.3, rank: 46) within the same pillar, achieve a more favourable, although globally average, performance.

As striking as the success of the *Institutions* and *Market Sophistication* pillars, is the under-performance of the *Business Sophistication* pillar. Here, the sub-pillars of Knowledge Workers (score 15.9, rank: 110) and Knowledge Absorption (score: 17.5, rank: 105) produce a **significant imbalance for Mauritius, polarising their successes and challenges greater than is seen in any other African country.**

Outputs:

The polarisation noted for the inputs is also surprisingly reflected in the output pillars, with the significant success of *Creative Outputs* (score: 36.3, rank: 31) contrasted with the lack of success in producing *Knowledge and Technology Outputs* (score: 13.6, rank: 93). Knowledge & Technology Outputs achieves low scores for all sub-pillars; *Knowledge Creation* (score: 5.9, rank: 104), *Knowledge Impact* (score: 21.4, rank: 95) and *Knowledge Diffusion* (score: 13.5, rank: 75). Here, however, it is worth noting that two indicators within *Knowledge Creation* are not awarded any score due to data not being available. The data that has been included is, however, low score despite this, which leads to the overall low rank.

Creative Outputs by contrast, achieves well overall (score: 36.6, rank: 31) despite average scores for two of the three sub-pillars. Intangible Assets score very well at 53.3 and a rank of 14, with *Creative Goods & Services* (score: 19.6, rank: 56) and *Online Creativity* (score: 19.2,

rank: 59) positioned slightly above a middle ranking (66). This disparity indicates a **tendency for the country to engage better in the more intangible, creative innovation sectors as, for instance, to the highly data-driven knowledge-based innovations which produce patents, scientific and technical outputs, and growth in productivity.**

Indicator Insights

Inputs:

As mentioned above, the highest-ranking sub-pillar for Mauritius is Investment (Market Sophistication pillar), which contains the indicators *Ease of Protecting Minority Investors*, *Market Capitalisation*, *Venture Capital Investors* and *Venture Capital Recipients*. The assumption concluded above that Mauritius is supporting a strong investor community engaging internationally was drawn from the scores and rankings of these latter two indicators. *Venture Capital Investors* ranks incredibly high at position 1 globally, overshadowing global leaders such as Switzerland where this indicator is ranked at position 7. The indicator of *Venture Capital Recipients* is also highly ranked, however, only reaching position 20, which, while achieving such a high position, indicates that the investors located here are investing abroad more than investments are being returned internally. This factor may not simply be due to an international preference from these investors and may instead be explained by the low scores for the Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, especially shown in the Knowledge Creation sub-pillar, ranked incredibly low at 104 (score 5.9). **If Mauritius is not able to maximise the creativity of its market, converting this strength into innovation and ingenuity, the investors will need to seek outside of their home market to be able to maximise commercial goals.**

This imbalance is indicative of a country which is providing strong institutional support and nurturing open creativity but requires further development in the scientific and technical ecosystem to generate balance, which would raise its innovation potential. This assumption is further backed up when considering the Business Sophistication pillar (score: 17.1, rank: 111), where the provision of Knowledge Workers (sub-pillar, score: 15.9, rank: 110) requires significant development in the indicators *GERD performed by Business* (score: 0.0, rank: 81) and *GERD Financed by Business* (score: 4.1, rank: 85), as well as in the sub-pillar Knowledge Absorption (score: 17.5, rank: 105), where the indicators *Intellectual Property Payments* (score: 0.2, rank: 89) and *High-tech Imports* (score: 6.0, rank: 97) rank extremely low for a country achieving such dynamic results in the other indicators. Another indicator providing support for this imbalance of knowledge generation is the *University-industry R&D Collaboration* (Pillar Business Sophistication, sub-pillar Innovation Linkages), where a score of 31.1 and rank of 109 demonstrates **a disparity between the knowledge-driven and creative innovation communities.**

By contrast, the Education sub-pillar (Human Capital and Research pillar, score: 58.6, rank: 35) is performing reasonably well, with the indicator *Government Funding/Pupil, Secondary* scores 30.4 and is ranked incredibly high in position 6 globally. The second and third sub-pillars here, Tertiary Education (score: 30.1, rank: 75) and Research & Development (score: 3.1, rank: 88) also reflect this imbalance compared to government funded secondary education, with the indicators of *Tertiary Enrolment* (score: 40.6, rank: 72) and *Gross Expenditure on R&D* (score: 0.3, rank: 77) **demonstrating a drop in capabilities to support the further education of the population beyond school age, and as a result, generate the R&D outputs evident in successful innovation economies.**

Outputs:

As mentioned above, there is disparity in the two output pillars, demonstrating a polarisation in the societal engagement of the population of Mauritius. However, the missing indicators of *PCT (Patent Corporation by Treaty) Patents by Origin* and *Utility Models by Origin* will have impact on this outcome. Two missing data points seen in the Creative Outputs pillar could equally impact the final positioning of the country globally, with a lack of data regarding *Global Brand Value* (Intangible Assets sub-pillar) and *Entertainment & Media Market* (Creative Goods and Services sub-pillar) leading to an amount of uncertainty as to the real positioning should such data have been available. These missing indicators would have provided a better indication of the international reputation and engagement with the innovation sector of Mauritius, which may have influenced the overall positioning of the country within Africa and globally.

For outputs overall, Mauritius produces its strongest result in the *Trademarks by Origin* indicator (Creative Outputs pillar, Intangible Assets sub-pillar; score: 85.0, rank: 17). This outcome is in direct contrast with the significantly lower performance against the *Patents by Origin* indicator (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Creation sub-pillar; score 0.1, rank: 108). The *New Businesses* output indicator (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Impact sub-pillar; score: 9.3, rank: 18), however, aligns almost exactly to the *Ease of Starting a Business* input indicator (Institutions pillar, sub-pillar Business Environment; score: 94.5, rank: 19). These results demonstrate **a direct relation to the efforts made and impacts achieved in investing in the stability of the business environment, but an imbalance in the outcomes seen in the production of more scientific innovation outcomes.**

Summary:

- Mauritius is the top-ranking African country for innovation, providing input support that is not converting to equal expected outputs levels,
- A polarisation exists between great successes and great challenges for this Island nation,
- A disparity is also seen in the types of innovation outputs achieved, with creative industries achieving greater successes than scientific or technological (academic-based) fields. However, the country is currently unable to convert this creativity into market and economic strength,
- Mauritius is successful enough to be competitive on a global level, especially in providing business and regulatory stability,
- There is an active investor community engaging well on an international level but not locally,
- A disconnect exists between the success of secondary and tertiary education, with an inability to turn innovative drive into academic success,
- Business inputs and outputs are reasonably well balanced, although there is an imbalance in inputs made towards scientific innovation versus the outputs achieved.

2.3.3.3. Morocco

Figure 18- Morocco GII mapping

Morocco sits within the lower-middle economy group and produces a reasonably balanced positioning across input and output pillars, with a dip only occurring within the Business Sophistication pillar (Figure 18). However, this balance is located mainly within the lower half of the global market meaning that Morocco is not achieving significant success in any particular pillar, neither input not output. The main strengths are seen in both of the output pillars: Knowledge & Technology Outputs and Creative Outputs.

In the 2021 GII, Morocco loses two places in the overall ranking, moving from an overall position of 75 to 77, generating an output rank of 67 and an input rank of 84. This shows that, overall, **Morocco is producing greater innovation output levels than expected for the inputs invested.**

Pillar and Sub-Pillar Main Take-aways

Inputs:

Morocco's highest ranking input pillar is *Institutions* (score: 61.6, rank: 74), followed closely by *Human Capital & Research* (score: 27.5, rank: 82) and *Infrastructure* (score: 36.5, rank: 84). These pillars are firmly positioned in the bottom half of the overall global rankings, below the middle position of 66. Within *Institutions*, the highest ranking sub-pillar is that of *Business Environment* (score: 73.0, rank: 59), ranking just above the half-way position. However, a higher-scoring sub-pillar exists within the *Human Capital & Research* pillar, where the *Education* sub-pillar is ranked 56 (score: 53.2). Although closely positioned, this demonstrates that Morocco's most successful area of innovation development is in the efforts made to support secondary educational success. However, similar to Mauritius, this score is then in direct contrast to the *Tertiary Education* sub-pillar which ranks much lower at 91 (score: 22.6). This indicates another situation within Africa where **the conversion of efforts to support education transition from secondary to tertiary education have been mainly unsuccessful.** Such an understanding is further supported when considering that position of the *Research & Development* (score: 6.7, rank: 71), *Knowledge Workers* (score: 22.1, rank: 97), *Innovation Linkages* (score: 14.0, rank: 112) and *Knowledge Absorption* (score: 18.0, rank: 103) sub-pillars, where low rankings demonstrate this **lack of retention in education, which is affecting the capacity to produce tangible innovation outcomes into the national economy.** Development in this area needs to be greatly developed to not only raise Morocco's overall position within the GII but also provide a greater innovation offer to both the national as well as international markets.

The lack of success and activity in R&D overall, can be seen to directly impact the *Credit* (score: 33.1, rank: 97) and *Investment* (score: 23.3, rank: 98) sub-pillars, as well as the *Research & Development* sub-pillar itself (score: 6.7, rank: 71). With a lack of clustered R&D activity,

Morocco is subsequently lacking in the general innovation outputs, however, despite this lack of input, the output pillars and sub-pillars rank higher than expected.

Other more successful sub-pillars for Morocco exist when considering the position of *Ecological Sustainability* (score: 29.1, rank: 62) and *Trade, Diversification and Market Scale* (score: 69.2, rank: 64). Despite these scores not being extreme in their difference to each other or the other sub-pillars, this does also indicate a slight advantage for Morocco regarding ecological innovations and trade diversification.

Outputs

Of the output pillars, *Knowledge & Technology Outputs* ranks higher at 67 (score: 20.1) than *Creative Outputs* at 70 (score: 22.8). Within the former, the strongest performing sub-pillar is *Knowledge Impact* (score: 31.6, rank: 60) followed closely by *Knowledge Diffusion* (score: 17.4, rank: 63). However, despite a pillar ranking lower than *Knowledge & Technology Outputs*, the best ranking *Creative Outputs* sub-pillar, *Intangible Assets*, positions higher at rank 41. The subsequent two sub-pillars in *Creative Outputs*, *Creative Goods & Services* (score: 5.1, rank: 104) and *Online Creativity* (8.8, rank: 104), come in at an equally low rank, pulling down the overall position for this pillar.

These results, while not dramatically different or significant, do show that within Morocco, there is a **greater tendency towards the production of knowledge and technology-based outputs as opposed to creative activities**, which is a direct contrast to countries like Mauritius.

Indicator Insights

Inputs:

At the indicator level, Morocco shows particular strengths in the input areas of *Government Funding/Pupil, Secondary* (Human Capital & Research Pillar, Education sub-pillar; score: 36.4, rank: 4), *GDP/Unit of Energy Use* (Infrastructure pillar, sub-pillar Ecological Sustainability sub-pillar; score: 14.5, rank: 26), *Gross Capital Formation* (Infrastructure pillar, General Infrastructure sub-pillar; score: 28.1, rank: 27) and *Domestic Credit to Private Sector* (Market Sophistication pillar, Credit sub-pillar; score: 87.8, rank: 32). These strengths, though not as successful as expected for this economic level, highlight Morocco's prioritisation of general environmental infrastructure in addition to secondary education.

However, within these two pillars, there are also other indicators who are performing very low in comparison. *Pupil-teacher Ratio, Secondary* ranks very low at 92 (Human Capital & Research pillar, Education sub-pillar; score: 18.8), followed not far behind by *Electricity Output*, ranked at 95 (Infrastructure pillar, General Infrastructure sub-pillar; score 1,131.3) and *Government's Online Service and E-Participation*, both ranking at 99 (Infrastructure pillar,

Information & Communication Technologies sub-pillar; score: 52.3 and 51.2 respectively). Even lower than these, though, is Logistics Performance ranked at 103 (Infrastructure pillar, General Infrastructure sub-pillar; score 22.9). Such outcomes demonstrate an imbalance within the sub-pillar levels that appear to negate the potential impact that the efforts being made within the indicator levels can have. As many of these are directly controlled or influenced by political strategies, the assumption is drawn that there is a disconnect occurring within the strategic priorities and tangible activities being employed nationwide.

Other pillars also offer particularly low performing sub-pillars and indicators, most notably the Market Sophistication and Business Sophistication pillars, where indicators *Ease of Getting Credit* (Market Sophistication pillar, Credit sub-pillar; score 45.0, rank: 101), *University-industry R&D Collaboration* (Business Sophistication pillar, Innovation Linkages sub-pillar; score: 29.2, rank: 114) and *Knowledge-intensive Employment* (Business Sophistication pillar, Knowledge Workers sub-pillar; score: 6.9, rank: 115) as incredibly low for a country in the lower-middle income economy group. The low performance of these of these indicators demonstrate also, that **Morocco is struggling to stabilise innovation financing and academic-industry collaborations, which would increase technology transfer and innovation development at an economic level.**

Outputs:

Morocco's output indicators present a slightly improved impact than those of the inputs, with *Industrial Designs by Origin* ranking highly in position 10 (Creative Outputs pillar, Intangible Assets sub-pillar; score: 12.5). Other successes can be seen in *High-tech Manufacturing* (Knowledge & Technology Outputs, Knowledge Impact sub-pillar; score: 38.5, rank: 29), *ICT Services Exports* (Knowledge & Technology Outputs; Knowledge Diffusion sub-pillar; score: 3.3, rank: 30) and *Trademarks by Origin* (Creative Outputs pillar, Intangible Assets sub-pillar; score: 58.7, rank: 37). These ranks highlight **Morocco's main output success in developing innovative creative, ICT and technological designs produced within the market.**

In contrast, and again highlighting another situation of disparity both between and within pillars, the lowest ranking output indicators are *Creative Goods Exports* (Creative Outputs pillar, Creative Goods & Services sub-pillar; score: 0.1, rank: 101) and *Intellectual Property Receipts* (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Diffusion sub-pillar; score 0.0, rank: 91), demonstrating that, **despite the strength in production of innovative designs, the capacity to protect and export creative services and products has not been achieved.** As balance within the indicators of the GII is indicated as holding the key to creating innovation success, it seems clear that a focus on **balancing these aspects of both input and output would have a great impact in increasing Morocco's potential.**

Summary:

- Morocco is producing greater innovation outputs than expected for the level of input being invested,
- The country demonstrates successful efforts in supporting secondary education, however, the conversion of engagement from secondary to tertiary education has been unsuccessful,
- This lack of retention into higher education is restricting Morocco’s potential for innovation and economic success, limiting financial and academic collaborations, which would produce technology transfer and international exports that are fundamental to a strong innovation ecosystem,
- Morocco demonstrates a greater tendency towards knowledge and technology outputs as opposed to creative,
- Successes in national infrastructure developments are negated through low rankings against other infrastructure indicators. This disparity indicates a lack of overarching strategy for the national infrastructure as a whole,
- Despite a strength in knowledge and technology-based design, the capacity to protect and export creative products and services has not been achieved,
- A balance across and within pillars would help Morocco maximise innovation.

2.3.3.4. Tunisia

Figure 19- Tunisia GII mapping

Tunisia, placed in the lower-middle economy group and ranking in position 71 overall, leads within Africa in the Human Capital & Research and Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillars (Figure 19). However, Tunisia drops six places in the 2021 GII, moving from position 65 in the 2020 GII to position 71. Tunisia also **demonstrates a higher capacity to produce innovation outputs compared to the investment put in.**

It is worth noting, that a reasonably strong disparity can be seen within the input and output pillar groups, with the input pillar of Human Capital & Research ranking high in position 35 (score: 42.7), whilst input pillar Business Sophistication ranks incredibly low at position 114 (score: 16.5). Similarly, output pillar Knowledge & Technology Outputs ranks well in position 55 (score: 24.0), whilst output pillar Creative Outputs ranks low at position 80 (score: 20.6).

Pillar and Sub-Pillar Main Take-aways

Inputs:

The pillar of *Human Capital & Research* ranks very well in position 35 (score: 42.7), with sub-pillars also producing good results on average. The sub-pillar of *Education* ranks incredibly well in position 8 (score: 71.2), being the best scoring sub-pillar overall. The other sub-pillars of *Tertiary Education* (score: 48.6, rank: 16) also ranks very well, with *Research & Development* positioned just within the top half of the ranking at position 65 (score: 8.2).

Following this, however, the next best pillars position much lower, demonstrating the breadth of the aforementioned disparity. The second-best performing input pillar is *Institutions*, which actually sits firmly within the lower half of the global rankings in position 75. Here, the sub-pillar of *Business Environment* ranks best in position 54 (score: 74.4), followed by sub-pillar *Political Environment* in position 84 (score 53.1). This large difference in rankings of sub-pillars evidences an **imbalance in efforts to provide a stable overall national ecosystem**. This also evidences that the business regulation is being driven through a more successful strategy than the government can obtain within and for itself.

The lowest scoring pillar of *Business Sophistication* (score: 16.5, rank: 114) shows a more balanced ecosystem set, although all are very low in ranked positions. *Knowledge Workers* is the best sub-pillar in rank position 102 (score: 19.6), with *Knowledge Absorption* following not far behind in position 113 (score: 16.1), and *Innovation linkages* even closer behind this in position 114 (score: 13.9). This appears to be a significant problem area for Tunisia, with each of the three sub-pillars ranking below 100. Together, these rankings show **a lack of success in providing a good ecosystem for academic, knowledge-driven R&D to flourish within the business markets.**

Outputs

Considering the lack of success in knowledge-driven R&D as mentioned in the previous section, it is perhaps surprising to note that the highest output pillar for Tunisia is that of Knowledge & Technology Outputs, although this score is not significantly successful in an of itself (score: 24.0, rank: 55). A review of the sub-pillars here demonstrates that the core success can be seen in the *Knowledge Creation* sub-pillar with a rank of 38 (score: 24.2), followed by Knowledge Diffusion, ranked in position 60 (score: 18.0) and Knowledge Impact, rank 63 (score: 29.7). The former shows a strong capacity to generate knowledge-based innovations, however the latter two sub-pillars demonstrate **a lack of ability to translate this knowledge into equal economic and academic impact.**

Creative Outputs on the other side ranks poorly in position 80 (score: 20.6) although this rank is to be taken into account alongside the knowledge that not all indicators have provided data. This relates to both the *Intangible Assets* sub-pillar, where a rank of 65 has been allocated (score 30.5), and the Creative Goods & Services sub-pillar, achieving a rank of 70 (score: 12.9). The only sub-pillar therefore to have a confirmed ranking is that of Online Creativity, where a rank of 107 has been achieved (score: 8.3). Such a ranking should therefore be taken with caution when drawing conclusions, however, the rankings given indicate Tunisia to be an environment generating more success, albeit lower than expected, in physical creative products and services than online creativity. Overall, therefore, Tunisia is a country more successful in producing R&D innovative outputs than creative products and services, although with the success of both output areas do not match the lower levels of investments being made.

Indicator Insights

Inputs:

At an indicator level, input strengths are evident in a number of different areas, most significantly is *Government funding/pupil, Secondary*, which ranks in 1st place globally (score: 52.4), followed closely by *Graduates in Science & Engineering* in position 2 globally (score: 43.3), both of which are in the Human Capital & Research pillar, with the former in the Education sub-pillar, and the latter in Tertiary Education. The Ease of Starting a Business indicator also ranks very highly in position 18 (Institutions pillar, Business Environment sub-pillar; score: 94.6). These significantly high rankings indicate that **Tunisia has a unique strength in supporting secondary education, which it is then able to then convert to success in the tertiary education areas of science and engineering, retaining the investment made at secondary level in higher education. The business environment is then strategically aligned to support this scientific knowledge to be transferred into new business generation,**

however, very low ranks in the Business Sophistication pillar indicate that this strategy struggles in both retaining and converting this knowledge into economic success.

Within the same pillar, the *Expenditure on Education* indicator (Education sub-pillar; score: 6.6) also achieves a significant rank in position 7. One would assume, that this pillar and sub-pillar would be incredibly high ranking, however, the pillar ranks at 35, although this particular sub-pillar does achieve position 8. When considering the other sub-pillars, one can see that mid to low scores across the other indicators is the reason for a low overall pillar rank, for example in *Tertiary Enrolment*, which ranks in position 82, and achieves a score of 31.8. This outcome indicates that, despite being very strong in certain, focused activities, Tunisia has a long way to go to balance out the various individual areas that support the research sector.

Another point of difficulty for Tunisia, appears to be in the regulatory and infrastructure areas, where *Regulatory Quality* achieves a very low score of 101 (Institutions pillar, Regulatory Environment sub-pillar; score: 32.1), and *Logistics Performance* and *Gross Capital Formation* also rank among the lowest at 100 and 124 respectively (both within the General Infrastructure sub-pillar; scores: 24.3 and 10.3 respectively). This incredibly low ranking for Gross Capital Formation, demonstrates that **Tunisia is struggling to provide investments into the country's general and environmental infrastructure, achieving one of the poorest investments seen globally.**

Outputs:

The success in science and engineering sectors is not only evident in the input rankings, but also in the output rankings, where *High-tech Exports* (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Diffusion sub-pillar; score: 4.0), ranks in position 40, demonstrating that there is further success in converting this knowledge into high-tech products, which are in demand internationally. Success in this pillar is also noticeable in the *Software Spending* (score: 0.3, rank: 35) and *ISO 9001 Quality Certificates* (score: 8.6, rank :32) indicators (both within the Knowledge Impact sub-pillar).

However, the best outcomes are achieved in the *Scientific & Technical Articles* indicator (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Creation sub-pillar; score: 40.9, rank: 18), and the *Creative Goods Exports* indicator (Creative Outputs pillar, Creative Goods & Services sub-pillar; score: 2.0, rank: 30). It appears from this result, that Tunisia is not only able to achieve success within science and research, but also within the export capacity of creative products and services, where international exports are able to impact Tunisia's overall global position. Other indicators within the Creative Outputs pillar, however, don't appear to fare as well, with *ICTs and Organisational Model Creation* achieving a very low position of 105 (Intangible Assets sub-pillar; score: 42.7). This demonstrates once again, **an imbalance in Tunisia's sectors and innovation activities, which is undermining their ability to compete globally.**

Summary:

- Tunisia demonstrates a higher capacity to produce innovation outputs than inputs,
- There is a strong disparity between sub-pillars and indicators within all input and output pillars, evidencing an imbalance across the whole ecosystem,
- Business regulation is more successful than governmental regulation,
- Academic and R&D investment is strong, however, there is a lack of ability to convert this into business and market success,
- Physical creative goods and services are more successful than online creativity, with science and knowledge-based products more successful than creative,
- Tunisia is very strong in providing investment into secondary education and converting this into science-based tertiary education in particular,
- The business environment is designed to convert tertiary education success into the business economy, however, there is a lack of capacity to convert this success into equal economic success,
- There is a significant lack of success in providing a strong general infrastructure, which would support the overall innovation ecosystem and ranking,
- Tunisia is far from achieving a good general balance across and within the pillars.

2.3.3.5. Egypt

Figure 20- Egypt GII mapping

Egypt, located in the lower-middle income group and ranked overall in position 94, an increase of 2 positions since 2020. Egypt generally performs in the lower half of the rankings for all pillars, with three located within the lowest quartile. The strongest performing pillar is the output pillar of Knowledge & Technology Outputs (score: 19.4, rank: 70) with Infrastructure being the highest-ranking input pillar (score: 33.5, rank: 92). Overall, **Egypt demonstrates a greater capacity to provide innovation outputs than inputs**, with an output rank of 86 and an input rank of 102 (Figure 20).

Pillar and Sub-Pillar Main Take-aways

Inputs:

Egypt's pillar rankings are lower than expected for its income group, with the pillars of *Infrastructure* (score: 33.5), *Human Capital & Research* (score: 21.8) and *Market Sophistication* (score: 40.9) ranking highest in position 92, 93 and 96 respectively. The highest-ranking sub-pillars are those of *Trade, Diversification and Market Size* (*Market Sophistication* pillar; score: 73.6, rank: 49) and *Research & Development* (*Human Capital & Research* pillar; score: 10.7, rank: 55), demonstrating that Egypt's main successes are in diversifying and growing its trade and economic ecosystem alongside developing R&D activities, which are ranked reasonably equally. However, despite these being the strongest pillars for Egypt, they still achieve a low rank against global competition. Other points of interest lie in *Innovation Linkages* (*Business Sophistication* pillar; score: 20.7, rank: 65) and *Ecological Sustainability* (*Infrastructure* pillar; score 26.7, rank: 76), which are the next highest ranking sub-pillars and demonstrate further success within Egypt's innovation ecosystem, albeit also ranked low globally.

The lowest ranking sub-pillars are those of *Regulatory Environment* (*Institutions* pillar; score: 35.8, rank: 124), *Investment* (*Market Sophistication* pillar; score 19.6, rank: 117), *Knowledge Workers* (*Business Sophistication* pillar; score: 13.9, rank: 113), *Credit* (*Market Sophistication* pillar; score: 29.5, rank: 108), *Tertiary Education* (*Human Capital & Research* pillar; score: 13.9, rank: 105) and *General Infrastructure* (*Infrastructure* pillar; score: 21.4, rank: 102). These low rankings show that Egypt has ranked in the lowest 30 countries globally in these areas, and further indicate that, despite success in R&D inputs in general, **any attempts to achieve high levels of success in higher education attendance and the business economy has been unsuccessful**. Of those R&D activities within universities, however, there is **some success in establishing valuable partnerships, which can translate into innovative companies and products**, which will also explain the rankings achieved in the output pillars.

Outputs

Knowledge & Technology Outputs is the most successful of the two output pillars, achieving a ranking of 70 (score: 19.4) compared to the 104-ranking position of *Creative Outputs* (score:

15.5). At sub-pillar level, *Knowledge Impact* ranks highest in position 53 (*Knowledge & Technology Outputs* pillar; score: 33.0), with the next highest ranking achieved by *Knowledge Creation* (*Knowledge & Technology Outputs* pillar; score: 13.8, rank: 68), although this ranks 15 positions lower than the former. The rest of the sub-pillars rank at or below position 87, with both *Creative Goods & Services* (*Creative Outputs* pillar; score: 8.2) and *Online Creativity* (*Creative Outputs* pillar; score 11.4) ranking in position 87. Such outcomes demonstrate **Egypt's capacity to produce more knowledge-driven innovations as opposed to creative innovations, which is understandable considering the input successes seen in R&D, trade and innovation collaborations.**

Egypt's lowest ranking sub-pillars are *Intangible Assets* (*Creative Outputs* pillar; score: 21.3, rank: 95) and *Knowledge Diffusion* (*Knowledge & Technology Outputs* pillar; score: 11.3, rank: 90), with the latter being an unexpected result considering the input success in R&D as mentioned. Such a ranking shows that, despite this success, **Egypt is unable to convert R&D developments into high-volume exportable products and services.**

Indicator Insights

Inputs:

At indicator level, a significant success is noticeable in the input indicator *State of Cluster Development & Depth* (Business Sophistication pillar, Innovation Linkages sub-pillar; score: 67.2, rank: 12). This is a significant rank to achieve, which stands out compared to the mainly low-rank positions achieved throughout the GII indexing. This also indicates the reason for the success achieved at sub-pillar level. Similar success is also seen in the *Domestic Market Scale* indicator (Market Sophistication pillar, Trade, Diversification & Market Scale sub-pillar; score: 1,292.5, rank: 19). Such high-ranking indicators point to high levels of success in very focused areas of Egypt's innovation economy, with **Egypt's cluster developments leading the R&D collaboration success** noted previously. This is of particular interest when considering the impacts that S&T clusters can have on GII rankings and performance within income-level groups, although, to date, no S&T clustering is evident in any African country. This demonstrates then, that **a potential opportunity exists for Egypt to build on their existing clustering success to further their innovation economy and GII ranking. Such an opportunity would require further political and financial investments to increase S&T activity overall, to significantly improve the capacity and potential for innovation development and progression.**

The next best ranking following the abovementioned indicators, is seen in *High-tech Imports* (Business Sophistication pillar, Knowledge Absorption sub-pillar; score: 9.3, rank: 40). Despite this being a strength for Egypt, this ranking is still a long way down from the success of the aforementioned indicators. Other reasonable achievements are also seen in the ranking

positions achieved against *Global Corporate R&D Investors* (Human Capital & Research pillar, Research and Development sub-pillar; score: 0.0, rank: 41), *FDI Net Inflow* (Business Sophistication pillar, Knowledge Absorption sub-pillar; score: 3.1, rank: 44), *Domestic Industry Diversification* (Market Sophistication pillar, Trade, Diversification & Market Scale sub-pillar; score: 92.2, rank: 45) and *GDP/unit of Energy Use* (Infrastructure pillar, Ecological Sustainability sub-pillar; score: 26.7, rank: 48), although, despite this ranking, *Global Corporate R&D Investors* is actually noted within the GII as being a specific point of weakness for Egypt.

Outputs:

Within the outputs pillar, a yet-greater success is seen in the *Labour Productivity Growth* indicator (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Impact sub-pillar; score: 4.5, rank: 9). Such a ranking, positions Egypt within the top ten countries globally and demonstrates success in Egypt's ability to generate a strong GDP growth rate per person employed, a direct outcome of the knowledge being generated through innovation inputs. This indicator is the highest-ranking indicator for Egypt.

Following this success, the next highest-ranked indicator, *Creative Goods Exports*, features much lower in position 40 (Creative Outputs pillar, Creative Goods and Services sub-pillar; score: 1.3). This is a particularly surprising result considering the success of the other input and output pillars, which indicate that Egypt's strengths are found more in the knowledge-based innovations. This outcome shows that Egypt is, in fact, reasonably successful in being able to produce and export creative goods as a percentage of total trade. The only other indicator deemed to be a strength for Egypt is that of *Citable Documents H-Index*, ranked in position 46 (Knowledge & Technology Outputs pillar, Knowledge Creation sub-pillar; score 17.7), an achievement more expected and aligned to Egypt's achievements across the board.

Egypt's lower performing indicators are more populous, however, with six output pillars scoring below position 90. In fact, one of Egypt's lowest scoring indicators overall is seen in the Creative Outputs pillar, where *Country-code TLDs* (top-level domains) is ranked in position 123 (Creative Outputs pillar, Online Creativity sub-pillar; score: 0.0). This demonstrates a particular struggle for Egypt to be able to support online innovations as a form of creative output. This is also reflected in the other low indicator rankings in the rest of this sub-pillar, with *Generic TLDs* ranked at position 92 (score: 1.2) and *Mobile App Creation* ranked at 85 (score: 0.2). Only *Wikipedia Edits* is ranked higher in position 76 (score: 45.1). **Such a disparate outcome for outputs demonstrates the lack of balance in both knowledge-based and creative outputs, with the outcomes providing extremes of success and challenges.** A more balanced outcome in outputs would, of course, enable Egypt to better produce and export innovations to the success of its overall economy.

Summary:

- Egypt has been able to produce a greater provision of innovation outputs than inputs, with knowledge-generated innovation success proving a much greater strength for the country than creativity-based. This is somewhat expected when considering the equal levels of success generated in R&D, trade and innovation collaboration inputs. Egypt is, however, unable to convert this R&D development into high volumes of exportable products and services,
- The strongest pillars for Egypt are still ranked low compared to other countries,
- Attempts to increase higher education attendance and a strong business economy has been unsuccessful,
- Egypt's cluster developments are leading the R&D collaboration success. Considering S&T clusters are a high driver of innovation success, and that no S&T clusters currently exist in Africa, Egypt has an opportunity to greatly impact their innovation success and GII ranking if they can increase their political and financial investments in clustering,
- There exists across all indicators, a severe disparity in input and output indicator rankings, demonstrating extreme imbalance, which is affecting their capacity to maximise their innovation potential.

Chapter 3

Start-up Innovation Support Across Africa - An
Overview

Methys (MET) & Steinbeis 2i GmbH (S2i)

3. Start-up Innovation Support Across Africa - An Overview

To complement the data-driven analysis conducted in chapter 2, the following sections provide a field-based perspective on the innovation ecosystem of Africa provided by Methys. This overview thereby provides an alternative perspective and overview of the landscape of activities and those key actors engaging in the region.

3.1. Innovation Overview Across Africa (MET)

3.1.1. Start-up/Technology Ecosystems

The African continent is one of the world's most entrepreneurial regions. Africa can rely on a diverse mix of innovation ecosystems in many of its countries. The continent's fifty-four countries are very diverse, and they are not all on the same level when it comes to innovation. Within the continent, we can identify six major African tech ecosystems. The first are termed the 'Big 4', which are Nigeria, South Africa, Egypt, and Kenya, however, we could also include Senegal and Tunisia, the first two countries in Africa to enact a Start-up Act (discussed in detail in 3.2.2.3) and leading regions for African start-up growth.

As the African start-up ecosystem's value is concentrated in these six regions, the goal of this chapter is to take a close look at the region to understand the differences and similarities, as well as to gain an overview of the overall landscape of activity. Then we will take a closer look at the continent's challenges and opportunities.

The first focus will be on the 'Big 4' (Nigeria, South Africa, Egypt, and Kenya), which, according to Max Curvellier and Mawime Bayen (Figure 21), are receiving most of the funding in 2021. The analysis on the Big 4 provided below will help us understand this result.

Nigeria

Nigeria will have the highest ecosystem value in Africa again in 2021, thanks to a large customer market, very low entry barriers in many sectors which foster amazing innovation, low regulation, which allows innovative founders to thrive, a strong anchor with the US ecosystem, and the ability to create 'unicorns' (Interswitch, Flutterwave, Andela, OPay, Jumia).

We have found that many start-ups operate in the FinTech sector, taking advantage of the country's under-provision of banking services. When asked about the boom of FinTech in Nigeria, the Nigerian start-ups are unanimous "*Payment is key to the whole economy. Nigeria*

is the largest economy on the continent, which means there are a lot of transactions happening. FinTechs are solving those transaction issues. We expect to see more, and the final customer will benefit from it. Payments enable other sectors and new companies can do business better thanks to FinTech”, says Ifeanyi Anazodo, the founder of Farmcrowdy, a start-up that aims to create an access to finance for farmers.

Figure 21- African Start-up fundraising map 2021

South Africa

This mature ecosystem is one of the leading ecosystems in Africa, with the country recording the second-highest number of start-ups after Nigeria (with the majority concentrated in Cape Town, which is home to approximately 60% of South Africa's tech start-ups). South Africa's main assets are its high internet penetration, developed VC network and large number of start-up accelerator programmes. This country has sub-sector strengths in FinTech and EdTech.

Egypt

The Egyptian ecosystem serves as a link between the African and Middle Eastern markets, making it very appealing to entrepreneurs and investors. The Egyptian market also has a great and strong academia (Cairo University, Alexandria University, Mansoura University) as well as a dynamic scene of local investors, which attracts international investors not only from the Middle East but also from the United States (US). The Egyptian market holds a lot of promise.

Kenya

Kenya, the economic capital of East Africa, has developed a thriving start-up scene and established itself as a tech hub in recent years as a result of its high internet penetration, a growing number of international investors, a tech-savvy population and mobile money innovation. This is clearly enhanced by the mobile banking company M-Pesa created in 2007, which has revolutionized banking not only in Kenya but also across Africa and has brought financial inclusion to millions with access to banking services through mobile phones, paving the way for a lot of FinTech start-ups. Kenya also has a rich network of coworking spaces, incubator programmes and community hubs.

According to the M&M 2021 report²², Nigeria, South Africa, Egypt, and Kenya continue to have the most advanced ecosystems, accounting for 80 percent of the funding raised by African start-ups. Other African countries, however, have seen a number of notable developments. Indeed, some less well-funded emerging tech ecosystems are now seeing an increase in funding facilities and interest. For this report, we will concentrate on Senegal and Tunisia, two countries that have adopted a Start-up Act and are experiencing rapid growth.

Senegal

Senegal's ecosystem is the most developed in Francophone Africa. Senegal became the second African country to pass the Start-Up Act in December 2019. In addition, the country has a

²² <https://thebigdeal.substack.com/>

young, skilled, and qualified workforce. Wave, a Senegalese-based mobile money lender, has become the first francophone unicorn, indicating that things are beginning to change.

The creation of DER/FJ (General Delegation for Rapid Entrepreneurship of Women and Youth) a Government Venture Capital Fund, which invest in start-ups at a pre-seed level and other state-created start-up organizations was one of the most visible boosts to the start-up scene.

If we look at the Francophone countries in Africa, Senegal is one of the first countries in term of innovation. Mostly specialized in FinTech, HealthTech and AgriTech. We can also see that some of the key ecosystem players are located here, such as Partech or Orange Venture, companies which create all the conditions to make Dakar a Tech hub in Francophone Africa.

Tunisia

Tunisia has established itself as a digital hub because of the Tunisian Start-up Act, an innovative and legal framework launched by the Tunisian government to assist local entrepreneurs who choose to invest in the country. **Tunisia was the first African nation to enact a Start-up Act.** The Tunisian Start-up Act is a great example of collaboration between civil society, the private sector, and the government. The encouraging outcomes being seen currently, should persuade other African countries to follow suit and implement their own versions.

Despite its deep innovation potential, active start-up community, and access to European markets, the Tunisian ecosystem is still in its early stages, with only Flat6lab and the giant AfricInvest as major local funds. This leads to one of the most serious issues confronting Tunisian entrepreneurs looking to expand: the lack of funding. Furthermore, the Tunisian ecosystem continues to face challenges in developing its funding landscape and attracting more foreign investment. At the moment, there is a high demand for additional legal instruments to raise funds (in the frame of the intended Start-up Act 2.0).

The funding raised by start-ups in Africa in 2021 has already reached 4 billion dollars²³, this is promising and in the next few years, we expect to see continuous record-breaking capital injection into start-ups on the continent. With a young and passionate population, a truly entrepreneurial spirit, and a solid technical infrastructure, Africa's potential is limitless.

²³ <https://thebigdeal.substack.com/>

3.1.2. Challenges & Opportunities (Funding, Infrastructure, Education, and regulation)

It is impossible to make broad statements about the challenges that African entrepreneurs and investors are facing. There are fifty-four different countries in Africa, each with its own characteristics, however, there are some pan-African issues to consider which are obvious bottlenecks that can prevent Africa from keeping up with the rest of the world's trends. Below are a number of structural barriers that make Africa difficult for entrepreneurs and investors to flourish in Africa, which will be further elaborated in the coming pages:

- A lack of funding and financing
- A lack of infrastructure
- A scarcity of talents
- Inconsistent and complex regulation

A Lack of Funding and Financing

According to the findings of an AfricArena survey on African entrepreneurs, **the most significant barrier for entrepreneurs is a lack of adequate funding** (Figure 22). When asked what the most difficult aspect of proving their concept was, nearly 60% said funding.

Figure 22- Survey results on biggest challenges for entrepreneurs when proving their concept²⁴

²⁴ AfricArena: 'State of Tech Report', 2020

In Africa, the return on venture capital investment is low. Africa begins with returns of less than 3% on average across the region over five years, compared to around 11% in Asia-Pacific and nearly 16% in Europe (Maher, Laabi, Ivers, & Ngambeket, 2021). Even though the possibility of obtaining Venture Capitalist funding has increased, it remains very low in comparison to Europe, the US, or China. Most founders finance their ventures in the beginning with personal savings and money from family and friends, which limits innovation to only those who can afford personal savings (Figure 23).

Figure 23- Survey results on financing for start-ups²⁵

To raise capital, African start-ups appear to be following one of two models. The first is the ‘Nigerian model’, in which founders incorporate their businesses in the US or other investor-friendly regions and raise capital from within those regions. Foreign investors are likely to be drawn to the Nigerian market because of perceived favourable demographics, which, when combined with a US incorporation (considered more investor friendly), would result in increased demand for investment. *“The size of these economies and the opportunities that have emerged in these countries appear to be attracting private equity and venture capital investors”*, mentioned AVCA, the African Private Equity and Venture Capital Association.

The second model is where founders raise capital from investors in their country of incorporation: the ‘Kenyan model’. It is very difficult to invest remotely into seed-stage start-ups, so it is best for VCs to have a base where they are investing to understand the market

²⁵ AfricArena: ‘State of Tech Report’, 2020

better and deploy capital quicker. There is therefore an increasing need for countries to enact legislation to make it easier for businesses to incorporate locally as an entrepreneur, but also to start a local investment fund and invest in seed-stage businesses from the country.

To go around the funding obstacle, a growing number of incubators are setting up micro-VC funds to support their entrepreneurs with amounts varying usually between \$40k and \$150k (AfricArena, 2020). Most efficient early-stage investors are those that take a hands-on approach by helping entrepreneurs access customers, providing them strategic advice and critical in-house expertise and those with a specialisation in terms of sector or maturity stage.

Based within the lack of financing issue, **another obstacle to attracting funding in Africa is data**. It is extremely difficult to learn about start-up deals and valuations in a region where **information is scarce and fragmented**. Furthermore, due to a lack of available data, valuations at a certain stage (B+) appear to be disconnected from economic realities, rather than the result of inflation caused by foreign fund managers looking for opportunities with limited risks, which are in short supply when compared to early-stage start-ups seeking funding.

Poor Infrastructure

Infrastructure is required for innovation to function and drive economic growth, and Africa is severely lacking in basic developed infrastructure. In order to conduct business anywhere in the world, infrastructure is essential. There will be no meaningful business transactions without good roads, a functional rail system, an effective air transport system, and fast telephone and internet systems, despite the fact that cell phone and internet services are growing rapidly and widely in Africa. Businesses will not function continuously, efficiently, or effectively if there is no reliable water, sanitation system, or electricity supply, and acquiring alternative sources of these resources adds to operating costs, making the country less competitive. This is reflected in Africa's low rankings in many major classifications or indexes.²⁶

Many African nations have recognised the critical importance of infrastructure in meaningful national development and are currently investing a lot of resources in infrastructure development, with the assistance of China in particular. Furthermore, the AU's Programme for Infrastructure Development for Africa (PIDA) (see chapter 3.2) identified various levels of infrastructure readiness to support innovation in African economies.

A Scarcity of Talents

Advanced educational and technical skills are essential for establishing and maintaining a successful innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem. However, educational attainment

²⁶ African Union Commission, 2014.

levels in Africa are low across the continent. On top of that, there is a need to educate early-stage entrepreneurs about how the tech ecosystem works in general.

A major challenge is to attract talent. Some progress needs to be done on the incubators and accelerators side, to guide start-ups by recruiting strong core teams and developing internal cultures, especially since accessing talent in Africa is often enabled by the power of the network.

Raising money to hire employees with critical skills seems quite logical as there is a need for a high-level core team to execute the vision. This can be difficult in Africa as **there is a lack of graduates**, and the stock option way of remuneration is not working as well as in the US or in Europe due to limited Mergers and Acquisitions (M&A) activity and prospects for Initial Public Offerings (IPO) (AfricArena, 2020).

From an investor's perspective, **a gap exists in the entrepreneur's education on how venture capital investment works.** It may prove hard to do deals when entrepreneurs do not know what to expect in terms of funding mechanisms and requirements. Which metrics are expected? Which documents will be required? Which structure is needed?

The lack of strong incubators, accelerators, and mentorship programmes across the region, that are truly capable of improving the investment readiness of start-ups reflects the scarcity of talents. Too many of them are still struggling to find a long-term economic model that will allow them to pay experienced mentors. Few of them provide funding and access to the necessary talent to help companies grow. **Rather than establishing new incubators or accelerators, those already in place could collaborate with international ones with extensive experience to find long-term revenue streams by learning and sharing experiences with leaders in the space**, such as the Co-Creation Hub (Cchub) in Nigeria. Corporates and public stakeholders may play a role in establishing joint programmes with these organizations or in financing them in exchange for attractive investment opportunities for external growth for corporations or on behalf of development.

Complex and Inconsistent Regulation

African entrepreneurs have long faced **unfavourable regulatory environments, which make it difficult to launch, grow, and scale an innovative business.** Start-ups require a legislative environment that promotes business creation, data sovereignty, and legislations governing these topics. At the moment, this is extremely difficult because we are relying on laws that are fifty years old, resulting in lags. **Governments in Africa must do more to improve the regulatory and investment environments for start-ups because legislation enables start-ups to operate with the certainty, provided by a well-defined framework for growth.**

Start-up Acts could be part of the solution (see section 3.2.2.2). Start-up Acts are a collection of policies designed to increase the incentives for entrepreneurs to start a venture and investors to put their money into promising companies, and other ecosystem actors to lend their support where it is needed. These policies are part of broader government strategies in Tunisia and Senegal to position their countries as innovation hubs by leveraging an emerging tech scene to improve economic development. South Africa, Nigeria and Kenya, have subsequently begun discussions with key stakeholders to also follow suit. Pro-start-up legislation, such as **the Start-up Act, will help Africa increase innovation, create jobs, and build trust between governments and entrepreneurs** because there is still a lack of proper and consistent regulation across the continent.

Based on the identified challenges, we can see that African start-ups may have the potential to be innovative, but they still require adequate funding, better infrastructure, formation and retention of a talent pipeline and a good regulatory framework. However, **due to the continent's youthful and growing population, rising internet penetration, and the application of emerging technologies, Africa provides a fertile environment for tech entrepreneurs.** There are, therefore, opportunities, which Africa should capitalize on.

Following this overview of the challenges, the following sections will explore the opportunities facing innovation actors across Africa.

New Approaches to Securing VC

Securing funding is a major issue and success factor for companies world-wide, however, in Africa, this requirement has seen great developments in recent years (Figure 24). A new approach to securing venture capital is emerging. We can consider the case of corporate innovation. Corporates are still in the early stages of becoming involved in African innovation. More widespread Open Innovation and increased corporate VC activity have the potential to have a massive impact in the coming years.

Investing in early-stage start-ups has appeared to have slowed down, with the current investor landscape being very fragmented and its requirements or ways of doing business varying. **Looking to solve this issue, a collective of VCs from across the continent has been set up, Digital Collective Africa, and is currently developing new standards for the industry such as terms sheets, due diligence checklists and other tools.** Development of new angel investment groups across the continent and the emergence of training programmes to reinforce their impact such as provided by the African Business Angel Network (ABAN), AfriLabs, African Angel Academy or VC4A are also solutions to effectively tackle the financing challenge. To address data scarcity, several great private initiatives focusing on making deal data available, have emerged in recent years, including the Partech Report, The Wetracker Report, and Briter Bridge's intelligence system, among others.

Figure 24- Number of tech start-ups securing funding in Africa²⁷

Construct a Functional Infrastructure System

In recent years, Africa has developed an ever-greater a drive to construct a functional infrastructure system capable of supporting an innovation-based economy. Due to Africa being regarded as one of the world's fastest growing economic hubs, **meeting the demand for critical infrastructure has been identified as a top priority.**

Mobile phones are among the most powerful of these new drivers, with the number of mobile phone subscribers in Africa increasing by 2,500% between 2000 and 2012. Many Africans use them for commerce as well as communication, thereby establishing a new value chain (EY Global, 2020). Increased mobile penetration improves connectivity, but the real driver is the variety of payment options now available to mobile users. M-Pesa, Kenya's mobile-money platform, is the first and most well-known example of telecommunications creating a value chain. It began as a way to send money between people and has since evolved into a marketplace. Kenyans can use it to pay for insurance, a haircut or a loan. *"It has impacted each and every sector of the economy,"* says Francis Kamau, a partner at Ernst & Young LLP (EY), Kenya. *"The bankers use it, and the president uses it. My mother-in-law is 85 and she uses it."*

Strengthen the Talent Pool

Africa produces talents, but most of them go abroad, primarily to the US or Europe. **One opportunity to strengthen the talent pool is to retain talents into their home country.**

Talent has proved to be a key success factor in the capacity of start-ups to deliver their promises. Big steps have been made in Africa with a growth in both private and public

²⁷ AfricArena: 'State of Tech Report', 2020

initiatives striving to develop vocational schools, especially for the developers. Tunisia, which has long been a talent exporter, has also spent the past year focusing on capitalising on its local human capital. GoMyCode, a rapidly expanding coding school, has trained 5000 developers and opened three local offices as well as offices in Morocco and Algeria, as an example. However, as these initiatives are quite recent, there is a limited number of experienced professionals able to lead projects and train newcomers (AfricArena, 2021).

In terms of training programmes for entrepreneurs, the Seed Transformation Program taught at Stanford and dedicated to CEOs and founders from emerging markets, is an intriguing example of what can be done in terms of training programmes, to reinforce the ability of the start-up team to scale and be attractive to investors.

Transform the Government into Ecosystem Enablers

Tunisia and Senegal are two excellent examples of governments transforming into enablers. In Senegal, for example, the establishment of DER/FJ was a visible boost to the start-up scene, allowing youth and women to become entrepreneurs. Finance and technical support are provided by the structure. Since its inception, the DER has provided financial assistance to over 120 start-ups.

In Tunisia, some actors, such as STARTUP TUNISIA by Smart Capital, plays an important role in strengthening the start-up ecosystem and creating a culture of entrepreneurship. STARTUP TUNISIA is a national initiative looking to make Tunisia a 'Start-up Nation' with a vision built on three pillars: legal framework (Start-up Act.), start-up investment (Anava fund of funds), and start-up ecosystem support (financial support, connectiveness and promotion).

There are opportunities and the African unicorns of the day have demonstrated that it is possible to successfully roll out innovative solutions. **Africa's technology and start-up ecosystems have seen consistent growth in recent years and are seen as playing an increasing role in defining the continent's attractiveness.**

Summary:

- Key actors in the African Ecosystem are Partech, Orange Venture, Flat6lab, Africinvest, CcHub Nigeria, Digital Collective Africa, ABAN, Afrilabs, African Angel Academy, VC4A,
- The most significant barrier for entrepreneurs is a lack of adequate funding,
- In Africa, the return on venture capital investment is low,
- Data access is another obstacle to attracting funding in Africa, with information being scarce and fragmented,
- Infrastructure is required for innovation to function and drive economic growth, and Africa is severely lacking in basic developed infrastructure. Meeting the demand for critical infrastructure has therefore been identified as a top priority.
- A major challenge is to attract talent and there is a lack of graduates. One opportunity for Africa is to therefore strengthen the talent pool by retaining talents into their home country.
- A gap also exists in the entrepreneur's education on how venture capital investment works
- The lack of strong incubators, accelerators, and mentorship programmes across the region, that are truly capable of improving the investment readiness of start-ups reflects the scarcity of talents,
- Rather than establishing new incubators or accelerators, those already in place could collaborate with international ones with extensive experience to find long-term revenue streams by imitating leaders in the space,
- Unfavourable regulatory environments, which make it difficult to launch, grow, and scale an innovative business,
- Governments in Africa must do more to improve the regulatory and investment environments for start-ups because legislation enables start-ups to operate with the certainty, provided by a well-defined framework for growth. Start-up Acts could be a helpful instrument to cement the support and consolidation of start-ups, as they will help Africa increase innovation, create jobs, and build trust between governments and entrepreneurs,
- Due to the continent's youthful and growing population, rising internet penetration, and the application of emerging technologies, Africa provides a fertile environment for tech entrepreneurs,

3.2. Public Sector Innovation Support: Policies, Regulations and Investment Programmes (S2i)

3.2.1. Intragovernmental Strategies, Plans & Support Programmes

Public-centred support towards innovation in Africa were, until the beginning of the last decade, rather sporadic, with policy efforts centred on traditional research policy which did not necessarily lead to sufficient practical on the ground changes. However, since 2015, the year the UN member states adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and particularly SDG goal 9 (which underscores the importance of fostering innovation and investment in R&D), the attention shifted towards innovation and its support via innovation policies as well as via national innovation systems. Not only did the national governments then become increasingly involved in innovation support, but also international and intergovernmental actors, such as development banks, also gradually began to focus on innovation and entrepreneurship as areas requiring funding and support (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). Intragovernmental actors therefore play an increasingly important role in supporting innovation in Africa.

3.2.1.1. African Union

The AU as the continental union for Africa, is one of the main intergovernmental actors with the intention to strengthen the innovation capacities of its fifty-four member states. In the last decade it has published various strategies and plans that either directly or indirectly focus on and promote innovation on the continent.

Agenda 2063

In 2013, the AU adopted the [Agenda 2063](#), a long-term vision with aspirations of achieving the “Africa We Want” by 2063, aiming to attain inclusive and sustainable development on the whole continent in the context of a rapidly changing world. The agenda articulates that Africa’s growth and economic transformation necessitates continuous innovation in all

development-relevant sectors as well as an ongoing investment in emerging technologies. As a result, Agenda 2063 is committed to laying a strong foundation in STI in Africa, as STI is seen critical for the achievement of the agenda’s aspirations (African Union Commission, n.d.). Particularly in the first ten-year implementation plan of Agenda 2063, various programmes are included, which aim at promoting and implementing STI in economic development activities on the continent. Among the (flagship) programmes and projects that support STI and/or the economy in general on the continent, are the following:

- [The African Continental Free Trade Area \(AfCFTA\)](#),
- [Programme for Infrastructure Development for Africa \(PIDA\)](#),

- [The establishment of an annual African Economic Forum,](#)
- [The Pan-African E-Network](#)
- [The African Virtual and E-University](#)

(African Union Commission, n.d.).

Considerable effort and progress in establishing important institutions were achieved by the AU and its member states from 2014 to 2019. These institutions seek to support the growing STI-enabling environment on the continent, and include initiatives such as:

- [African Scientific Research and innovation Council,](#)
- [African Observatory for Science, Technology, and Innovation,](#)
- [Pan African Intellectual Property Organization](#)
- [Pan African Quality Assurance and Accreditation Framework,](#)
- Committee of Ten Heads of State and Government championing Education, S&T,
- [Pan African Private Sector Trade and Investment Committee](#)

(African Union, 2019).

Moreover, the AU adopted three strategies for advancing education and STI to efficiently contribute to the implementation of Agenda 2063:

- Science, Technology, and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2024 (see below),
- [Continental Strategy for Education \(CESA-16-25\),](#)
- [Continental Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training,](#)

In the following section, the STISA-2024 will be further discussed as this strategy can be seen as a core strategy to enable the further growth of innovation and technology in Africa.

Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2024

The AU has been influential in developing STI policies at pan-African level since the 1980s and takes STI policies very seriously. This is visible in the [Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2024 \(STISA-2024\)](#), which was adopted in 2014 and will be of major importance for the STI efforts on the continent until the year 2024. It represents a framework for STI development in the AU Member States and forms part of the ten-year incremental phasing strategies of the Agenda 2063 vision. It is based on the consensus that investments in STI are essential to drive both the economy and sustainable growth in Africa forward, and “accelerate the transition of African countries to innovation-led, and knowledge-based economies”. This shall be achieved by improving STI readiness and implementing specific policies and programmes, based on four pillars:

- building and/or upgrading research infrastructures,
- enhancing professional and technical competencies,

- promoting entrepreneurship and innovation,
- providing an enabling environment for STI development in Africa.

Under this strategy, continental, regional and national programmes will be designed, implemented and synchronized to ensure that their strategic orientations and pillars are mutually reinforcing, and achieve the envisaged development impact” (African Union Commission, 2014).

STISA-2024 encourages and involves all key stakeholders (public, private, civil society) to inclusively deploy STI in all sectors relevant for socio-economic development (Ikounga, n.d.).

The strategy is being implemented at three levels:

- At national level- Member States shall include STISA-2024 into their National Development Plans,
- At regional level- Regional Economic Communities (RECs), research institutions, networks etc., should utilize the strategy in designing and coordinating initiatives as well as mobilizing donor resources for national and regional STI implementations (Figure 25),
- At continental level- the AU Commission (AUC), New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) (AU's Development Agency) and their partners shall create awareness as well as mobilize necessary resources (institutional, human, and financial), particularly for developing and implementing national and regional plans and programmes.

(AUDA-NEPAD, 2019).

Figure 25- STI importance within STISA-2024

Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa

While the STISA-2024 is related specifically to innovation and technology, another strategy exists, which complements the STISA-2024 but is more focused on the facilitation of the digital transformation in Africa. The AU's [Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa \(2020-2030\)](#) was published in 2019, supported by the World Bank Group, other development partners and various sector stakeholders. It can be seen as a wide-ranging digital strategy, serving as a blueprint for the AU, national governments, and other stakeholder in accelerating Africa's digital transformation. On the basis of a consensus to increase the usage and adoption of digital technologies and innovation, it emphasizes major policy reforms, investments and cooperation requirements at national and regional level, for the continent to achieve its digital development ambitions. Specifically, the following activities shall be implemented until the year 2030 (see Figure 26):

- Building a Digital Single Market in Africa with free movement of persons, services and capital and seamless access and engagement in online activities possible,
- Harmonizing the digital environment, including laws, policies, regulations, etc.,
- Empowering people so they are able to use digital technologies safely and securely,
- Building inclusive digital skills and human capacity,
- Implementing a Digital Identity Document (ID) system.

(African Union, 2019).

Figure 26- Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa- themes, critical sectors and pillars²⁸

²⁸ African Union, 2019

African Continental Free Trade Agreement

The [AfCFTA](#) was founded in 2018 and came into effect as of January 1st 2021 to become the largest Free Trade Area in the world, measured by the number of countries participating. It connects 1.3 billion people across fifty-four countries with a combined GDP valued at US\$3.4 trillion (Madden, 2019) (World Bank, 2020). The AfCFTA is expected to shape the future of Africa in the upcoming years and will consolidate progress toward Agenda 2063, in that it allows for trade that is faster, more efficient, and cheaper, based on reduced tariffs among member countries, intending to overcome the fragmentation of Africa's markets, resulting in further stimulation of economic activity (Madden, 2019) (World Bank, 2020). As of December 2021, AfCFTA has eliminated tariffs on 95% of all intra-African traded goods (Devonshire-Ellis, 2021), with full implementation meaning reform to markets and economies across the continent (World Bank, 2020). However, to realize this, it will be necessary to create measures and policies that facilitate trade as well as encourage and protect domestic innovation (Songwe, 2020). Either way, AfCFTA will have a profound impact on STI and entrepreneurship because it will, due to eased trade restrictions and integrated regional trade networks, spur innovation (African Union, 2019) (Signé & Schneidmann, 2018).

Programme for Infrastructure Development for Africa

In Africa, there has been substantial progress towards connecting the continent with transport, energy, and ICT infrastructure. The [PIDA](#) plays in that regard an important part in this progress. This is visible in three hundred pan-African infrastructure projects, as well as several capacity-building programmes. Moreover, due to PIDA and other supporting programmes, the establishment of continental e-networks was facilitated, such as the Pan African e-Network (to be discussed in chapter 3.2.3), which is focused on educational and research institutions. Overall, though, the progress of PIDA is less than expected, given its vast scale. To support further progress, AU proposes to improve capacity building activities related to infrastructure as well as to integrate local problem-solving expertise into infrastructure projects (African Union, 2019).

3.2.1.2. African Development Bank

The African Development Bank (AfDB) outlined in 2015 five development priorities (called [the High 5s](#)) in a priority strategy for the period from 2015 to 2025. These priorities are:

- Light up and Power Africa,
- Feed Africa,
- Industrialize Africa,

- Integrate Africa,
- Improve the Quality of Life for the People of Africa.

These priorities are seen as essential in transforming Africa and have also been emphasized as critical priorities in the Agenda 2063 (African Development Bank, n.d.). The AfDB has, as part of the High 5 strategy and in alignment with AU's STISA-2024, been organising a Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) forum since 2012, which aims to raise awareness on the significance of smart investments in STI in Africa by targeting a multitude of public, private, and civil society stakeholders. The fourth STI Forum shall be held in West Africa on the topic of innovation (African Development Bank, 2019); it had to be cancelled in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Jobs for Youth in Africa Strategy

The [Jobs for Youth in Africa Strategy](#), adopted in 2016, aims to create 25 million jobs and impact 50 million youth from by the year 2025. It seeks to support Africa's entrepreneurship ecosystems and support the creation of sustainable jobs for young Africans by preparing youth start-ups, micro-enterprises and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) with skills and financial support. It also intends to enable the business environment through three strategic intervention areas:

- *Integration,*
- *Innovation,*
- *Investment.*

Through *Integration*, the bank itself and member countries will act as role models for job creation for young Africans. Through *Investment*, private sector investments that fuel job creation and youth employment will be catalysed. Through *Innovation*, partners are brought onboard to incubate, implement, assess, and scale promising solutions. Such support includes:

- Programme models, which are based on best practices and focused on developing youth entrepreneurs, and which are to be implemented and scaled in partnership with the private sector,
- Development of an index to measure youth employment in labour markets as well as enabling policies,
- An Innovation and Information Lab (via Boost Africa, see below) which supports the incubation of new ideas and assesses best practices.

(African Development Bank, 2016).

These actions are initially focused on the sector agriculture, industrialisation, and ICT, as these were deemed to be sectors with high potential for youth inclusion, which could be embedded in the initial flagship programmes. These programmes are, among others:

- Rural Microenterprise Flagship Program Model,
- Skills Enhancement Zone Flagship Program Model,
- Computational Thinking Flagship Program

(African Development Bank, n.d.).

Boost Africa

[Boost Africa](#) is a joint initiative between the AfDB and the European Investment Bank (EIB), which was launched in 2016 and forms part of the Jobs for Youth in Africa strategy. It seeks to contribute to the development of an efficient entrepreneurial ecosystem in Africa, and specifically to accelerate the growth of African start-ups by becoming a key platform to launch competitive companies from within Africa. The platform shall include the following aspects:

- Investment programme to support the creation of innovative and highly scalable start-ups and SMEs, targeting fund managers, business angels, accelerators, and incubators,
- Technical Assistance Pool to provide capacity building and disseminate best practices,
- Innovation & Information Lab to incubate promising new ideas as well as provide (financial) support at national ecosystem level, including developing human capital.

The focus of Boost Africa is on sectors where innovations can improve the quality of lives via ICT, financial services, inclusion and education. The initial pilot countries are Egypt, Kenya, South Africa, Nigeria, Ghana and Cote d' Ivoire, and the initiative aims to leverage €1 billion in investments, which will fund 1,500 SMEs and contribute to 25,000 direct and at least 70,000 indirect jobs (African Development Bank, n.d.).

Youth Entrepreneurship and Innovation Multi-Donor Trust Fund

The [Youth Entrepreneurship and Innovation Multi-Donor Trust Fund](#) was launched in 2017 and is part of the Jobs for Youth in Africa Strategy. Until 2025, the fund (which had a volume of ca. \$40 million in 2018) brings together donors and partners, and supports activities within the following three components:

- Business development services to enterprise support organizations (incubators, accelerators) to boost capacity and expand access to financial services,
- Research and project preparation funding, including the expansion of knowledge and policy advisory tools for entrepreneurship and youth employment,
- Technical assistance for governments, public agencies etc., to strengthen policies and regulations focused on job creation, skills, etc. (African Development Bank, n.d.).

3.2.1.3. Islamic Development Bank

Engage Digital Hub

The Islamic Development Bank (IsDB) launched the [digital hub Engage](#) in 2018 to strengthen economic and social progress on basis of STI. It is working to establish an innovation ecosystem that enables innovators, start-ups and corporations to engage, connect and better develop innovations. This is achieved by providing them with customised mentoring services and expert advice, as well as access to financial resources, partnerships etc. More specifically, it provides the following services:

- Assist innovation ecosystems by leveraging on technologies with high impact potential
- Matchmaking opportunities that allow actors in the innovation ecosystem to connect with potential partners and members
- Provision of solutions and technologies to be leveraged to address development challenges, deliver innovations and/or contribute to the creation of good and services

(Islamic Development Bank, n.d.).

Transform Fund

The [Transform Fund](#) is a \$500million fund linked to the Engage hub, which will provide seed money for start-ups and SMEs, funding for the commercialisation of services and products developed and support governments in developing their technical and functional STI capacity (Islamic Development Bank, n.d.).

Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy

The [STI Policy of IsDB](#) was adopted in 2019 and is centred on UNESCO's Global Observatory of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy Instruments methodology. It aims to strengthen the Bank's endeavours in mainstreaming STI. This STI policy is a key component of IsDB's institutional policies aimed at delivering coordinated and integrated efforts to strengthen socio-economic development. The objective is to improve STI activities in the member countries through multiple interventions, which include capacity building, policy support and adequate policy instruments. Success indicators of the policy in the member countries will, among others, be the following:

- Increase in the average R&D intensity,
- Increase in the share of business sector in R&D,
- Increase in the number of researchers with focus on gender balance,
- Increase in the world share of scientific articles.

(Islamic Development Bank - STI Department, 2019).

3.2.1.4. World Bank

Digital Economy for Africa Initiative

The World Bank has in recent years, started to address digital development globally. In Africa, it started the [Digital Economy for Africa \(DE4A\) Initiative](#), which was launched in 2018 and aims to ensure every individual, business and government in Africa will be digitally enabled by 2030. It supports the AU's Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa as well as associated policy reforms and interventions to achieve a more coherent and coordinated approach in the digital sphere (African Union, 2019), as well as seeking to leverage public and private investments in the digital economy. It recommends African countries to increase their spending on digital transformation and to prioritize important reforms (World Bank, n.d.). The projects are diverse and include, among others, electronic identification and banking, mobile money services, training, and mentoring through digital hubs. In Summer 2021, one-hundred-and-forty-nine projects were active in thirty-four African countries (Neto & Rogy, 2021). The projects' successes are measured in the form of a 'Digital Economy Scorecard' which assesses five foundational pillars of the digital economy: digital infrastructure, digital public platforms, digital financial services, digital businesses and digital skills (World Bank, n.d.).

XL Africa – Scaling Up Digital Innovation

The [XL Africa – Scaling Up Digital Innovation](#) project supports twenty African later-stage technology start-ups in the form of mentorship and access to investors. These start-ups must already be offering services and/or products and should, if possible, make use of emerging digital solutions/technology. The objective is to provide them with the necessary skills, knowledge (via mentoring), partners and funding (access to proven investors with no brokerage fees or equity taken) to help their existing businesses grow and scale. Moreover, access to a global repository of information, case studies, tools, and people. Start-ups might be based within, but are not limited to, the following sectors:

- FinTech,
- Transport,
- Energy,
- Education,
- Smart cities,
- Media.

(XL Africa, n.d.).

Gender Innovation Lab

The World Bank's [Africa Gender Innovation Lab](#) (GIL, see Figure 27) is one of two GILs worldwide. It conducts impact evaluations to measure the effects of development interventions in sub-Saharan Africa, as well as to provide information on how to close the gender gap in earnings, productivity, assets, and agency. GIL is focused on five thematic areas (Agriculture, Private Sector Development, Property Rights, Social Norms, and Youth Employment) and has provided support to over 100 projects in more than thirty-five countries worldwide. As of late 2018, GIL's direct influence totalled 2.17 billion USD (World Bank, n.d.).

Figure 27- Gender Innovation Lab mission²⁹

Eastern and Southern Africa Higher Education Centers of Excellence

The \$140 million [Eastern and Southern Africa Higher Education Centers of Excellence](#) project seeks to strengthen twenty-four selected Eastern and Southern African higher education institutions between 2016 and 2021. Specifically, the quality postgraduate education as well as the collaborative research capacity shall be increased in five priority areas, which are seen as crucial to address the region's development challenges that the region is facing. These are:

- Industry (i.e., science, technology, engineering, and mathematics),
- Agriculture,
- Health,
- Education,
- Applied statistics.

²⁹ World Bank, n.d.

Moreover, partnerships and collaborations with other national, regional, and international institutions and the private sector are to be developed and strengthened. The project is implemented in eight countries: Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda, and Zambia (World Bank Group, n.d.).

International Development Association

The International Development Association (IDA) is a World Bank fund which finances developing countries in areas such as health, agriculture, transport, energy, water, and sanitation. The areas of education and ICT infrastructure, seen as major catalysts for innovation, receive IDA financing as well. Besides this, IDA supports business climate improvements and institutional reforms. It has financed African tech hubs in recent years. Overall Africa receives about 50 percent of total IDA commitments each year (World Bank, n.d.).

International Finance Corporation

The International Finance Corporation (IFC) provides financing and advisory services and supports the collaboration between public and private sector. It lists education as a priority area for sub-Saharan Africa. In that regard, it seeks to support the expansion of access to qualitative tertiary and technology-based education in Africa. More specifically, its work includes supporting innovative educational models, including digital skills, as well as regulatory reforms and promoting online education (International Finance Corporation, n.d.). In the Middle East and North Africa, SMEs as well as youth employability are seen as priority areas for the IFC: Regarding the former, it works with banks, industry associations and governments to support small businesses grow and provide jobs. Youth employability is strengthened provided through the E4E Initiative for Arab Youth (International Finance Corporation, n.d.). Here, IFC helps to provide the youth with skills via training programmes in up-and-coming fields like ICT that are relevant to the marketplace. This is to be achieved by investing in employment-focused and replicable education, engaging multiple stakeholders and bolstering the role of the private sector in providing high-quality post-secondary education. The Initiative seeks to implement its activities in four countries at the initial stage: Jordan, Egypt, Tunisia, Morocco (E4E Arab Youth, n.d.).

3.2.1.5. United Nations Development Programme

Accelerator Lab Initiative

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) launched the [Accelerator Lab Initiative](#) in 2019 with the intention to set up the world’s largest learning network. The objective of this initiative is to put innovation at the heart of its action by catalysing grassroots solutions and innovative ideas via experimentation and rapid iteration. With this initiative, the UNDP seeks to support Agenda 2063 and change how it approaches problem-solving in Africa. The idea is to reimagine how development could look like, while answering complex questions to better understand challenges, and facilitate inclusive growth. Various programmes and projects shall be implemented and funds for greater efficiency and effectiveness provided. Active learning is seen as a key component of the network. To date, twenty-seven African Accelerator Lab Initiative pilot offices can be found in Africa (out of a total of sixty offices around the world, see Figure 28) (United Nations Development Programme, n.d.).

Figure 28- Locations of Acceleration Lab Initiative Offices³⁰

3.2.1.6. The Smart Africa Alliance

[Smart Africa](#) is a commitment to innovation made by seven African Heads of State since 2013. These countries committed to provide leadership and support in using ICTs to strengthen socio-economic development as well as contribute to economic growth and job creation. To make the commitment more actionable, a Smart Africa Alliance was formed to implement, monitor and evaluate the manifesto. This Alliance has, since 2013, grown and consists of

³⁰ United Nations Development Programme, n.d.

around 30 African countries in 2020 which represent more than 700 million African citizens. Other partners of the Alliance are the AU, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), World Bank, AfDB, the UN Economic Commission for Africa, the GSM Association, the Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN), and the private sector. The Alliance is based upon multiple pillars and cross-cutting enablers (see Figure 29):

- Pillars: Policy, Access, e-Government, Private Sector/Entrepreneurship, Sustainable Development.
- Cross-cutting enablers: Innovation, Communications and Advocacy, Capacity Building, Resource Mobilization.

(Smart Africa, 2020).

Figure 29- SMART Africa pillars and enablers³¹

3.2.2. National Innovation Support & Policies across Africa

Countries which lead in ICT, innovation, scientific research and development are among the most competitive countries worldwide (African Export-Import Bank, 2021), with STI being understood to play a major role for social and economic development on national, regional (and global) levels (Twiringiyimana, Daniels, & Chataway, 2021). Many African governments are therefore exploring R&I as an engine for stimulating growth (Guchu, 2021). In Africa, to

³¹ Smart Africa, 2020

facilitate and support the development of its regions and countries, it is essential for policy and governance related to STI to become deeply embedded in the countries' national system of innovation, instead of simply adopting a science-push approach to innovation (Gachie & Govender, 2017). Moreover, national STI policy and strategies shall seek to establish connections between different private and public stakeholders and should be adopted with the interest of major STI stakeholders at heart (African Development Bank, 2019) (Wolken, 2020). Such policies could strengthen innovation and private sector competitiveness as well as improve the labour market's job creation potential (African Development Bank, 2019). This is because STI links the generation of knowledge to product or service innovations and entrepreneurship in general (African Union, 2019).

Before 2010, only very few African countries were able to boast of an active STI policy. However, since then, innovation is increasingly recognised by African governments as a key pillar for achieving economic and social goals (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). This chapter provides information on the current status and recent developments, as well as opportunities related to STI policy.

3.2.2.1. Science, Technology, and Innovation Policies: Status, Developments & Opportunities

In recent years, a regulatory reform across the continent regarding business friendliness was visible, so that the ease of doing business in Africa has recently improved, with varying levels of progress between countries being seen (Duffy, 2021). In recent years, many African RECs and countries became involved in developing, adopting and/or reviewing their regional/national STI strategies and policies. This led to an increase of active strategies being in place in more and more countries (African Union, 2019) (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019) and allowed them to address the challenges faced by entrepreneurs (Maher, Laabi, Ivers, & Ngambeket, 2021).

In 2016, around 25 countries were reported to have STI strategies in place (African Union, 2019), however, this is still fewer than half of African countries (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018). They have been more proactive in developing their ICT policies though and in the same year at least forty-five African countries boasted an ICT policy framework, which are generally seen as having been effectively implemented (African Union, 2019). The development towards an increased adoption of STI policies and strategies indicates that African countries intend to become knowledge-based economies and seek the adaptation of knowledge and technology to be able to be better equipped in addressing and responding to the given challenges of the 21st century (UNECA, 2016).

While these ongoing efforts laid the foundation for the development of mainstream S&T across the continent (African Export-Import Bank, 2021), and for countries to transform their innovation potential into economic growth (African Union, 2019), in reality, the innovation activity is concentrated in only few countries (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). Research and

patent activity is also primarily located in only selected countries. Such realities pose a risk in that **many countries in Africa may get left further behind when it comes to their STI activities** (African Union, 2019).

While the countries with the most visible innovation activity are South Africa, Ghana, Senegal, Rwanda, and Nigeria (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019), STI policies can also be found in Algeria, Angola, Botswana, Burundi, Ethiopia, Egypt, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, Tanzania, Tunisia, Senegal, South Africa, Swaziland, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe (see Figure 30 of 15 African countries and their adoption of first STI policy) (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018) (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). Some countries, such as Nigeria, South Africa, Rwanda, and Tunisia have also provided tax incentives and cash grants for investing in specific innovation-relevant sectors, such as ICT (Maher, Laabi, Ivers, & Ngambeket, 2021).

Figure 30- Year of Adoptions of first STI policy of 15 African countries³²

Note: Zimbabwe and South Africa joined the Organization of African Unity in 1980 and 1994, respectively.

Source: Based on Nwuke (2015).

Across Africa, the application of a sectoral approach to the structure of STI policy means that nearly all show striking similarities to each other (except for South Africa, which employed a horizontal approach across various sectors) (UNECA, 2016). Each national STI policy specifies a set of essential national priorities, which range, for instance, from six for South Africa to eighteen for Nigeria. **Common priorities across African countries are education, agriculture, energy, health, environment, industry, transport, and communications** (UNECA, 2016). Some of these priorities are very much focused on the national context (though many are not) and seek to build on areas where countries either possess sufficient knowledge and capacity or consider STI as a means to help address pressing challenges in specific areas (UNECA, 2016).

STI policies of African countries comprise a mix of measure types, including nudges to change behaviour, explicit regulations or measures based on market incentives (UNECA, 2016). In

³² UNECA, 2016

recent years, policies have increasingly focused on the role of the private sector and specifically also young entrepreneurs (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). Few African governments, though, have started to test new regulatory frameworks, which facilitate experimentation (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). The diversity of STI measures reflect the countries' differences in political orientation, particularly the diverse views on roles of state and markets (UNECA, 2016).

Due to the fact that African countries have low levels of savings, it is said to be **imperative for them to collaborate with other actors outside their own countries in order to follow a long-term innovation policy** (Diop, 2017). In recent years, there has indeed been an increase in financing initiatives in Africa, which aim to strengthen the development of technical competences as well as the promotion of scientific research. These initiatives help in cross-cutting financing of STI instead of regional activities, which are more narrowly focused (African Union, 2019). Such a more networked approach with international and regional partners is a new trend emerging, which also helps in implementing the vision of a single economic and research space in Africa (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). In that regard, it is beneficial that African RECs recognise the fundamental role of STI for integrating their regions further. Additionally, they should understand the importance of an economic space free of entry barriers to accelerate innovation (UNECA, 2016).

In general, Africa is said to contain a lot of policy entrepreneurship and innovation, which provides valuable lessons for Africa as well as the rest of the world, however, African countries can also learn from experiences in other parts of the world on how to create a robust innovation system (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). This can be seen when considering the development of STI policies among some African countries, where several international organisations were actively involved (Gachie & Govender, 2017).

3.2.2.2. Challenges & Gaps: Existence and Quality of STI policies/regulations

The existing current policy frameworks in Africa do neither adequately protect nor sufficiently encourage innovation (Songwe, 2020). As a result, innovation systems in Africa are overall still considered as weak (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019) and fragmented, which is intensified by the absence of an explicit innovation strategy (Gachie & Govender, 2017). Research is said to be fragmented as well (African Union, 2019). Literature continues to point to weaknesses regarding African ecosystems including policy, science, research and innovation as a key reason for the region's inability to fully exploit the existing STI endeavours (Twiringiyimana, Daniels, & Chataway, 2021). This inability to advance in STI has been intensified by the fragmentation of Africa's markets (African Export-Import Bank, 2021), in that each African country faces its own regulatory hurdles when it comes to economic engagement (Giuliani & Ajadi, 2019). Vice versa, the insufficient investment in STI as well as a lacking scientific infrastructure is said to have contributed to a weakening of the economic transformation process both at the structural level and at sectoral level (African Export-Import Bank, 2021).

African entrepreneurs have had to deal with unfavourable policy and regulatory environments for a long time, which increased the difficulties in starting, growing, and scaling an innovative business. Often, a lack of clarity in business endeavours, and/or the time necessary for lobbying on policy and regulation, interfere with growing the business instead. As a result, entrepreneurs may not have a favourable view of the governments (Wolken, 2020). Moreover, the current lacking status of STI policies is visible in that Africa's STI performance is still rather low in comparison to other countries globally, with African countries still generally performing poorly in tertiary education, IP and innovativeness as well as productivity and competitiveness (UNECA, 2016).

The governments in developing countries can lack sufficient human resources as well as adequate organisational efficiency to design and implement policies, which foster innovation (Cirera & Maloney, 2017). In the following section, seven existing challenges and gaps regarding policymaking in Africa are described:

Limited evidence and data-based policy development and monitoring

Overall, only narrow evidence-based policy development takes place in Africa (African Union Commission, 2014), which includes insufficient monitoring and accountability surrounding STI policies (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018). One result of this is that the already struggling African countries who fail to generate adequate data on STI, get left even further behind when it comes to education and innovation (African Union, 2019).

Insufficient funding for STI policy making

Overall, inadequate budgets can be seen as a hindering factor in implementing adequate STI policies. In the majority of African countries, both governments and research institutions dedicate insufficient funding to promote R&I partnerships (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018).

Lacking policy capacity and skills

African countries do not yet possess the sufficient capacities for policymaking focused on supporting innovation (Sadeski, Kouacou, & Ploeg, 2019). This is specifically a result of inadequate skills or training of officials responsible for drafting policy documents (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018). This is visible in various areas, among others in construction and ICT (African Development Bank, 2019). Additionally, learning materials are either inadequate (African Development Bank, 2019) or it is difficult to access relevant information for policymaking (African Union Commission, 2014). One reason for the insufficient human capital is the continued brain-drain of Africa's talented citizens (African Export-Import Bank, 2021).

Missing strategies and insufficient policy designs

In many African countries, adequate STI strategy development is lacking (African Union, 2019). As a result, only few African governments invest intelligently and strategically in STI-relevant aspects, such as their digital infrastructure or in advancing entrepreneurship skills (World Bank, n.d.). Moreover, while several international organisations were involved to a large degree in the development of S&T policies among African countries, their initiatives have generally focused on developing S&T with only slight emphasis on the role of policies and their designs (Gachie & Govender, 2017).

Inconsistency of policy and predictability

Regulations which seek to support innovation are often inconsistent in Africa (Maher, Laabi, Ivers, & Ngambeket, 2021). One reason is that cooperation in the R&I field is in many cases only ad hoc or short-term, with inadequate institutional and government support (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018). Because of changes in political administration, many STI-related policies become inconsistent due to changes in political will and commitments. Moreover, bilateral, and multilateral cooperation mechanisms, which facilitate STI development in African countries, are designed in a way whereby no true ownership and accountability is being achieved (African Union Commission, 2014).

Missing efficacy of policy implementation

A major challenge in Africa is how STI policies are being translated into practical applications, including the efficient implementation of AU and REC initiatives (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018). Many countries which have STI strategies in place, often do not pursue these with concrete plans and sufficient budget allocations (African Union, 2019) due to a present inability to estimate the costs of STI policy implementation (UNECA, 2016)

Weak linkages between other policies and stakeholders

Despite adjustments in STI policy, governance and structures in African countries, the majority of the institutions in charge of STI policy making have operated in isolation from other policy entities (African Union Commission, 2014). Moreover, continually weak links are visible between research, policymaking and regulatory frameworks (African Development Bank, 2019) (Twiringiyimana, Daniels, & Chataway, 2021) as well as to private and education/research sectors (African Union Commission, 2014); all of which very much impacts the degree of progress of R&I. The weak collaboration between stakeholders as well as the absence of inter-sectoral linkages and policy areas make the policy and institutional outputs of Africa less reliable (African Union Commission, 2014). Additionally, the majority of African countries are inclined to fund scientific research with less emphasis on innovation and

technology development (Namubiru-Mwaura & Marincola, 2018). A review carried out by the African Academies of Science came to the conclusion that oftentimes, African national STI policy frameworks do not include social and environmental goals to a sufficient degree (African Union, 2019).

3.2.2.3. Start-up Acts

Start-ups are commonly seen as important pillars to achieve economic growth. As a result, it is a major goal of many governments worldwide to cultivate a lively innovation ecosystem (Wolken, 2020). African governments are also more and more seeing the advantage of entrepreneurship as a solution to create quality jobs, increase productivity, encourage economic growth as well as to provide market-based innovations which address development challenges (Ecosystem Build, 2020), (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021). Overall, the governments acknowledge the potential of the SMEs to transform their economies (Ecosystem Build, 2020).

More developed countries (such as the US, China, Israel, Sweden etc.) have taken an approach to foster a 'start-up culture' which promotes risk-taking and rewards talent, backed by substantial government funding and investment in local start-up ecosystem support organisations and start-up legislation, which streamlines business transactions. In Africa, thriving start-up ecosystems have not benefited as greatly from government engagement, due to the lack of resources available specifically for start-up support. **If entrepreneurs could be engaged in providing direct input into bureaucracy, such issues could be greatly reduced** (Wolken, 2020) **and vital trust could be built between governments and entrepreneurs.** With even the measures to support start-ups and entrepreneurship in the ecosystem often being fragmented and uncoordinated (Ecosystem Build, 2020), new policy formation based on the interests of entrepreneurs and investors, alongside other important ecosystem stakeholders, are desperately needed (Wolken, 2020).

Some governments across the region, though, have put in efforts to build a more supportive legislative framework for SMEs and start-ups, directly supporting entrepreneurship (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021) (Barry & Adoh, 2021). This dates back to the year 1981, when Ghana passed the first Small Business Act (SBA) in Africa. However, in recent years, some of the smaller African countries have tried to strengthen their innovation ecosystems in form of supportive legislation (Wolken, 2020), allowing start-ups and SMEs to operate with the certainty of a clear and robust framework, which facilitates start-up growth. Due to this fact, African start-ups are often actively lobbying their governments for such regulatory frameworks (Bischof, 2021).

Examples of regulations and legislation related to the support of start-ups, SMEs and entrepreneurship are SBAs and Start-up Acts. They can be seen as comprehensive legislative and regulatory frameworks, predominantly designed with a national and transversal scope.

Such laws are, however, are not as common as SME policies and strategies. **Both SBAs and Start-up Acts are two of many potential instruments which could be adopted by governments to spur innovation, foster entrepreneurship and facilitate the creation of new start-ups with high growth potential** (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021). As of 2020, 19 African governments have passed legislations in the form of SBAs (17x) and Start-up Acts (2x) (Ecosystem Build, 2020), as highlighted in Figure 31.

Figure 31- Timeline of SBAs and Start-up Acts in Africa, including the number of interventions³³

The Start-up Acts are a more recent form of support for start-ups and SMEs, as compared to SBAs (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021). Increasingly, Start-up Acts are gaining prominence in Africa as new tools to offer incentives for entrepreneurs to create start-ups, as well as support them along their journey. Such acts also support investors as they seek potential companies to invest in, yet further supporting the development of strong tech ecosystems (AfricArena, 2020). Mostly holistic in their scope, they include interventions and targeted incentives, such as tax exemptions, subsidies, procurement (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021) or pre-seed financing, as well as measures, such as the improvement of digital governance and macroeconomic conditions (Ecosystem Build, 2020). Overall, they seek to make it easier for businesses to operate by addressing specific challenges they, i.e., start-ups with high potential for growth and innovation, but depending on the target beneficiaries of each Start-up Act, are facing (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021) (Ecosystem Build, 2020).

Starting in the 1990s, the majority of the countries in Europe and North America have to date adopted at least some measures aimed at supporting start-ups. Also, in Asia, some countries,

³³ Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021

such as India and Israel have focused on targeting start-ups in the form of various policies, programmes and legislative amendments to the existing regulatory framework supporting entrepreneurship. However, these policies do not qualify as Start-up Acts since they do not form part of a broader legislative framework, being isolated and rather limited in their impact (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021). Despite the clear benefits, as of 2021, only five countries have adopted Start-up Acts: Italy (2012), Argentina (2017), Tunisia (2018), Senegal (2019) and the Philippines (2019) (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021) (Paul, 2021).

The adoption of Start-up Acts in Tunisia and Senegal, in 2018 and 2019 respectively, showed a small, but growing, interest from African countries to achieve a more enabling environment for start-ups and investors, which laid the foundation for other African countries so follow suit (Wolken, 2020) (Barry & Adoh, 2021). (Giuliani & Ajadi, 2019). Mali also began the process of adopting a Start-up Act, drafting an act which was approved in 2019. Mali, Senegal and Tunisia's Start-up Acts were all developed under the collaborative leadership of both the start-up communities and senior government officials, as well as with the help of i4Policy (a multi-stakeholder group of innovation hubs and other start-up catalysts promoting policy reforms in Africa's start-up space). Such help was provided in the form of innovative policy hackathons (Ecosystem Build, 2020) (Wolken, 2020). Indeed, Start-up Acts need to be defined through a collaborative process involving the cooperation of multiple stakeholders of the entrepreneurship ecosystem (public and private sectors), including entrepreneurs, incubators, innovative hubs etc. (Investment Climate Reform Facility, 2021).

As of 2020, Start-up Acts were being considered or under development in an increasing number of countries (see Figure 32), such as Benin, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Egypt, Ghana and Rwanda (Ecosystem Build, 2020). Even larger economies, such as Kenya, Ethiopia, and Uganda, also started their Start-up Act processes and are currently in various stages of development. For Rwanda, who started the discussions with key stakeholders in 2020 (Wolken, 2020), the act shall provide a policy framework as well as various proposed incentives, including residency programmes for high-skilled graduates, tax breaks for local angel investors, and certain incentives for digital nomads (Duffy, 2021). In South Africa, a National Start-up Act is being co-created, led by a steering committee representing the local entrepreneurship ecosystem, and including various stakeholders, such as investors, incubators, accelerators, and founders (Startup Act South Africa, n.d.).

Seen as a new component to expand Africa's start-up ecosystems, the Start-up Act developments across Africa are of particular note (Figure 32). If implemented more broadly, they could trigger more positive change in Africa's general business environment, by improving support for entrepreneurs and attracting new investors (Wolken, 2020). However, Start-up Acts are too new, and external assessments too scarce, to be able to fully understand their effectiveness. However, existing assessments suggest that they can have a significant

impact on private sector development if they are well designed and correctly implemented (Ecosystem Build, 2020).

Figure 32- Start-up Act developments in Africa from 2018 to 2021³⁴

³⁴ Udoh, 2021

Examples of Start-up Acts in Africa

Tunisia

Tunisia has been active in adopting innovative policy seeking to facilitate business friendliness. Moreover, it has been a pioneer in Africa in adopting its Start-Up Act in 2018 (Duffy, 2021). This act placed STI at the centre of its aspirations regarding economic transformation (Olasoji, 2021). It forms part of its government strategies to position Tunisia as an innovation hub and intends to leverage its emerging tech scene

(Wolken, 2020). It streamlined the creation of businesses and helped expand Tunisia's digital infrastructure, among others (Duffy, 2021). Key elements include state salaries for up to three founders per company in the course of the first year and substantial tax breaks, start-up grants, fast-track licenses to facilitate start-up registration, and increased state support for covering patent licenses. Two years after being passed, it has been said that this Start-up Act has helped strengthen the economy. In fact, the 2019 Q4 data from Entrepreneurs of Tunisia reveals that in a one-year period, more than 165 new start-ups were officially founded as well as twenty-four new co-working spaces launched, while \$18.5 million was fundraised. In an April 2020 profile by WeeTracker, a news portal focused on business and start-ups in Africa, various Tunisian entrepreneurs largely see the Start-up Act as an instrument, which made it easier for them to grow their venture (Wolken, 2020). It is also praised for encouraging similar acts to be developed and/or considered in Africa (Olasoji, 2021).

Senegal

Senegal's Start-up Act aims to assist the country to become the Francophone leader in tech and entrepreneurship on the continent and is part of the country's broader entrepreneurship government strategies (Wolken, 2020). This includes a \$50 million start-up fund, called DER, which seeks to accelerate entrepreneurship by providing funding, training and technical assistance (Fanny, 2019). The Start-up Act also includes three tax-free operational years for start-ups, training specifically for youth and female entrepreneurs, and an easily accessible start-up registration platform. However, it is too early to evaluate if Senegal's Start-up Act can prove to considerably impact its young tech ecosystem (Wolken, 2020).

3.2.3. Foreign Countries' Strategies & Investment Programmes for Africa

During the last decade, Africa has attracted an increased interest from a large number of investors and governments from around the world. These actors pursue different strategies when it comes to investing and implementing activities in African countries. In this section, first a short general overview shall be provided on FDI developments in Africa, which is then complemented by a deeper analysis of the activities of the following specific countries: China, India, the US and the United Kingdom (UK). These countries were chosen based on the amounts invested into the African continent, their geopolitical standing and the volume of reported information discovered during the desk-based research.

In Figure 33, the largest number of FDI (investors per capital invested) projects and jobs created in Africa are shown, which is based on data from Ernst & Young's Africa Attractiveness Report from 2019 (Hlophe, Crous, & Custers, 2019). As is visible, across all columns, all investor countries - with the exception of France, partially driven by strong historical relationships – come from outside of the European Union (EU). The largest investors by number of projects were the more traditional investor nations: the US, France, and the UK, respectively. However, China was the largest investor in terms of the total capital invested, which is more than twice as high as the amounts of France or the U.S (\$), followed by the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Similar results can be observed in terms of jobs created where China leads the way with more than double the amount of the US and France, which achieve similar results, followed by the UK (Madden, 2019).

Figure 33: Largest FDI investors in Africa by capital invested, number of projects and jobs created (2014-2018) ³⁵

	Capital (in US\$m)	Projects	Jobs created
1.	China (72 235)	USA (463)	China (137 028)
2.	France (34 172)	France (329)	USA (62 004)
3.	USA (30 855)	UK (286)	France (57 970)
4.	UAE (25 278)	China (259)	UK (40 949)
5.	UK (17 768)	South Africa (199)	UAE (39 479)

³⁵ Hlophe, Crous, & Custers, 2019

In the aforementioned report, it becomes visible that emerging countries besides China, such as the United Arab Emirates or India, are increasingly becoming important as investors in Africa. Collectively (including China) they implement more than one third of all projects, while creating over 50 percent of jobs and investing more than 50 percent of capital. In addition to this, further growth of intra-African investment was also visible in 2018: South Africa continued to be the major investor in other African countries, while Kenya and Nigeria contributed significantly to East and West Africa respectively and Egypt and Morocco to North Africa. Analysing the FDI by sector, it becomes apparent that, while the majority of inbound capital was invested in extractives during 2018 (36 percent), the majority of projects and jobs created could be found in the services and industry sectors; specifically, Telecoms, media, and technology (TMT) was a sector with increased growth in 2018, driven by a rise in investment in technology due to the increasing trend of global technology companies becoming involved in Africa on the ground (Madden, 2019). Overall, though, it has to be noted that Africa attracted less FDI than any other region in 2018 (EY Global, 2020).

Foreign countries' policies, plans & development finance

In the following sections, the activities of four countries will be discussed, which are relevant for the growth of innovation ecosystems in Africa. These countries can be separated in two Western countries (UK, US) as well as two non-Western countries (China and India).

3.2.3.1. United Kingdom

The UK's innovation-relevant involvement in Africa from the past years, included a renewed commitment to the African continent in 2018, with a major focus on sub-Saharan Africa. This commitment aims to invest £4 billion across several African countries in the upcoming years. This commitment was called a 'fundamental shift' in the UK's long-term investment in the African economy, going beyond the previous more development-aid focused funding. This shift also involved a change within the UK departments, with new UK-Africa initiatives launched or expanded to manage this engagement. These initiatives and partnerships are mostly focused on only three African countries: South Africa, Kenya and Nigeria.

[Key initiatives](#) include the establishment of teams to boost technology innovation, an accelerator programme, UK Tech Hubs and entrepreneurship schemes. The intention is to share skills and ideas among UK and African entrepreneurs as well as encourage future trade between the UK and Africa (UK Government, 2018). These initiatives are described below, including the countries where they are to be implemented:

- UK STI / Innovation Partnership team (Kenya, South Africa) seeks to provide a 'one stop shop' of comprehensive and tailored support, idea exchange and partnerships opportunities. The team shall become involved in diverse areas of research and technology, and work with several sectors in African countries. Additionally, the team shall be backed with the expertise from different UK government departments and

build on the robust and existing science relationships with South Africa and Kenya. Furthermore, links to digital technologies as well as the UK-Africa trade and partnership opportunities shall be established.

- New regional tech experts (Kenya, Nigeria) shall improve the connections between the UK and Africa's cutting-edge digital sectors and support start-ups in a wide range of fields to grow and to create jobs, as well as provide digital skills training
- Tech acceleration programme / Innovation Partnership programme (Kenya, South Africa) is equipped with a £32m fund to accelerate the development of promising new technologies and offer tailored support to entrepreneurs as well as the growth of start-ups from various sectors. This includes early-stage investment and connecting them with private investors, as well as the facilitation of connections across the innovation ecosystems forging links across the UK's and Africa's innovation networks. Additionally, training for entrepreneurs to enhance their business skills is provided so they can scale their ideas. The partnership also seeks to influence policy and regulatory hurdles which may hinder growth of innovation solutions in African Cities.
- Tech Hub technology programme (Kenya, South Africa). The already existing UK-South Africa Tech Hub in Johannesburg (South Africa) shall be complemented by a new hub in Nairobi (Kenya), all based on the successful UK-Israeli Tech Hub model. These Hubs seek to facilitate and leverage local and international connections in the tech space which should facilitate trade and support local start-ups as well as enable UK companies to settle more easily in Africa.
- Digital skills and entrepreneurship programmes (Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa), which includes the TeXchange, Global EdTech Awards, Go Global as well as Founders and Coders programmes. These programmes shall contribute to the aim of the UK to become the partner of choice for African start-ups to expand internationally (UK Government, 2018) (Hochadel & Wells, 2019)

In January 2020, government officials and business leaders from the UK and twenty-one African nations, participated in the first ever [UK-Africa Investment Summit \(2020\)](#). It allows new partnerships between the UK and African nations to be established, based on trade, investment, and mutual values and interest (UK Government,

2020). British Prime Minister Boris Johnson acknowledged Africa's vast business potential and explained the UK's intention of becoming Africa's "investment partner of choice." (Ottaway, 2021). Billions of pounds of funding as well as new initiatives were announced to further strengthen the existing relationship with Africa, support the transformation of African economies, increase infrastructure financing, and reinforce the trading relationship (UK Government, 2020). While this summit is not necessarily focused on innovation per se, it is to

UK-AFRICA INVESTMENT SUMMIT 2020

be seen if subsequent versions of this summit pick up the topic of innovation in their respective editions.

This summit, however, marked an important step in the UK-Africa relationship (Ottaway, 2021), although it is argued that the UK should seek a stronger partnership with Africa based on a greater strategic interest, as discussed in the 2020 report ‘The UK and sub-Saharan Africa: prosperity, peace and development co-operation’, published by the House of Lords’ International Relations and Defence Committee. Moreover, the Overseas Development Institute (ODI) argued that the UK government should consider using the UK-Africa Investment Summit as a foundation, which could usher in a new medium-term economic partnership by increasingly diversifying UK investment in Africa and taking advantage of Africa’s new AfCFTA integration (te Velde, 2020). The decision of the UK government to reduce its aid budget from 0.7% to 0.5% of national income is said to be a step in the wrong direction (Ottaway, 2021).

Further UK initiatives strengthening R&I in Africa:

- The [Science and Innovation Network \(SIN\)](#) can count on approx. one-hundred officers in over forty countries around the world, which seek to build partnerships and collaborations in science and innovation by working with the local science and innovation community across multiple thematic programmes, among others, Health and Life Sciences, Clean Energy, Future Manufacturing, Cyber and ICT, Quantum Technology, Future Cities. In Africa, SIN is based in Kenya and South Africa (UK Government, n.d.).
- The [Global Alliance Africa](#) is a six-year project, facilitated by the Knowledge Transfer Network (KTN), which seeks to establish long-lasting, knowledge transfer and innovation partnerships between the UK and Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa, aiming to facilitate and accelerate innovations, which contribute to inclusive economic growth, job creation and the reduction of poverty. To achieve this, the alliance seeks to:
 - Connect investors, innovators and governments
 - Align the UK approach for African innovation support by working closely together with other UK initiatives
 - Create opportunities for innovators to share their work and facilitate new connections by strengthening collaboration and training provision
 - encourage sharing and showcasing of new ideas and best practice in the innovation ecosystem (Knowledge Transfer Network, n.d.)
- [Human Development innovation Fund \(HDIF\)](#) is a £ 40 million challenge fund focused on Tanzania, which was launched in 2014 and provides grants to businesses, NGOs and research institutions so that they can scale in education, health and water, sanitation and hygiene. The objective of the fund is to facilitate the experimentation and diffusion

of innovations for human development (Human Development Innovation Fund (HDIF), n.d.).

- The [Strengthening Research Institutions in Africa \(SRIA\)](#) programme explores the capacity of a country's research system to efficiently carry out and disseminate high-quality research, with the aim to strengthen knowledge-driven sustainable development. Seven African countries are included in the SRIA programme: Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda (Fosci & Loffreda, 2019).
- The [Global Challenges Research Fund \(GCRF\)](#) is a fund assisted by nine UK entities and in partnership with UNDP, which supports cutting-edge and challenge-led disciplinary research and seeks to strengthen the capacity and impact of research and innovation to improve lives and opportunity in the developing world. An exchange through partnership with excellent UK research and researchers is seen as essential in that regard. One of the funded projects includes twelve interdisciplinary research hubs, which each receive £13 million and £20 million over five years. These hubs shall connect researchers, governments, NGOs and community groups in developing countries and the UK, to facilitate the sharing of knowledge and expertise on innovative and sustainable solutions (UK Research and Innovation, n.d.).

3.2.3.2. United States

The US involvement in Africa in recent years was focused specifically on strengthening trade and private sector investment (Cohen & Steiger, 2021), as 90% of finances flowing into emerging markets, originate from private investors (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). This is specifically visible in form of the launch of the [Prosper Africa Build Together](#) government Initiative in 2018. This initiative is backed by the resources and expertise of seventeen U.S. government agencies and departments and seeks to build robust business environments with Africa which support two-way trade and investment between both regions (ShareAmerica, 2021). It connects buyers, suppliers and investors in multiple sectors and across both regions via a virtual deal room that facilitates trade opportunities and offers important information, which makes smarter investments possible (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). The initiative supports projects and facilitates deals, which improve wages and support job creation (ShareAmerica, 2021). Since its launch, it has enabled more than 800 deals between the US and African nations, as well as more than \$50 billion in exports and investments on the continent. The five key sectors in terms of deals facilitated, include energy (107 deals), agribusiness (75 deals), healthcare (54 deals), ICT (43 deals) and aerospace and defence (36 deals) (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021).

Besides Prosper Africa, USAID, has, since 2018, shifted its focus towards increased investment in the private sector by adopting the '[Private-Sector Engagement Policy](#)', which specifically

stressed the importance of the private sector, among others, to spur growth in SMEs. USAID has started various projects, which provide funding or access to private investment for African SMEs, such as the [Partnering to Accelerate Entrepreneurship \(PACE\)](#) element of the GrowthAfrica initiative, which seeks to align investors and SMEs needs. Additionally, USAID sponsors three regional trade and investment hubs (in West Africa, East Africa, and Southern Africa) launched in 2013 and 2014. These hubs contribute to the improvement of ‘the region’s trade competitiveness, encouraging the diversification of exports beyond natural resources, and promoting broader, more inclusive economic growth’. Between 2014 and 2019, the East Africa Trade and Investment Hub, for example, helped facilitate more than \$56.2 million in private sector investment in Africa and established more than 1,700 linkages among buyers and sellers (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021).

Despite these initiatives, **US economic engagement for strengthening economic relations with African states is said to have been inconsistent and rather modest over the last decade** (Carr, 2020) (von Soest, 2021). This can also be seen when considering that the U.S. FDI for Africa continued to decrease since 2008, going so far that FDI flows have been negative since mid-2017 (Wilkins, 2021). It has also been argued that the US is working on a rather short-term time horizon and does not sufficiently support US companies with economic assistance via government action overseas; both aspects are said to be better handled by China (Carr, 2020). All these aspects might possibly be related to an apparent ‘fragmentation of institutions and programmes’ and the ‘proliferation of uncoordinated development assistance programmes for Africa’, as van de Walle lamented already 12 years ago (van de Walle, 2009).

Further US initiatives strengthening R&I in Africa:

- The [U.S.-Africa Business Summit](#) is a conference between the US and the African region, which is held every two years and has been regarded as the essential conference on doing business with and investing in Africa. In its 13th edition a focus was put, among other things, on expanding trade between the two regions, the digital transformation, the Future of Energy, and the manufacturing ecosystems (Corporate Council on Africa, 2021).
- The [U.S. International Development Finance Corporation \(DFC\)](#) was founded in 2019 and offers African SMEs loans, guarantees, and equity and could also provide grants for technical assistance in limited circumstances. In sub-Saharan Africa, the DFC work jointly with local financial institutions to increase funding and support for SMEs and to strengthen the financial ecosystem overall (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021).
- The [Connect Africa initiative](#) was launched in 2018 by the Overseas Private Investment Corporation (OPIC), a U.S. Government’s development finance institution. Its intention is to provide investments of more than \$1 billion for projects that support

transportation, ICT, and value chains in Africa over the next three years, to further integrate Africa into the global market (U.S. International Development Finance Corporation, 2018). An example of its work is the signing of a commitment letter for \$100 million to expand access to telecommunications in Africa, particularly in Uganda and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (McGee-Abe, 2018).

- The [Better Utilization of Investments Leading to Development Act \(BUILD Act\)](#) was passed in 2018, possibly as a response to China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). It aims to facilitate the participation of the private sector (in the form of investments and skills) in the further economic development of low or lower-middle income countries (Ingram, 2018). Furthermore, the BUILD Act seeks to improve the financial conditions of US investments in important infrastructure projects in developing countries (von Soest, 2021).
- The [Millennium Challenge Corporation \(MCC\)](#) is a bilateral U.S. foreign aid agency established in 2004, independent from the State Department and USAID. It aspires to reduce global poverty through economic growth and provides grants and technical assistance to countries that meet specific requirements for good governance, fighting corruption and respecting democratic rights. In July 2021, it announced it will provide \$1 billion in form of grants for financing economic growth and infrastructure programmes in Africa by the end of 2022, alongside policy reforms. Additionally, MCC is collaborating with Africa50 launch the Millennium Impact for Infrastructure Accelerator (MIIA) – Africa. This partnership is a global project preparation platform which seeks to develop and prepare bankable infrastructure in order to attract impact investments in Africa (Millennium Challenge Corporation, 2021).
- The [U.S. African Development Foundation \(USADF\)](#) is an independent U.S. government agency for foreign assistance. It directly supports African grassroots enterprises and social entrepreneurs in the form of grant/seed capital as well as via capacity building and technical assistance, all of which aim to develop, grow and scale African enterprises and help (specifically women-led and/or young African) entrepreneurs. The aim is to support new ideas and solutions, which address some of Africa's biggest challenges. The foundation claims that 50% of its grants allow enterprise to double their sales value, while around 33% of enterprises achieve continued growth, even beyond the USADF grant period (U.S. African Development Foundation, n.d.). Over the past five years (2017-2021), USADF has invested \$117 million into more than 1,000 SMEs in Africa. Moreover, it also seeks to strengthen local financial ecosystems, by working with African financial intermediaries (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). It operates in 21 African countries, as visible in Figure 34:

Figure 34: The 21 African countries the USADF operates in³⁶

- The [Young African Leaders Initiative \(YALI\)](#), launched in 2010, supports young African leaders via professional leadership development training. Moreover, a virtual online community of around 700,000 members provides networking opportunities. This is complemented by four Regional Leadership Centres (RLCs – in Ghana, Kenya, Senegal and South Africa) are located at higher education institutions in sub-Saharan Africa and provide in-person and online training leadership training programmes, as well as networking, and professional development opportunities. Since 2015, YALI has provided more than 20,000 young leaders with leadership training, including training focused on business and entrepreneurship (Young African Leaders Initiative, n.d.).

3.2.3.3. China

In the last two decades, China has extended its economic ties with countries in sub-Saharan Africa, mostly through infrastructure investment and increased trade (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021), based on the intention to build long-term relationships (Carr, 2020). The reasons for this are commercial, as well as strategic, intentions (Ze Yu, 2021). Due to increased investments, China has become Africa's largest trading partner since 2009 (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021) and has additionally surpassed the US as the largest equity investor in Africa as measured by FDI in 2013 (Ze Yu, 2021). This can be attributed to the fact that since 2000, China's FDI flows to Africa averaged an annual growth rate of 40% (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). Since the start of the 2000s, trade with Africa has multiplied by 20 (breaking \$200 billion in 2019), and the FDI for Africa has in the same time frame multiplied by 100, reaching \$49.1

³⁶ U.S. African Development Foundation, n.d.

billion in 2019 (Ze Yu, 2021). The majority of China’s financial support is provided to governments in the form of loans for infrastructure, or to Chinese-owned firms in Africa (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). In 2018, the major sectors of Chinese investments were transport (33%) and energy (33%), making up two-thirds of all investments, with investments in technology making up around 2%. The countries receiving the lion’s share of investments are Nigeria (17%), Angola and Ethiopia (both 8%), which receive one-third of all investments going into Africa, as visible in Figure 35:

Figure 35: Locational distribution by percentage of Chinese investments in Africa³⁷

Source: Chinese Investment Tracker, AEI

BROOKINGS

A major initiative of China’s involvement in Africa is the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which was formally announced in 2013. It provides easy-access financing for much-needed infrastructure to African governments, which enable transport networks, power grids, renewable energy projects and digital infrastructure to be built. These are seen as the foundations of future growth by African leaders (Ottaway, 2021). Currently, Chinese companies are actively involved in building the digital infrastructure in Africa and providing internet services (Si & Zhihua, 2021). In this regard, U.S. firms have failed to compete against Chinese firms (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). The initiative has provided loans of approximately \$5 bil. per year since 2013 (Wilkins, 2021) to the forty African countries which have signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with China to join the initiative (see Figure 36) (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). Generally, a large percentage of Africa’s infrastructure initiatives are powered by Chinese companies and/or backed by Chinese funding (Shepard, 2019), both of which supports with infrastructural projects related to the AfCFTA (Carr, 2020).

³⁷ Sow, 2018

Figure 36: African countries with a BRI MoU

Graphic © Asia Briefing Ltd.

Chinese investments are said to have a positive economic impact on job growth (at least in some contexts), with the connections between Chinese actors and local suppliers and buyers leading to growing investment and trade relationships. However, China's involvement on the continent has led to an increase in Africa's debt, so that **in 2021 around 30% of African debt payments went to China, which is a significant cause for concern** (Runde, Savoy, & Staguhn, 2021). Moreover, in many cases, Chinese support has been linked with procurement to Chinese firms and Chinese state-owned enterprises (SOEs). Many of the infrastructure developments are said to involve rather unfavorable conditions for the African countries/partners in terms of finances or technical and environmental aspects. Despite these negative perceptions, the benefits, which go hand in hand with Chinese investments in Africa, have generally been well received (Carr, 2020).

Findings from a 2017 McKinsey study estimate that more than 10,000 Chinese corporations, (mainly private) carry out business in Africa, mostly investing in the infrastructure, energy, and banking (Jayaram, Kassiri, & Sun, 2017). According to the Chinese Ministry of Commerce, Chinese private companies represent around 90% of the total number of Chinese companies investing in Africa, and are responsible for 70% of the value of Chinese FDI (Ze Yu, 2021).

The Chinese Development Bank's China-Africa Development Fund (CADFund) was established in 2007 as the first Chinese equity investment fund that focuses on investments in Africa and has since then become the main platform for Chinese investment in Africa. It encourages and supports Chinese enterprises to invest in Africa, and provides, among other things, capital financing and value-added services, linking Chinese companies to African projects. While Chinese private companies continue to dominate the trade and investments in Africa overall,

SOEs can be seen as key actors in the energy, transportation, and resources sectors, due to strategic aspirations as well as the long-haul return on investments (Ze Yu, 2021).

The [Forum on China-Africa Cooperation \(FOCAC\)](#) has since the year 2000, been the major exchange venue for China and African leaders to discuss future partnerships, initiatives, and funding, as well as to decide on specific action plans (Anshan, 2012). The FOCAC Beijing Action Plan which lasted from 2019 to 2021 sought to leverage the role of STI as an instrument for growth and development according to South African Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, Dr Blade Nzimande (South African Government, 2021). This plan has been replaced by the [FOCAC Dakar Action Plan](#), which was adopted during the Eighth Ministerial Conference of the FOCAC, held in Senegal in November 2021. It lays the foundation of actions for the years 2022 to 2024 (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2021), revealing China's continued strong interest in expanding the cooperation with Africa within the framework of the FOCAC. The results included specifically a China-Africa Cooperation Vision 2035, the continuation of the BRI in Africa and the following specific programmes, among others:

- Green development programme: Undertake ten green development, environmental protection, climate action projects; build centres of excellence on low-carbon development
- Capacity Building programme: Invitation of 10,000 high-level Africans for training programmes; promote vocational training and skills for African labour
- Investment promotion programme: Encouraging Chinese companies to invest at least US\$10 billion in Africa over the coming three years; establish a platform for China-Africa private sector investment promotion
- Trade promotion programme: Continued support to the development of the AfCFTA
- Digital innovation programme

(Devonshire-Ellis, 2021)

Specifically, the latter, focused on digital innovation and a digital economy, is said to be a key measure in the Dakar Action Plan so as to foster cooperation and enhance communication and exchanges with African governments in order to boost the innovative development of digital technology and promote the building of an information society in Africa, as well as enhance information sharing in a digital economy, including elevating the digital capacity SMEs. This shall be done mainly through capacity building activities, innovation centres, and strategic consultation on ICT policies and development. Moreover, the China-Africa Digital Cooperation Forum, as well as the China-Africa BDS Cooperation Forum, which was first held in November 2021, shall be continued (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2021). In this regard, the [China-Africa Digital Innovation Partnership Program](#), first announced during the China-Africa Internet Development and Cooperation Forum in August 2021, shall be implemented. It focuses on the following aspects:

- Strengthening digital infrastructure and connectivity, including digital infrastructure projects and the expansion of internet access,
- Growing the digital economy by promoting integrated development of digital technologies and the real economy, as well as raising the level of digitisation in the public and corporate sectors and strengthening e-commerce,
- Promoting digital education by training young talents in digital-related fields, implementing programmes, such as the Talented Young Scientist Program, as well as encouraging Chinese enterprises to enhance cooperation with Africa's digital innovation professionals,
- Supporting African countries in applying digital technologies in various sectors and leveraging digital technologies to strengthen governance, including public e-service platforms,
- Building cooperation platforms to promote digital progress between China and Africa, including the establishment of a high-level dialogue platform on China-Africa digital cooperation, the China-Africa Innovation Cooperation and Development Forum and the China-Africa Innovation Cooperation Centre.

(Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2021).

Besides the digital economy, another area of interest in the Dakar Action Plan is S&T cooperation and knowledge sharing, where both regions seek to enhance synergy between STI strategies and policies to fully leverage STI. This specifically includes the implementation of the Belt and Road Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation Action Plan and the China-Africa Science and Technology Partnership Program 2.0. Besides this, the development of joint laboratories, institutes, and STI cooperation bases are to be established. Additionally, a multi-tiered system for scientific, technological and people-to-people exchanges via several programmes shall be built, including the International Outstanding Young Scientists Exchange Program and the Africa Young Scientists in China Program (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2021). In recent years, additionally China has assisted Africa in nurturing scientific and technological talents via the Belt and Road Region Scholarship, Chinese government scholarships and other activities (Xinhua Net, 2021).

3.2.3.4. India

India has played an important role in building African capacity in the recent past (Chakrabarty, 2021). Its economic relations with Africa are diverse, including concessional lines of credit (LOCs), grant-in-aid to African countries, capacity building and technical assistance, as well as supporting key projects and the establishment of industrial units, among other things (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2021). India is Africa's third-largest trade partner (Chakrabarty, 2021), with the bilateral trade between both regions growing year-on-year, achieving a trade volume of US\$55.9 billion in 2020-21 (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2021). Additionally, Indian investments in Africa have grown rapidly in the last decade, making

India the seventh-largest investor in Africa in 2021 (Chakrabarty, 2021). During the 15th CII-EXIM Bank India-Africa Project Partnership Conclave in September 2020, the Minister of State for External Affairs, V. Muraleedharan, mentioned that “as of September 2020, India has executed 194 developmental projects in 37 African countries; currently working to complete 77 additional development projects in 29 countries, with a total outlay of USD 11.6 billion. Grants-in-aid worth more than USD 700 million have been extended to African partner countries for projects in infrastructure, connectivity and skill development [...]” (Basu, Narayan, & Gera, 2020). A fund that aims at supporting the implementation of public-private partnerships and knowledge sharing via grants with Africa in areas such as infrastructure and railway development, ICT, science, technology and non-conventional energy is the India Africa Economic Cooperation Fund (INAFEC - also known as India Trust Fund), which India and the AfDB signed in 2015.

The [India-Africa Forum Summit \(IAFS\)](#) is the official platform for India-Africa relations, aiming to develop strategies that seek to strengthen the existing India-Africa partnership, which, to date, has taken place three times (in 2008, 2011 and 2015). The 2015 IAFS was attended by representatives from all fifty-four African countries, including forty heads of states. The fourth summit was scheduled to be held in 2020 but had to be postponed due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Basu, Narayan, & Gera, 2020). The IAFS establish partnerships with Africa at three levels:

1. The AUC level,
2. The level of the Regional Economic Communities and
3. The bilateral level.

When it became apparent to India that the bilateral level was the most meaningful level to achieve implementation on the ground, it has since then (around the time of the 2015 IAFS) focused on bilateral engagement, instead of cooperating extensively with the RECs and the AUC. However, it is important for India to maintain the pan-African level of engagement as well (Singh, 2021).

The first IAFS 2008 laid the foundation for strengthening partnerships across various sectors, including considerable support towards S&T development in Africa (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2015), based on the fact that ICT is generally seen an important part of India’s technical cooperation with Africa, related to the relevance the ICT sector played in India’s growth (Chakrabarty, 2021). Since 2008, various [India–Africa S&T initiatives](#) have been implemented. For instance, India has signed technology cooperation agreements with four African countries (South Africa, Tunisia, Egypt, and Mauritius) (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2015) and established in recent years, IT centers in South Africa, Egypt, Morocco, Ghana, Namibia, and Tanzania. Some of these centers are focused on entrepreneurship (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2021).

The cooperation between India-Africa has also focused on techno-economic capacity building, as skill development and capacity building are important pillars in the IAFS. This is complemented by the [Indian Technical and Economic Cooperation \(ITEC\)](#) programme, which was launched in 1964 to share India's lessons in development with other developing countries. It remains an important area of Indian development cooperation. In its frame, training programmes and study tours are conducted, as well as project-based cooperation carried out. Africa is a key beneficiary because close to 50% of the training slots are reserved for African countries. Currently, about 98 Indian institutions provide training courses in fields such as engineering and technology (Chakrabarty, 2021).

In addition to this, the CV Raman Fellowship for African researchers was started in 2010, with the intention to provide opportunities to African researchers to participate in research in S&T in Indian universities and research institutions, in cooperation with renowned Indian scientists (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2015). India's Department of S&T provides technical assistance to African research institutions in the form of training of African researchers, as well as via technological know-how sharing and overall, by establishing linkages with African academic and research institutions. Moreover, at the third IAFS in 2015, India pledged to set up institutions of higher learning in Africa and offer 50,000 scholarships to African students over a five-year period as part of India's scholarship programme. Over 80% of the available scholarship slots have been used in the last five years (Chakrabarty, 2021).

The [Pan-African e-Network \(PANEP\)](#) was launched in association with the AU in 2009 in and ran until 2018. Its aim was to help bridge the digital divide in Africa and harness the socio-economic benefits of ICT. Indian expertise in IT was used to provide improved healthcare and education facilities, as well as to support capacity building in education and medicine in Africa. A fibre-optic network was set up to provide satellite connectivity, telemedicine, and tele-education services in forty-seven of the forty-eight African countries that signed the agreement. Overall, one-hundred-and-sixty-nine centres have been commissioned and integrated with the network (Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, 2015). In 2017, the project was handed over to the AU (Basu, Narayan, & Gera, 2020). The second phase of this programme, [e-VidyaBharti and e-ArogyaBharti \(e-VBAB\)](#) started in 2018 and is fully funded by the Indian government. The objective is to provide free tele-education to four-thousand African students each year for five years, as well as to continue medical education for one-thousand African doctors, paramedical staff, and nurses (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2021).

The [CII- EXIM Bank Conclave on India Africa Project Partnership](#) is an initiative launched by CII & EXIM Bank of India, with the support of the Indian government, which has been held yearly since 2005. It is seen as a major event in enhancing the economic engagement between India and Africa as well as for Indian and African governments and other stakeholder to explore and decide on new areas of partnerships (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2021). Subrahmanyam Jaishankar, India External Affairs Minister argued at the 2021 event, that both Africa and India

should strengthen collaboration in digital delivery, capacity building, and the green economy, among other things. Moreover, participants mentioned that scope for investment and partnerships also exists in the digital technology sector (African Development Bank Group, 2021).

Summary:

- In recent years, around half of all African countries started developing, adopting and/or reviewing their STI strategies and policies. However, innovation activity is heavily concentrated in only a few African countries, proving a risk for many countries to get left further behind when it comes to their STI activities,
- Common priorities across African countries are education, agriculture, energy, health, environment, industry, transport, and communications,
- Since African countries have low levels of savings, it is imperative for them to collaborate with other actors (private sector and outside their own countries) to be able to follow a long-term innovation policy,
- Seven challenges exist in developing and implementing STI policies: 1. Limited evidence- and data-based policy development and monitoring; 2. Insufficient funding for policy making; 3. Lacking policy capacity and skills; 4. Missing strategies and insufficient policy designs; 5. Inconsistency of policy and predictability; 6. Missing efficacy of policy implementation; 7. Weak linkages between other policies and stakeholders,
- If entrepreneurs could be engaged in providing direct input into bureaucracy, issues could be greatly reduced and vital trust built between governments and entrepreneurs,
- Both SBAs and Start-up Acts are two of many potential instruments which could be adopted by governments to spur innovation, foster entrepreneurship and facilitate the creation of new start-ups with high growth potential,
- US economic engagement for strengthening economic relations with African states is said to have been inconsistent over the last decade,
- Currently, China is Africa's largest trading partner and equity investor,
- In 2021 around 30% of African debt payments went to China, which is a significant cause for concern.

3.3. Private Sector Innovation Support: Networks, Corporate Involvement and Start-Up Funding (MET)

3.3.1. Tech Hubs and Start-up Support Networks

Technology is driving change and development in almost every industry and area of our lives. It is a critical factor for modern economic growth and development. Sadly, Africa trails behind in terms of technological progress compared to the developed world. However, the continent shows tremendous potential and tech hubs are helping to bridge the gap. Africa's biggest cities are witnessing the development of lively tech realities. Currently, Nigeria, South Africa, and Kenya have the highest number of tech hubs in the continent.

What is A Tech Hub?

Tech hubs are spaces primarily focused on developing a digital entrepreneurship ecosystem, or a network of engagement between digital entrepreneurs, designers, and potential investors. Tech hub structures consist of innovation centres such as accelerators, co-working spaces, marketplaces, and incubators.

Over the past few years, technology ecosystems in Africa have experienced tremendous growth. Increased corporate involvement and venture funds are some of the factors that are driving growth. The ever-growing, innovative communities in the continent have also been driving the current growth of African tech hubs. Furthermore, most technology hubs in Africa are offering communities the infrastructure to support and promote home-grown innovations. These hubs provide training, access to fast internet, and technical support to start-ups. Also, they are offering social and professional networking through which tech entrepreneurs can thrive.

According to research done by AfriLabs and Briter Bridges, Africa has about 643 active hubs, with 10 African cities being home to about 250 tech-hubs, while the rest are spread out throughout the continent. A tech hub of note that has contributed a lot across the continent is AfriLabs, created to support African technology hubs by providing financing, mentoring, networking opportunities and other capacity-building resources for high-potential entrepreneurs. Their vision is to build a thriving innovation economy in Africa, powered by communities. AfriLabs has a broad network of 292 technology and innovation hubs across 49 African countries. As a network organization, AfriLabs works towards the following objectives:

1. Encourage technology, innovation, and entrepreneurship in all forms.
2. Promote the creation of African-made technology, with a special focus on social, economic, and environmental sectors.

3. Provide an environment characterized by open collaboration, technical innovation, and support for the technology community at large.
4. Commitment to capacity building, mentorship, networking and forming bonds that will serve as building blocks for a new generation of thinking.

Start-up Support Networks

StartupBlink Ecosystem Index Report 2021 (StartupBlink, 2021), reports that South Africa is far ahead in terms of having the most developed start-up ecosystem, closely followed by Kenya, Nigeria and Rwanda. Some key support networks from the Big 4 that deserve mentioning, are the CChub, a social innovation centre dedicated to accelerating the application of social capital and technology for economic prosperity. This technology hub is the first in Nigeria to serve as an Open Living Lab, in which user-driven innovation is fully integrated in the co-creative process of new services, products and societal infrastructures.

Then there is the Silicon Cape Initiative, an ecosystem in the Western Cape of South Africa, that serves to attract and bring together local and foreign investors, the brightest technical talent, and the most promising entrepreneurs to foster the creation and growth of world-class IP start-up companies in an environment that competes with other similar hubs around the world against the backdrop of one of the most beautiful settings and pleasant places to live, work and play on the globe.

Startupbootcamp is also a key actor, with a global network of industry-focused accelerators, taking start-ups global by giving them direct access to an international network of the most relevant partners, investors, and mentors in their sector. Impact Hub, a part innovation lab, part business incubator, and part community centre, offers its members a unique ecosystem of resources, inspiration, and collaboration opportunities to grow social entrepreneurship. From Accra to São Paulo, San Francisco to Zurich it provides access to spaces, resources, connections, knowledge, talent, and investments to turn ideas into action. Finally, AfricArena, an African tech accelerator that runs corporate open innovation challenges throughout the African continent, bringing together tech start-ups, corporations and investors to foster co-investment and collaboration that can move the economies and people of the continent forward.

3.3.2. Start-up Funding

More than \$4bn of funding has been raised by start-ups in Africa through 754 deals \$100k in 2021 alone, with the Big 4 tech-ecosystems leading the way with the most funding raised by start-ups across Africa: Nigeria \$1.4b from 215 deals, South Africa \$838m from 118 deals, Egypt \$588m from 119 deals and Kenya \$375 with 119 deals completed (Max Cuvellier and Maxime Bayen)(Figure 37).

Figure 37- Total funding raised by start-ups in 2021

Africa has made great strides in working towards becoming a launch pad for high-tech innovative start-ups/companies. Between 2015 - 2020, the number of African tech start-ups that have received financial backing has grown six times faster than the global average, at 46% annually (Partech, 2020).

Venture Capitalists provide a lot of assistance to start-ups when it comes to funding and supporting a business in scaling up. According to prominent angel investor and Managing partner at *Launch Africa Ventures*, Zacharia George, when looking for investment opportunities, corporates mainly look for repeat start-up founders with a lot of experience, as opposed to a new start-up founder. A founder that has failed before, failed fast and failed forward, stands a better chance of getting funding opportunities from VCs or angel investors. VCs generally look for big Total Addressable Markets (TAM), start-up ideas that solve problems for more than one market, or industry. Start-ups that are ready to disrupt the market through various industries such as ecommerce, education, retail, transport and insurance, attract more

investment/funding opportunities from potential investors. However, Africa's investment/funding landscape for start-ups is slowly changing as more volume of, and less risk averse, venture capital flows into the continent. Today sources for investment capital for African businesses are growing beyond family and government funding.

As reported by SME South Africa (SME South Africa, 2021), International investors are actively searching for African unicorns to invest in with venture capitalists discovering rare opportunities on the continent that offer double digit returns on their investment. In 2017 alone R31.3 billion was invested; a 102% increase over the previous year. Over the past few years, investors have also been seen to move away from wanting to invest just in technology and digital retail. In 2016 the ICT sector made up 30% of all deals, with more money being invested in biotechnology, health and medical devices developed in Africa and AgriTech.

As the amount of money investors are channelling into Africa grows, now is the best time to consider approaching both local and international investors for your start-up. There have been some key players who have been at the forefront of offering funding and investment opportunities to African start-ups: Knife Capital is Cape-based venture capital firm with a focus on post-revenue stage companies that require funding for growth or expansion and a strong product or service offering a scalable business model. Earlier this year, they invested in Skill Up, a Cape Town-based start-up that offers parents and students across South Africa access to thousands of highly skilled and vetted tutors based on grades, subject, location, and budget. Machine learning company, DataProphet, also secured funding from the firm earlier this year. Another key contributor is Kalon Venture Partners, a South Africa-based section 12J venture capital fund and one of a few 12J funds that invests in tech start-ups. Their focus is on disruptive tech start-ups and in 2020 they invested in a shopping app, Snapnsave, solar power financial system, Sun Exchange, and online payment processor, i-Pay. The company invests as little as R110 000 and as much as R20 million into start-ups.

On an African continent stage, Meltwater Entrepreneurial School of Technology (MEST) Africa has been a major contributor towards assisting African tech start-ups scale their ventures. Launched in 2008, MEST is a Pan-African entrepreneurial training programme, seed fund and tech incubator for tech start-ups in Africa. According to Ventureburn, in September last year, \$700 000 was allocated to seven selected African tech start-ups that had graduated from its 2020 training programme. According to its website, they offer investment of \$50k to \$250k to help launch and scale early-stage companies. In addition to funding, MEST offers 18 to 24-month incubation at the MEST hubs and access to MEST's Africa-wide tech community. MEST Africa was founded by the Meltwater Foundation and has incubation hubs located in Accra (Ghana), Lagos (Nigeria), Cape Town (South Africa), and Nairobi (Kenya).

Lastly, VC4Africa is a networking platform that links African businesses with investors and provides mentoring and support for African entrepreneurs. Early this year, they launched Jack Ma Foundation's Africa Netpreneur Prize which offers an annual \$1 million prize for ten new

enterprises that tackle Africa's challenges and further its digital economy through entrepreneurship.

In closing, venture capital funds can widen the pool of potential 'zebras' by making corporate partnerships the heart of their value proposition. Rather than adopting a 'spray and pray' approach to investing, **venture capitalists should provide hands-on support to new businesses by introducing them to potential partners, helping frame win-win collaboration models, and sourcing talent through late funding stages.** Such support could help close the seed-funding gap between Africa and more advanced economies.

Making Africa a more fertile environment for dynamic technology start-ups should become an urgent priority of both the public and private sectors. Doing so will not only generate more zebras and unicorns but also wealth for entrepreneurs and investors. It also will unleash a wave of innovation that will create jobs, economic opportunities, and greater access to health care, finance, and education across the continent (Maher, Laabi, Ivers, & Ngambeket, 2021).

3.3.3. Corporate Involvement

Corporate involvement in the market has been steadily increasing, and we can see that it is hastening the development of disruptive solutions. Corporates can be involved in the tech ecosystem in a variety of ways. In this section, we will enumerate the existing options and make a focus on open innovation challenges and Corporate Venture Capital (CVC).

The first way for a corporation to get involved with the innovation ecosystem is through sponsorship. The AfricArena model, whose main goal is to bridge the gap between entrepreneurs, investors, and corporations through a series of events, is a perfect example. The goal of sponsorship is for a corporation to sponsor a specific event in order to engage with the start-up ecosystem. There are several ecosystem events we can think of such as hackathons, start-up competitions, meet-ups, and conferences to mentioned but a few.

The corporate can also get involved by also developing a mentorship programme, which helps to build long-term relationships with start-ups, by nurturing start-ups through partnerships with incubators or by establishing their own accelerators. Examples of such engagement can be seen with Google Launchpad Accelerator, Facebook NG Hub Lagos, Microsoft Development Centres in Nairobi & Lagos, and IBM SA. A corporation-run incubator or accelerator provides a supportive environment for entrepreneurs. These models are ideal for corporations looking to establish relationships with the ecosystem and gain exposure to emerging solutions and talents. In the following section, we will look at the open innovation challenge model and see how it can foster innovation in Africa.

Open Innovation Challenges

When it comes to innovation, organisations do not have access to all the various resources they require to innovate and are frequently limited to the boundaries of their own company. On the other hand, early-stage start-ups have limited access to market, knowledge and hardware. The majority of the time, corporates will present a problem statement and allow the start-up to propose a solution. If the collaboration is successful, the corporation and the start-up will create a proof-of-concept (PoC), pilots, or a fully implemented product. Indeed, there are different ways of doing open innovation PoCs; partnerships, market access, market intelligence or even venture capital, the options are plentiful and will vary from one programme to another as we can see in Figure 38.

Figure 38- Models of open innovation engagement

Different models of incorporating open innovation		
Compiled by AfricArena (deal information found on Crunchbase and PitchBook)		
Open Innovation	Type	Definition
Inflow	In-sourcing	Use of external knowledge to stimulate internal innovation and reduce time-to-market
	Venture investment	Investing in promising startups to get new ideas and reduce time-to-market
	Customer involvement	Finding new ideas by involving customer feedback
Two ways	co R&D	Conducting R&D activities with external partners
	Alliances and M&A	Building alliances with new businesses or buying them
Outflow	Licensing-out	Granting licenses or selling unused technologies to external business
	Spin-off	Spinning off internal organisations to market
	Open-sourcing	Granting free access to an internal project

From an entrepreneur’s point of view, corporate involvement is still minimal. According to Souleymane Gning, the founder of Assuraf, an Insurtech start-up based in Senegal, *“Corporates are not yet here. They have not embraced digital enough, especially in insurance”*. However, he recognises that corporate involvement *“is absolutely interesting, and potentially another source of funding. That is something that needs to be worked on”*.

Investors also see a lot of potential in corporate involvement. According to Zach George, the Managing partner of Launch Africa, *“Corporates have access to hundreds of thousands of customers, they have customer data, they can help with the ability to test the product and service that the start-up has with the existing customer, and still keep control of who owns the*

customer". However, one of the greatest fears for corporates, according to Zach, is the fear of losing their customer *"if I work with start-ups, they will take my customer away"*.

As an open innovation platform in Africa, AfricArena has gathered valuable experience and data, especially in the areas of in-sourcing, venture investment and R&D. With numerous international companies such as the Air France, KLM Group, Sanofi, Engie Africa, Vinci Energies, Old Mutual, and Saint-Gobain among many others, AfricArena have had the chance to run more than 30 open innovation challenges in the last five years. Various verticals from CleanTech, FinTech, HealthTech and Blockchain are covered by the open innovation challenges.

As we can see, there are great benefices for corporate and start up collaboration through open innovation challenges. Start-ups can benefit from the corporate funding, resources, and access to customers, while corporates can benefit from access to new technologies, top talents and, when it works, return on investment. However, **during the first few months of the COVID-19 crisis, corporations tended to drastically reduce their open innovation in order to focus on their core business. The challenge after the pandemic may be to find the right model for corporate involvement, and we can see that CVC has grown dramatically in recent years.** Large corporations are establishing venture capital funds to assist, partner with, or acquire start-ups.

While there are some similarities, CVC is not the same as institutional VC. CVCs invest corporate funds in start-ups with the goal of gaining a strategic and competitive advantage as well as potential financial returns. Corporates may employ venture investment to speed up their own digital journeys, selecting from various approaches ranging from investing off balance sheet, setting up a dedicated internal fund, or to establishing a separate fund with multiple LPs. As this proves more successful for them, most corporates inevitably end up with a separate fund structure and multi-year capital commitment. CVC funds are analysed as a key strategy for corporates to invest in up-and-coming companies and cutting-edge innovations.

Companies with CVC funds hedge their exposure through a portfolio of minority investments in start-ups while pursuing further opportunities. This enables them to leverage potential opportunities for growth, not only during the current time of disruption, but also to step beyond the post-pandemic environment. In order to drive digital transformation, CVCs can become a powerful complement to other instruments such as in-house R&D, alliances, joint ventures, M&A and corporate innovation programmes. The link between CVC funds and corporate open innovation is strong. According to Llew Claasen, Managing Partner at Newtown Partners, whose fund raised \$10m in early 2020 from Imperial Logistics, *"CVC programmes fit into a wider corporate open innovation programme. It depends on the sophistication and the maturity of the corporate innovation programme as to the way they open up participation to external parties. We think that CVC has the potential to have the*

quickest near-term impact on opportunities that are strategically relevant to corporates. But even then, CVC is not a near term programme, in the sense that it enables corporates to better understand how the ecosystem is developing, and how the overall business will be impacted over a 5 to 10-year time frame.”³⁸

One of the good examples of this is Orange Venture, which is present in most Francophone African countries. The start-up can use the platform and the structure of the corporate to scale all over Africa. Orange Venture works to offer all the infrastructure for start-ups to use their platform to scale in countries such as Senegal, Morocco or where Orange is present. Corporate involvement in the tech ecosystem and innovation can be understood to be generally increasing. The main challenge for corporations now will be to identify the best way to collaborate with start-ups, which could benefit both sides.

Summary:

- **Over the past few years, technology ecosystems in Africa have experienced tremendous growth. Increased corporate involvement and venture funds are some of the factors that are driving growth,**
- **Venture capitalists should provide hands-on support to new businesses by introducing them to potential partners, helping frame win-win collaboration models, and sourcing talent through late funding stages,**
- **Corporate involvement can take many forms, including sponsorship, mentorship, corporate accelerator and incubator programmes, open innovation challenges, Corporate Venture, and many others,**
- **Getting more corporate involvement in innovation and technology, can pave the way for start-ups and corporations to start working together to create value through innovation and entrepreneurship,**
- **As a result of the current COVID-19 crisis, corporations tend to drastically reduce open innovation in order to focus on their core business. The challenge after the pandemic may be to find the right model for corporate involvement,**
- **In recent years, corporate venture capital (CVC) has grown dramatically. Large corporations are forming venture capital funds to help, partner with, or acquire start-ups.**

³⁸ All the findings on this part are from the AfricArena “State of Tech in Africa 2021” report

Chapter 4

Conclusion

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4. Conclusion

4.1. Outcomes of Index Analyses- Chapter 2

The intention of this chapter is to summarise and compare the learnings from chapter 2, which were focused on an analysis of indicators across the rankings of the innovation landscape, the R&D indicators as well as the in-depth GII analysis of the top five countries.

In chapter 2.1, it became apparent that **countries, which cannot rely on strong economic data, can still end up being perceived as an innovative country.** This was shown in that the Innovation Engineers appear higher in the top fifteen countries than the Rising Economies. Such results demonstrate that **innovation-relevant indicators are incredibly important to impacting and generating more competitiveness in the current global climate than economy-relevant indicators alone.**

When considering the GDP and GDP per capital data, it is also clear that innovation success is not dependent on high results in these areas, with countries such as Mauritius having a low GDP and yet achieving the highest rank for Africa with regards to innovation. What is clear, however, is that **in those countries where innovation is strong (as one of the six innovation-relevant categories), a higher overall economic performance is achieved,** even as an average across all seventeen indexes analysed, and a wide variety of indicators evaluated.

Regional location also does not seem to act as a driver for innovation success, with a dispersed level of success achieved by countries within each region across Africa. Mauritius in the East and South Africa in the Southern regions are the highest-ranking countries, in position one and two respectively, however, Tanzania (East) and Namibia (South) are also located in these regions and only reach the rank of twelve and ten respectively. Location and GDP also do not appear to be drivers for the different types of innovation ecosystem, suggesting the independent nature and responsibility of each country's governmental policies and, therefore, the **individual impact that each country can have on their innovation success.**

What is clear, is that the GDP inputs (investments) in R&D directly affect the R&D outputs returned to the economy, however, **governmental investment is not directly responsible for GERD success.** A country's position within the economic income groups can also be seen to directly affect the volumes of GOVERD, with high-income countries depending less on government investments, although not necessarily performing to expectations within these groupings. Where governments are directly affecting the **innovation success of a country is more evident in the investments into the R&D ecosystem, where increasing the numbers of researchers and the conversion of secondary into tertiary education attendance can impact a country's capacity to accelerate their GDP and competitiveness on a global level.** For Africa, the dependency on government spending in R&D is stark, however the success seen for

countries where private financing and R&D is a clear indicator that **a move for African countries towards increasing private financing and investments in R&D, and increasing the number of researchers, could in turn impact GDP** and support them to increase their economic income level grouping.

That said, it is also clear from Table 7, that R&D indicators alone, are not responsible for overall innovation success and global competitiveness. Across all seventeen indexes studies, as well as the GII independently, those countries with the highest R&D success do not also rank in the highest position for innovation overall. In fact, Mauritius, ranking in first place overall and within the GII, only reaches position 9 within the R&D indicator rankings. South Africa also only position 4. The most balanced country across all is Kenya, where a near equal ranking is achieved across all categories. Therefore, if African governments are going to maximise their innovation potential, a balance is required.

Table 7: Comparison between innovation ranking, R&D ranking and GII's ranking of top 10 countries

Country	Overall Rank Innovation Ranking (based on Chapter 2.1)	Overall Rank R&D Indicator Ranking ³⁹ (based on Chapter 2.2)	Overall Rank GII Report Ranking (based on Chapter 2.3)
Mauritius	1	9	1
South Africa	2	4	2
Morocco	3	1 (shared)	4
Tunisia	4	1 (shared)	3
Egypt	5	1 (shared)	7
Kenya	6	5	5
Rwanda	7	18	9
Botswana	8	8	11
Ghana	9	13	14
Namibia	10	12	8

Chapter 2.3 particularly reveals that **innovation success is based on a country's capacity to excel in, and balance, their institutional and market ecosystems**. An increase in the success within more pillars would help to increase their competitiveness and global innovation standing, with a simple balance across pillars alone not providing the required impact. Great success in certain pillars, while helpful, does not support success if other pillars are then performing incredibly low, however, greater success in individual pillars is more valuable than low-scoring balance across all. **A country needs to work on bringing balance across pillars,**

³⁹ Calculation of ranking based on the World Bank's indicators [Gross Expenditure in Research and Development \(GERD\) as % of GDP](#) and [Number of Researchers in R&D \(per million people\)](#)

whilst also raising their success in unison. Countries such as Mauritius and South Africa are very different in terms of population size and GDP but different strengths in multiple indicators across pillars, combined with a relatively balanced achievement across GII pillars, affects their global ranking.

Another insight discovered is that **innovation inputs appear to be more valuable to ranking success than the achievement of outputs.** Both Mauritius and South Africa show greater capacity to provide innovation inputs than outputs and are ranked in positions one and two in Africa respectively. The other countries analysed (Morocco, Tunisia, and Egypt) all have a greater capacity to produce outputs than inputs and are ranked lower overall. This again highlights the **importance of government investment and regulatory efforts in increasing a country's innovation potential.**

One final, but important aspect to note as an outcome from this chapter, is the insights that are provided around the importance of clustering to the success of innovation in a country. In Egypt, the success of their clustering activities has been an important factor in helping them achieve their rankings, a factor which offers them an opportunity to uniquely excel within the African landscape, achieving what no other country has yet done, which is to establish such a cluster.

The World Economic Forum Competitiveness Index Special Report 2020 ⁴⁰ identified that for countries around the world, the presence of S&T Clusters strongly affects the GII ranking and contributes to their performance within their income-level group. This demonstrates that the **development of S&T Clusters across Africa, created through political and financial support to increase S&T activity, would significantly improve the capacity and potential for innovation development and progression.** The GII 2019, referred to as a data point within the GII 2021, revealed that most top S&T clusters are in the U.S., Germany and China, countries also achieving a high position in the GII (ranking in position 3, 10 and 12 respectively), even achieving above expectations within their income group in the case of China. S&T clusters appear to offer a focused area for support that would see the R&D, researcher numbers and innovation outputs increase, supporting an upward movement of the countries involved within the index rankings. S&T clusters provide an insight into the spatial view of innovation performance, which is rooted in the recognition of innovation activities tend across a geographically area, not political, and therefore can spill out across borders, impacting more than one country. **An increase in S&T clustering activities in Egypt, or indeed any of the other countries, could therefore provide a multiplier effect on the success of surrounding countries. Such investments should therefore be shared across various African countries to raise the overall continental success.**

⁴⁰ [World Economic Forum: Global Competitiveness Report 2020](#)

4.2. Outcomes of Start-up Innovation Support Overview – Chapter 3

This chapter seeks to bring together the key results which emerged in chapter 3, focused on the start-up innovation support, both from within Africa as well as from outside of Africa, including public as well as private actors.

As was visible within chapter 3.1, over the past few years, technology ecosystems in Africa have experienced tremendous growth. Africa can rely on a diverse mix of innovation ecosystems in many of its countries. **Due to the continent's youthful and growing population, rising internet penetration, and the application of emerging technologies, Africa provides a fertile environment for tech entrepreneurs.** The continent's fifty-four countries are very diverse, however, they are not all on the same level when it comes to innovation. **The major share of innovation activity takes place in only a few countries, such as Egypt, Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa. Other countries, such as Senegal and Tunisia, have been improving their innovation ecosystems in recent years, however.** Overall, some key barriers exist, which should be tackled in order for African countries to further grow its distinct innovation ecosystems. **These major barriers are the following:**

- **A lack of adequate funding is the most significant barriers for African entrepreneurs.** In Africa, the return on venture capital investment is low. Data access is another obstacle to attracting funding in Africa, with information being scarce and fragmented,
- Infrastructure is required for innovation to function and drive economic growth. Since **Africa is severely lacking in basic developed infrastructure**, meeting the demand for critical infrastructure has been identified as a top priority for African countries and specifically governments,
- **A major challenge is to attract talent**, as there is a lack of graduates as well as a gap in the entrepreneur's education on how venture capital investment works. One opportunity for Africa is to therefore strengthen the talent pool by retaining talents into their home country.

The scarcity of talents is reflected by the lack of strong incubators, accelerators, and mentorship programmes across the region, that are truly capable of improving the investment readiness of start-ups. Rather than establishing new incubators or accelerators, those already in place could collaborate with international ones with extensive experience to find long-term revenue streams by imitating leaders in the space. Overall, **more collaboration seems to be a necessary measure to grow African innovation ecosystems**, which is shared by various ecosystem actors across several African countries. As stated by Giuliani and Ajadi (2019), there exists a need for more consolidation and collaboration. That this is becoming more of a reality

is visible in the increased number of hub alliances and shared initiatives, as well as by deeper conversations among stakeholders across the continent (Giuliani & Ajadi, 2019).

Generally, though, as Isaac already noticed in 2015, that whilst innovation is booming to some degree across the continent, there is a pressing need to grow and nurture innovations, so that they are able to compete effectively in a global context. All the existing barriers and gaps currently in the innovation ecosystem need to be faced by both effectively tackling the economy, while actively trying to create a thriving innovation ecosystem. For this, **investments in education and the development of innovation hubs and workshops would help develop local talent** (Isaac, 2015). **This and the provision of funding as well as better infrastructure requires both public and private actors to become more engaged.**

In the public sector realm (chapter 0), three important levels of engagement with regard to innovation can be perceived: 1. Intragovernmental level 2. National governmental level 3. Foreign countries. At the first level of engagement are major intragovernmental actors related to STI in Africa, including **the African Union, the African Development Bank, the Islamic Development Bank, the World Bank, among others. These actors either provide overarching agendas and strategies, specific initiatives, including on-the-ground projects, or financing.** Agendas and strategies are specifically published by the AU's, with major ones being the Agenda 2063, its Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2024 as well as the Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa. Key initiatives are AfDB's Jobs for Youth in Africa Strategy or IsDB's Engage Digital Hub, or the World Bank's Gender Innovation lab as well as its XL Africa project. Financing is oftentimes provided by the World Bank Group's International Development Association and the International Finance Corporation. It is to be proven, if all these initiatives can provide real tangible results in the African countries, leading to a growth in their respective innovation ecosystems.

The second level of engagement represent the different African countries and specifically their government activities. In recent years, a large number of **African countries have started developing, adopting and/or reviewing their STI strategies and policies, as well as adopting more supportive legislative framework for SMEs and start-ups in form of SBAs and Start-up Acts.** Start-up Acts are a rather new and holistic form of supporting start-ups and SMEs, which include various interventions, such as tax exemptions, subsidies, procurement or pre-seed financing, improvement of digital governance, depending on the country. They have been adopted in Tunisia (2018) and Senegal (2019), while various other African countries are considering or developing them. It is to be seen if they can achieve their potential of supporting the countries' innovation ecosystems. **Governments in Africa should overall do more to improve their oftentimes unfavourable regulatory and investment environments for start-ups,** which make it difficult to launch, grow, and scale an innovative business. Related to this is the fact that innovation activity is heavily concentrated in only a few African countries, proving a risk for many countries to get left further behind. As Guchu (2021) points

out, in the majority of African countries, R&I initiatives are implemented in a fragmented manner, without effectively and sufficiently engaging the private sector (Guchu, 2021). Besides this, **various challenges exist in developing and implementing STI policies, including limited data and monitoring; insufficient funding; lacking capacity and skills; insufficient policy designs; policy inconsistency and missing implementation; and particularly weak linkages between other policies and to stakeholders.** However, since African countries have low levels of savings, it is imperative for them to collaborate with other actors (i.e., private sector and stakeholders outside their own countries) to be able to follow a long-term innovation policy. Clear and robust legislation, which enables start-ups to operate with certainty, and which is provided by a well-defined framework for growth, is an aspiration the countries should aim to work towards to. As Isaac noted in 2015, to support a robust innovation environment, it is imperative for governments themselves to be innovative, adopt structural reforms that curb bureaucracy and boost the ease of doing business. Overall, a business-friendly environment, which attracts innovative companies from around the world should be developed, while at the same time massive educational reforms are needed which seek to upskill the local population (Isaac, 2015).

The third level of engagement is through the various foreign countries which have renewed their interest in the African continent, which can be seen in the investments granted, projects implemented, as well as new initiatives started, and summits taken place in recent years with African partners. These major countries are China, the US, the UK, France, India and the UAE, among others. In this report, four countries were analysed, being China, India, the UK as well as the US.

Until 2018, the **UK could count on various research initiatives with the African continent.** Since then, though, a shift could be seen in that **investments also flowed into more innovation-related initiatives, across several African** (mostly South Africa, Kenya and Nigeria), including the establishment of teams to boost technology innovation, an accelerator programme, tech hubs and entrepreneurship schemes. In 2020, a further impetus was provided in the form of the first ever UK-Africa Investment Summit. It is still to be seen if the UK is able to provide support to help advance Africa's innovation environments.

In comparison, the **US is more focused on strengthening trade and private sector investments,** specifically with its Prosper Africa government initiative from 2018 as well as USAID's 2018 'Private-Sector Engagement Policy'. Despite these initiatives, US economic engagement for strengthening economic relations with African states is said to have been inconsistent over the last decade and rather modest short-term time horizon been inconsistent over the last decade. It is to be seen if the US changes its approach in the upcoming years.

China has been deeply involved in Africa in the last two decades with regard to setting up infrastructure and extending its economic ties with Africa in trade (both mostly through its

BRI); all with the intention to build long-term partnerships. This led to China being Africa's largest trading partner and equity investor. The majority of cooperation and exchanges with African governments takes place within the FOCAC. Its 2021 adopted Dakar Action Plan (2022-2024) demonstrates that a **more digital route between China and African countries shall be established** in order to boost the innovative development of digital technology and promote the building of information society in Africa as well as enhance information sharing, including elevating the digital capacity SMEs. This is also explicitly stated in the 'China-Africa Digital Innovation Partnership Program'. Moreover, both regions seek to enhance synergies between STI strategies and policies to fully leverage STI.

India has been engaged in supporting Africa towards S&T development, particularly since 2008, when the basis for this was laid during the 2008 IAFS, which is the major platform between both regions aiming to develop strategies that seek to strengthening the existing India-Africa partnership. **The support includes various initiatives, such as technology cooperation agreements, IT centres, training programmes and technical assistance.** Scope for collaboration exists with regard to the green economy as well as in the digital technology sector. It is to be seen if both regions will interact more towards developing these areas.

In Chapter 0, different types of private sector support for start-ups was then discussed, among others, focused on capacity building (via tech hubs, start-up support networks and corporate involvement) and funding (via venture funds as well as corporate venture capital) based on the fact that start-up support networks, increased corporate involvement and venture funds are some of the factors that are driving growth in the existing innovation ecosystems. Regarding the aspect of capacity building, **tech hubs (i.e. innovation centres such as accelerators, co-working spaces, marketplaces, and incubators) are a key component in Africa's innovation advancements**, primarily focused on developing a digital entrepreneurship ecosystem, or a network of engagement between digital entrepreneurs, designers, and potential investors. In Africa, the ever-growing, innovative communities on the continent have been driving the current growth of African tech hubs. Africa has about 643 active hubs, with 10 African cities being home to about 250 tech-hubs. **Major start-up support networks are CChub, Startupbootcamp, Impact Hub as well as AfricArena.** Besides tech hubs and start-up support networks, corporate involvement plays a major role for African innovation ecosystems. It can take many forms, including sponsorship, mentorship, corporate accelerator and incubator programmes, open innovation challenges, and many others. **Getting more corporate involvement in innovation and technology can pave the way for start-ups and corporations to start working together to create value through innovation and entrepreneurship.** As a result of the current COVID-19 crisis, corporations tend to drastically reduce open innovation in order to focus on their core business. The challenge after the pandemic may be to find the right model for corporate involvement. Funding is, among other things, driven by venture capital. It is said that **venture capitalists should provide hands-on support to new businesses by introducing them to potential partners, helping frame win-**

win collaboration models, and sourcing talent through late funding stages. In recent years, CVC has grown dramatically. Currently, large corporations are forming venture capital funds to help, partner with, or acquire start-ups. According to Maher, Laabi, Ivers and Ngambeket (2021), large enterprises have the assets and means required to overcome Africa's ecosystem challenges, in form of capital, expertise as well as presence in multiple markets. African governments and tech innovators will have, according to them, a greater chance of success if they collaborate with such larger corporations. Additionally, governments should offer financial incentives and issue mandates for larger enterprises to collaborate with and foster start-up development (Maher, Laabi, Ivers, & Ngambeket, 2021).

Overall, according to Giuliani and Ajadi (2019), the progressive alignment of interests and agendas of the different stakeholders could help strengthen the innovation ecosystems in Africa. This, however, requires the different stakeholder in the ecosystem to understand each other's roles more comprehensively. If a more accurate and thorough taxonomy of the various players was to be created, investors and donors would likely intensify the dialogue with existing players and as a result, be able to create more impact (Giuliani & Ajadi, 2019). According to Golubski and Holtz (2021), to support innovation endeavours that drive job creation, economic opportunities, etc. in Africa, both governments and corporate enterprises could facilitate strategic alliances with local start-ups. **From the point of view of the private sector, such alliances with start-ups can help introduce new digital technologies as well as innovative business models that are advantageous and beneficial for the larger enterprise, the start-up, as well as consumers. From the perspective of the public sector, providing financial incentives for investors and large (national) companies, seeking to collaborate with start-ups and nurture these, have the potential to further develop and strengthen innovation hubs that draw foreign investment and talent (Golubski & Holtz, 2021).** Moreover, public-private networks could facilitate the collaboration between governments, private sector and novel start-ups, as well as establish improved capacity development and funding provision. Existing public-private networks are i4policy, the Africa Innovation Network, the African Innovation Alliance, the Pan African Capacity Building Programme as well as VC4Africa.

References

References

- Africa Foresight Group; Harambeans. (2020). *African Innovation Report - Understanding Market-Creating Innovation Across Africa*. Africa Foresight Group.
- African Development Bank. (2016). *Jobs for Youth in Africa*. African Development Bank.
- African Development Bank. (2019). *Brochure - Promoting Africa as global player through high level policy dialogue on STI*. Retrieved from African Development Bank: <https://www.afdb.org/en/documents/document/brochure-promoting-africa-as-global-player-through-high-level-policy-dialogue-on-sti-109446>
- African Development Bank Group. (2021, July 17). *Close partnership between India and Africa could improve the welfare of 2.5 billion people post Covid-19, participants at 2021 Indo-Africa business conclave say*. Retrieved from African Development Bank Group: <https://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/press-releases/close-partnership-between-india-and-africa-could-improve-welfare-25-billion-people-post-covid-19-participants-2021-indo-africa-business-conclave-say-44712>
- African Development Bank. (n.d.). *Boost Africa: Empowering Young African Entrepreneurs*. Retrieved from <https://www.afdb.org/en/topics-and-sectors/initiatives-partnerships/boost-africa-empowering-young-african-entrepreneurs>
- African Development Bank. (n.d.). *Jobs for Youth in Africa - Flagship Programs*. Retrieved from African Development Bank: <https://www.afdb.org/en/topics-and-sectors/initiatives-partnerships/jobs-for-youth-in-africa/flagship-programs>
- African Development Bank. (n.d.). *Jobs for Youth in Africa - Youth Entrepreneurship and Innovation Multi-Donor Trust Fund*. Retrieved from African Development Bank: <https://www.afdb.org/en/topics-and-sectors/initiatives-partnerships/jobs-for-youth-in-africa/the-youth-entrepreneurship-and-innovation-multi-donor-trust-fund>
- African Development Bank. (n.d.). *The High 5s*. Retrieved from African Development Bank: <https://www.afdb.org/en/high5s>
- African Export-Import Bank. (2021, October 22). *Africa Must Close Its Science And Technology Gap To Take Full Advantage Of The AfCFTA Says Ameenah Gurib-Fakim At Afreximbank's Fifth Annual Babacar Ndiaye Lecture*. Retrieved from <https://www.afreximbank.com/africa-must-close-its-science-and-technology-gap-to-take-full-advantage-of-the-afcfta-says-ameenah-gurib-fakim-at-afreximbanks-fifth-annual-babacar-ndiaye-lecture/>

- African Union. (2019). *CONTEXTUALISING STISA-2024: Africa's STI Implementation Report*. African Union.
- African Union. (2019). *THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGY FOR AFRICA (2020-2030)*. African Union.
- African Union Commission. (2014). *Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2024*. African Union Commission.
- African Union Commission. (n.d.). *Agenda 2063 - The Africa We Want*. African Union Commission.
- African Union Commission. (n.d.). *Agenda 2063 - The Africa We Want*. Retrieved from African Union: <https://au.int/agenda2063>
- AfricArena. (2020). *The State of Tech Innovation in Africa - Perspectives from founders, investors and corporates*. AfricArena.
- AfricArena. (2021). *The State of Tech in Africa 2021*. AfricArena.
- Anshan, L. e. (2012). *The Forum on China-Africa Cooperation: From a Sustainable Perspective*. WWF.
- AUDA-NEPAD. (2019). *African Innovation Outlook III*. Johannesburg.
- AU-EU High Level Policy Dialogue. (2020). *Concept Note - Innovation and Digitalisation*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/documents/5_concept_note_hlpd_innovation_and_digitalisation_0.pdf
- Barry, K., & Adoh, O. (2021, April 5). *Private equity in Africa: Trends and opportunities in 2021*. Retrieved from <https://www.whitecase.com/publications/insight/africa-focus-spring-2021/private-equity-africa-trends-and-opportunities-2021>
- Basu, K., Narayan, V., & Gera, A. (2020). *Unlocking the potential of India-Africa collaboration for healthcare innovation*. PricewaterhouseCoopers.
- Bischof, J. (2021, June 6). *Why African startups are lobbying governments for more regulation*. Retrieved from Yahoo Finance: https://finance.yahoo.com/news/why-african-startups-lobbying-governments-083044150.html?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAAJQLSHGbFJ_hTpvBfvJ6Lks3nj0z_2eNC4yEjXs1dmYnqoF6mNJjoqG7dqel9PdDtbFWKqKoZGXbhLJ7U2R-48

- Carr, E. (2020, September 4). *The US Versus China Investment in Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/earlcarr/2020/09/04/the-us-versus-chinese-investment-in-africa/?sh=4faafdf65d4c>
- Chakrabarty, M. (2021, April 26). *India-Africa relations: Partnership, COVID-19 setback and the way forward*. Retrieved from <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/india-africa-relations-partnership-covid19-setback-way-forward/>
- Cirera, X., & Maloney, W. (2017). *The Innovation Paradox: Developing-Country Capabilities and Unrealized Promise of Technological Catch-Up*. International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank.
- Cohen, Z., & Steiger, J. (2021, May 24). *On Africa Day, Celebrating U.S.-Africa Partnership and Cooperation*. Retrieved from <https://www.usglc.org/blog/on-africa-day-celebrating-u-s-africa-partnership-and-cooperation/>
- Confederation of Indian Industry. (2021, July 26). *India-Africa: Harnessing the Africa-India opportunity*. Retrieved from Confederation of Indian Industry: <https://www.ciiblog.in/india-africa-harnessing-the-africa-india-opportunity/>
- Corporate Council on Africa. (2021). *U.S.-Africa Business Summit 2021*. Retrieved from Corporate Council on Africa: <https://cca.glueup.com/event/u-s-africa-business-summit-2021-35917/>
- Devonshire-Ellis, C. (2021, December 2). *China Pledges US\$40 Billion In Multiple Infrastructure Projects For Africa*. Retrieved from Silk Road Briefing: <https://www.silkroadbriefing.com/news/2021/12/02/china-pledges-us40-billion-in-multiple-infrastructure-projects-for-africa/>
- Diop, M. (2017, November 30). *Innovation in Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/speech/2017/11/30/innovation-in-africa>
- Duffy, A. (2021, April 19). *African Tech Ecosystems of the Future — the dawn of a new era*. Retrieved from <https://www.fdiintelligence.com/article/79638>
- E4E Arab Youth. (n.d.). *About E4E*. Retrieved from E4E Arab Youth: <http://www.e4earabyouth.com/en/aboute4e/>
- Ecosystem Build. (2020). *Small Business Acts and Startup Acts in Africa*. Ecosystem Build.
- EY Global. (2020, September 11). *Why Africa is becoming a bigger player in the global economy*. Retrieved from https://www.ey.com/en_gl/tax/why-africa-is-becoming-a-bigger-player-in-the-global-economy

- Fanny, D. (2019, May 2). *Understanding the tech ecosystem in Francophone Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.entrepreneantaefrique.com/en/understanding-the-tech-ecosystem-in-francophone-africa/>
- Fosci, M., & Loffreda, L. (2019). *Strengthening Research Institutions in Africa: A Synthesis Report*. UK Department for International Development.
- Gachie, W., & Govender, D. (2017). Innovation Policy And Governance In The African Region. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 119-130.
- Giuliani, D., & Ajadi, S. (2019, July 10). *618 active tech hubs: The backbone of Africa's tech ecosystem*. Retrieved from <https://www.gsma.com/mobilefordevelopment/blog/618-active-tech-hubs-the-backbone-of-africas-tech-ecosystem/>
- Golubski, C., & Holtz, L. (2021, June 26). *The rise of African tech startups in 3 charts*. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/06/africa-tech-startups-technology-economics/>
- Guchu, S. (2021, June 10). *Africa's innovation gap: A view from Kenya*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-africa-views-2021-6-africa-s-innovation-gap-a-view-from-kenya/>
- Hlophe, S., Crous, S., & Custers, S. (2019). *How can bold action become everyday action? - EY Attractiveness Program Africa*. EYGM Ltd.
- Hochadel, A., & Wells, I. (2019). *African Cities Innovation Analysis*. Connected Places Catapult .
- Human Development Innovation Fund (HDIF). (n.d.). *Human Development Innovation Fund (HDIF)*. Retrieved from <https://hdif-tz.org/>
- Ikounga, M. (n.d.). *Science, Technology And Innovation Strategy For Africa 2024 (STISA-2024)*. Retrieved from Africa Policy Review.
- Ingram, G. (2018, July 10). *How the BUILD Act advances development*. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/future-development/2018/07/10/how-the-build-act-advances-development/#:~:text=The%20Better%20Utilization%20of%20Investments,House%20and%20Senate%20authorizing%20committees.>
- International Finance Corporation. (n.d.). *IFC in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Retrieved from International Finance Corporation:

https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/region__ext_content/IFC_External_Corporate_Site/Sub-Saharan+Africa

International Finance Corporation. (n.d.). *IFC's Priorities in the Middle East and North Africa*. Retrieved from International Finance Corporation: https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/region__ext_content/ifc_external_corporate_site/middle+east+and+north+africa/priorities

Investment Climate Reform Facility. (2021, April 22). *Startup Acts: an emerging instrument to foster the development of innovative high-growth firms*. Retrieved from Investment Climate Reform Facility: https://www.icr-facility.eu/fileadmin/files/downloads/event_flyers/event_presentations/startup_act_22.04.2021__2_.pdf

Isaac, J. (2015, August 25). *Where is Africa on the Innovation Landscape?* Retrieved from LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/where-africa-innovation-landscape-judith-objajulu-isaac>

Islamic Development Bank - STI Department. (2019). *Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) Policy for the IsDB*. Retrieved from <https://www.isdb.org/sites/default/files/media/documents/2020-02/STI%20Policy.pdf>

Islamic Development Bank. (n.d.). *Engage*. Retrieved from ENGAGE: <https://www.isdb-engage.org/>

Islamic Development Bank. (n.d.). *Transform Fund*. Retrieved from ENGAGE: <https://www.isdb-engage.org/en/page/transform-fund-en>

Jayaram, K., Kassiri, O., & Sun, I. (2017, June 28). *The closest look yet at Chinese economic engagement in Africa*. Retrieved from McKinsey & Company: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/middle-east-and-africa/the-closest-look-yet-at-chinese-economic-engagement-in-africa>

Knowledge Transfer Network. (n.d.). *KTN Global Alliance Africa*. Retrieved from Knowledge Transfer Network: <https://ktn-uk.org/programme/africa/>

Madden, P. (2019, October 9). *Figure of the week: Foreign direct investment in Africa*. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/africa-in-focus/2019/10/09/figure-of-the-week-foreign-direct-investment-in-africa/>

Maher, H., Laabi, A., Ivers, L., & Ngambeket, G. (2021, April 12). *Overcoming Africa's Tech Startup Obstacles - How established enterprises can help the region's innovators scale*

- up. Retrieved from <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2021/new-strategies-needed-to-help-tech-startups-in-africa>
- McGee-Abe, J. (2018, November 14). *OPIC gives \$100m backing to Africell to boost Connect Africa initiative*. Retrieved from Capacity Media: <https://www.capacitymedia.com/articles/3822699/opic-gives-100m-backing-to-africell-to-boost-connect-africa-initiative>
- Millenium Challenge Corporation. (2021, July 27). *MCC Commits More Than \$1 Billion in New Programs for Africa*. Retrieved from Millenium Challenge Corporation: <https://www.mcc.gov/news-and-events/release/release-072721-mcc-commits-over-1-billion-in-new-programs-for-africa>
- Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India. (2015, October 19). *India-Africa cooperation in science and Technology – Capacity Building*. Retrieved from Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India: <https://mea.gov.in/in-focus-article.htm?25947/IndiaAfrica+cooperation+in+science+and+Technology++Capacity+Building>
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China. (2021, August 24). *China will work with Africa to formulate and implement a China-Africa Partnership Plan on Digital Innovation*. Retrieved from Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China: https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/eng/wjbxw/202108/t20210825_9134687.html
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China. (2021, November 30). *Forum on China-Africa Cooperation Dakar Action Plan (2022-2024)*. Retrieved from Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China: https://www.fmprc.gov.cn/mfa_eng/zxxx_662805/202112/t20211202_10461183.html
- Namubiru-Mwaura, E., & Marincola, E. (2018). *Africa Beyond 2030 - Leveraging Knowledge And Innovation To Secure Sustainable Development Goals*. Nairobi, Kenya: African Academy of Sciences.
- Neto, I., & Rogy, M. (2021, September 22). *Too many Africans cannot access the technology they need. A World Bank initiative aims to help reverse that*. Retrieved from World Bank Blogs: <https://blogs.worldbank.org/digital-development/too-many-africans-cannot-access-technology-they-need-world-bank-initiative-aims>
- Olasoji, T. (2021, May 25). *Nigeria has the most startups in Africa but falls short on other critical metrics*. Retrieved from <https://qz.com/africa/2012780/nigeria-ranks-first-in-african-startups-but-faces-challenges/>

- Ottaway, R. (2021, March 23). *UK – Africa: Britain must act quickly to boost trade and investment across the continent*. Retrieved from The Africa Report: <https://www.theafricareport.com/74185/uk-africa-britain-must-act-quickly-to-boost-trade-and-investment-across-the-continent/>
- Partech. (2020). *2020 Africa Tech Venture Capital Report*. Partech.
- Paul, E. (2021, October 1). *Startup Acts: Can the decade's sexiest law save Nigeria's thriving but uncertain startup ecosystem?* Retrieved from Techpoint Africa: <https://techpoint.africa/2021/10/01/nigerias-proposed-startup-bill/>
- Runde, D., Savoy, C., & Staguhn, J. (2021, October 15). *China and SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Window of Opportunity for the United States*. Retrieved from Center for Strategic & International Studies: <https://www.csis.org/analysis/china-and-smes-sub-saharan-africa-window-opportunity-united-states>
- Sadeski, F., Kouacou, K., & Ploeg, M. (2019). *Innovation Policy in Africa: Catching-up or Leapfrogging ahead?* Retrieved from Technopolis Group: <https://www.technopolis-group.com/innovation-policy-in-africa-catching-up-or-leapfrogging-ahead/>
- ShareAmerica. (2021, November 15). *Prosper Africa: U.S. and African businesses growing together*. Retrieved from ShareAmerica: <https://share.america.gov/prosper-africa-us-african-businesses-growing-together/>
- Shepard, W. (2019, October 3). *What China Is Really Up To In Africa*. Retrieved from Forbes: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/wadeshepard/2019/10/03/what-china-is-really-up-to-in-africa/?sh=63699c5e5930>
- Si, M., & Zhihua, L. (2021, December 3). *China-Africa ties to spur digital field*. Retrieved from State Council of the People's Republic of China: http://english.www.gov.cn/news/international/exchanges/202112/03/content_WS61a96889c6d0df57f98e5f5a.html
- Signé, L., & Schneidmann, W. (2018, December 3). *Placing investment at the center of Africa's development strategy*. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/africa-in-focus/2018/12/03/placing-investment-at-the-center-of-africas-development-strategy/>
- Singh, G. (2021, January 5). *Rethinking India's engagement with the African Union*. Retrieved from Observer Research Foundation: <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/rethinking-india-engagement-african-union/>

- Smart Africa. (2020). *Who We Are*. Retrieved from Smart Africa: <https://smartafrica.org/who-we-are/>
- SME South Africa. (2021, February 1). *Funding Opportunities: A List Of Investors That Back SA Startups*. Retrieved from SME South Africa: <https://smesouthafrica.co.za/investors-invest-south-africa-startups/>
- Songwe, V. (2020, January 8). *A continental strategy for economic diversification through the AfCFTA and intellectual property rights*. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/research/a-continental-strategy-for-economic-diversification-through-the-afcfta-and-intellectual-property-rights/>
- South African Government. (2021, October 21). *Minister Blade Nzimande: 1st China-Africa Conference on Innovation Cooperation*. Retrieved from South African Government: <https://www.gov.za/speeches/minister-blade-nzimande-1st-china-africa-conference-innovation-cooperation-20-oct-2021-0000>
- Sow, M. (2018, September 6). *Figures of the week: Chinese investment in Africa*. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/africa-in-focus/2018/09/06/figures-of-the-week-chinese-investment-in-africa/>
- Startup Act South Africa. (n.d.). *Startup Act South Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.startupact.co.za/>
- StartupBlink. (2021). *The Global Startup Ecosystem Index Report by StartupBlink*. Retrieved from <https://www.startupblink.com/blog/global-startup-ecosystem-index/>
- te Velde, W. (2020, July 10). *It's time for the UK to reset its relationship with African countries*. Retrieved from Overseas Development Institute (ODI): <https://odi.org/en/insights/its-time-for-the-uk-to-reset-its-relationship-with-african-countries/>
- Twiringiyimana, R., Daniels, C., & Chataway, J. (2021). STI policy and governance in Sub-Saharan Africa: Fostering actors' interactions in research and innovation. *Industry and Higher Education*, 609-624.
- U.S. African Development Foundation. (n.d.). *U.S. African Development Foundation*. Retrieved from <https://www.usadf.gov/>
- U.S. International Development Finance Corporation. (2018, July 2). *OPIC Launches Connect Africa Initiative to Invest More Than \$1 Billion Supporting Infrastructure, Communications, and Value Chain Connectivity*. Retrieved from U.S. International Development Finance Corporation: <https://www.dfc.gov/media/opic-press-releases/opic-launches-connect-africa-initiative-invest-more-1-billion-supporting>

- Udoh, C. (2021, February 21). *Mali Startup Act Back On Track After Military Junta*. Retrieved from Afrikan Heroes: <https://afrikanheroes.com/2021/02/21/mali-startup-act-back-on-track-after-military-junta/>
- UK Government. (2018, August 29). *Ambitious new Innovation Partnerships with African countries*. Retrieved from UK Government: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/ambitious-new-innovation-partnerships-with-african-countries>
- UK Government. (2020, January 20). *UK Government Statement on the UK-Africa Investment Summit*. Retrieved from UK Government: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-government-statement-on-the-uk-africa-investment-summit>
- UK Government. (n.d.). *UK Science and Innovation Network*. Retrieved from UK Government: <https://www.gov.uk/world/organisations/uk-science-and-innovation-network>
- UK Research and Innovation. (n.d.). *Global Challenges Research Fund*. Retrieved from UK Research and Innovation: <https://www.ukri.org/our-work/collaborating-internationally/global-challenges-research-fund/>
- UNECA. (2016). *Assessing Regional Integration in Africa VII*. United Nations.
- UNECA. (2016). *Assessing Regional Integration in Africa VII*. United Nations.
- United Nations Development Programme. (n.d.). *Accelerator Labs*. Retrieved from <https://acceleratorlabs.undp.org/>
- van de Walle, N. (2009). US-Afrikapolitik: Bushs Vermächtnis und die Regierung Obama. *GIGA Focus Afrika*.
- von Soest, C. (2021). The End of Apathy: The New Africa Policy under Joe Biden. *GIGA Focus Afrika*.
- Wilkins, S. (2021, March 30). "Why Are We in Africa?": *The Dilemmas of Making American Strategy towards the African Continent*. Retrieved from The Strategy Bridge: <https://thestrategybridge.org/the-bridge/2021/3/30/why-are-we-in-africa>
- Wolken, J. (2020, December 9). *Startup Acts are the next form of policy innovation in Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/africasource/startup-acts-are-the-next-form-of-policy-innovation-in-africa/>

- World Bank. (2020, July 27). *The African Continental Free Trade Area*. Retrieved from World Bank: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/trade/publication/the-african-continental-free-trade-area>
- World Bank Group. (n.d.). *ACE II - Eastern and Southern Africa Higher Education Centers of Excellence Project*. Retrieved from <https://ace2.iucea.org/>
- World Bank. (n.d.). *A Digital Strategy for Africa*. Retrieved from World Bank: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/all-africa-digital-transformation>
- World Bank. (n.d.). *Africa Gender Innovation Lab (GIL)*. Retrieved from World Bank: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/africa-gender-innovation-lab#1>
- World Bank. (n.d.). *IDA - Driving Innovation in Africa*.
- World Intellectual Property Organisation. (2021). *Global Innovation Index 2021- Tackling Innovation Through the COVID-19 Crisis*. Geneva: World Intellectual Property Organization.
- Xinhua Net. (2021, November 26). *China and Africa in the New Era: A Partnership of Equals*. Retrieved from Xinhua Net: http://www.news.cn/english/2021-11/26/c_1310333813.htm
- XL Africa. (n.d.). *XL Africa*. Retrieved from <https://www.xl-africa.com/>
- Young African Leaders Initiative. (n.d.). *About YALI*. Retrieved from Young African Leaders Initiative: <https://yali.state.gov/about/>
- Ze Yu, S. (2021, April 2). *Why substantial Chinese FDI is flowing into Africa*. Retrieved from <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/africaatlse/2021/04/02/why-substantial-chinese-fdi-is-flowing-into-africa-foreign-direct-investment/>

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Indexes and rankings used for analysis- section 2.1

Table 8: Rankings/Indexes used for analysis

Nr.	Category	Index/Ranking	Publisher	Year		Names Pillars	Results African Countries
1	Innovation	Global Innovation Index (GII)	Cornell University; INSEAD; World Intellectual Property Organization	2021	The GII measures countries' capacity for, and success in, innovation.	<u>7 Pillars:</u> Institutions, Human capital and research, Infrastructure, Market sophistication, Business sophistication, Knowledge and technology outputs, Creative outputs	52 – 132 2 African countries in highest 50% Total: 132
2	Start-ups & Entrepreneurship	Global Start-up Ecosystem Index (GSEI)	Start-up Blink	2021	The GSEI ranks the start-up ecosystems around the world.	<u>3 Pillars:</u> Quantity Score, Quality of start-ups & supporting organization, Business environment	48 – 100 1 African country in highest 50% Total: 100
3	Start-ups & Entrepreneurship	African Tech Ecosystems of the Future	Financial Times, Briter Bridges	2021	The African Tech Ecosystems of the Future ranking ranks the continent's nascent tech ecosystems and their potential moving forward.	<u>5 Pillars:</u> Economic Potential, Business Friendliness, Human Capital and Lifestyle, Cost Effectiveness, Connectivity	Ranking only focused on African countries Total: 17
4	Start-ups & Entrepreneurship	Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI)	Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute	2019	The GEI measures the health of entrepreneurship ecosystems.	<u>14 Pillars:</u> Economic freedom & rights, Education, Connectivity, Country risk, Corruption, Tax & governance, Labour market, Comp regulation, Tech absorption, Technology transfer, Science, Finance & strategy, Economic complexity, Depth of capital market	51 – 137 5 African countries in highest 50% Total: 137

5	Economic & Regulatory Environment	Global Competitiveness Index (GCI)	World Economic Forum	2019	The GCI measures the set of institutions, policies, and factors that set the sustainable current and medium-term levels of economic prosperity.	<u>4 Pillars:</u> Enabling environment, Human capital, Markets, Innovation ecosystem	52 – 141 2 African countries in highest 50% Total: 141
6	Economic & Regulatory Environment	Doing Business Index (DBI)	World Bank	2020	The DBI measures the regulations that enhance business activity and those that constrain it.	<u>10 Pillars:</u> Starting a Business, Dealing with Construction Permits, Getting Electricity, Registering Property, Getting Credit, Protecting Minority Investors, Paying Taxes, Trading across Borders, Enforcing Contracts, Resolving Insolvency	13 – 190 8 African countries in highest 50% Total: 190
7	Economic & Regulatory Environment	Index of Economic Freedom	The Heritage Foundation; The Wall Street Journal	2021	The Index of Economic Freedom measures the degree of economic freedom in the world's nations.	<u>10 Pillars:</u> Rule of Law, Government Size, Regulatory Efficiency, Open Markets	13 – 175 5 African countries in highest 50% Total: 178
8	Economic & Regulatory Environment	Global Attractiveness Index (GAI)	The European House - Ambrosetti	2021	The GAI measures the attractiveness and competitive sustainability of countries.	<u>3 Pillars:</u> Attractiveness, Dynamism, Sustainability and Growth Expectations	67 – 145 2 African countries in highest 50% Total: 148
9	Investment Attractiveness	RMB Investment Attractiveness Ranking	Rand Merchant Bank (RMB)	2020	The RMB Investment Attractiveness Ranking ranks investment attractive countries in Africa, aimed at investors targeting real assets in an economy or looking to expand businesses that rely on physical infrastructure.	<u>2 Pillars:</u> Economic activity, Operating environment	40 – 124 3 African countries in highest 50% Total: 125

10	Investment Attractiveness	Venture Capital & Private Equity Country Attractiveness Index	University of Navarra IESE Business School & EMLYON Business School	2021	The Venture Capital & Private Equity Country Attractiveness Index measures the attractiveness of a country for investors in Venture Capital and Private Equity assets	<u>6 Pillars:</u> Economic Activity, Depth of Capital Market, Taxation, Investor Protection and Corporate Governance, Human and Social Environment, Entrepreneurial Culture and Deal Opportunities	70 – 124 Ranking only focused on African countries Total: 125
11	Investment Attractiveness	Global Opportunity Index (GOI)	Milken Institute	2021	The GOI measures a country's attractiveness to international investors using a combination of economic, financial, institutional, and regulatory factors.	<u>5 Pillars:</u> Business Perception, Economic Fundamentals, Financial Services, Institutional Framework, International Standards & Policy	39 – 145 0 African countries in highest 50% Total: 145
12	ICT & Connectivity	EIU Technological Readiness Ranking	Economist Intelligence	2018	The Technological Readiness Ranking assesses how well-prepared countries are for technological change.	<u>3 Pillars:</u> Access to the internet, Digital economy infrastructure, Openness to innovation	42 – 82 No African country in highest 50% Total: 82
13	ICT & Connectivity	ICT Development Index (IDI)	International Telecommunication Union	2017	The IDI allows the benchmarking of the most important indicators for measuring the information society.	<u>3 Pillars:</u> ICT Access, ICT Use, ICT Skills	72 – 176 1 African country in highest 50% Total: 176
14	ICT & Connectivity	Global Connectivity Index (GCI)	Huawei	2020	The GCI offers practical insights and recommendations for policy makers on what it takes to succeed in the digital economy.	<u>3 Pillars:</u> ICT investment, ICT maturity, Digital economic performance	0 African countries in highest 50% Total: 79
15	ICT & Connectivity	Network Readiness Index (NRI)	World Economic Forum	2019	The NRI measures the propensity for countries to exploit the opportunities offered by information and communications technology.	<u>4 Pillars:</u> Technology, People, Governance, Impact	53 - 120 1 African country in highest 50%

							Total: 121
16	Human Capital & Talent	Global Talent Competitiveness Index (GTCI)	INSEAD	2019	The GTCI measures and ranks countries based on their ability to grow, attract and retain talent.	<u>6 Pillars:</u> Enable, Attract, Grow, Retain, Vocational and technical skills, Global knowledge skills	47 – 124 2 African countries in highest 50%
							Total: 125
17	Human Capital & Talent	Global Human Capital Index	World Economic Forum	2017	The Global Human Capital Index ranks countries on how well they are developing their human capital.	<u>4 Pillars:</u> Capacity, Deployment, Development, Know-how	71 – 130 0 African countries in highest 50%
							Total: 130

Appendix 2 – Country ranking according to the African regions

Table 9: Number of African countries in Top 5, Top 10 and Top 15 ranking, according to African region

	North			East			Southern			West			Central		
COUNTRIES IN THE TOP...	5	10	15	5	10	15									
Innovation	2	3	3	2	4	5	1	2	5	0	1	2	0	0	0
Start-up Ecosystems & Entrepreneurship	2	4	4	1	2	5	1	2	2	1	2	4	0	0	0
Economic & Regulatory Environment	1	3	3	2	2	4	2	3	3	0	2	5	0	0	0
Investment Attractiveness	2	3	4	3	3	5	1	2	3	0	2	3	0	0	0
ICT & Connectivity	3	5	5	1	2	4	1	2	3	0	1	3	0	0	0
Human Capital & Talent	0	1	2	2	3	5	2	4	4	1	2	4	0	1	2
AVERAGE	1.7	3.2	3.5	1.8	2.7	4.7	1.3	2.5	3.3	0.3	1.7	3.5	0	0.2	0.3

Appendix 3 – Overall country rankings according to six categories

Table 10: Overall Top 15 African countries ranking and according to the six categories

Rank	Overall	Start-up	Innovation	Economy	Investment	ICT	Human Capital
1	Mauritius	South Africa	Mauritius	Mauritius	South Africa	Mauritius	Mauritius
2	South Africa	Egypt	South Africa	Morocco	Egypt / Morocco	South Africa	Ghana
3	Morocco	Tunisia	Tunisia	South Africa	-	Tunisia / Morocco	South Africa / Rwanda
4	Tunisia	Kenya	Morocco	Rwanda	Mauritius	-	-
5	Egypt	Nigeria	Kenya	Botswana	Kenya / Rwanda	Egypt	Botswana
6	Kenya	Ghana	Tanzania	Tunisia	-	Algeria	Kenya
7	Rwanda	Morocco	Egypt	Cote d' Ivoire	Tunisia	Botswana	Namibia
8	Botswana	Namibia	Namibia	Ghana / Egypt / Namibia	Ghana	Kenya	Zambia
9	Ghana	Rwanda	Rwanda	-	Nigeria	Ghana	Egypt
10	Namibia	Algeria	Senegal	-	Botswana	Libya	Cameroon
11	Nigeria	Senegal	Botswana	Nigeria	Zambia	Namibia	Uganda / Tunisia
12	Tanzania	Cote d' Ivoire	Malawi	Kenya	Uganda	Nigeria	-
13	Algeria	Tanzania	Madagascar	Togo	Algeria	Senegal	Benin
14	Cote d' Ivoire	Ethiopia	Ghana	Senegal	Tanzania	Rwanda	Tanzania / Gabon / Gambia
15	Senegal	Uganda	Zimbabwe	Tanzania	Cote d' Ivoire	Uganda	-

NB Overall: The following countries are missing in more than two indexes of the overall seventeen indexes: Cote d' Ivoire (five times missing), Mauritius (four times missing), Senegal and Botswana (both three times missing). All other eleven countries are missing in maximum two rankings.

NB Categories: In some categories, countries have not been included since they appear in to less than 50% of the rankings/indexes of each category. This is the case for Botswana, Eswatini and Mauritius (all three for Start-up), Cote d' Ivoire (for ICT) and Gabon (for Start-Up and ICT). If a country is included in less than fifty percent of the indexes of a category, then it is not included in Figure 5.

Appendix 4 – Country performance: Population, location, and GDP data

This appendix details the performance of each African country (in order of the country rank), complemented with information on population⁴¹, location⁴² as well as GDP⁴³ data.

Mauritius (1) ranks as 1st place in 4 of the 6 categories (Innovation, Economy, ICT, Human Capital) and a high 4th place in Investment. However, it is not included in the top 15 for Start-up because this category is based on 3 indexes, and Mauritius was only ranked in one index⁴⁴.

Population: 1,300,000	Population per km ² : 624	Location: East Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 10.9	GDP per Capita: \$8,620	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 3.6%

South Africa (2) performs very well in all 6 categories (In top 3 in each of them) and achieves a 1st place in the categories Start-up and Investment.

Population: 59,000,000	Population per km ² : 49	Location: Southern Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 301.9	GDP per Capita: \$5,090	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 0.79%

Morocco (3) ranks very high when it comes to Economy, Investment, ICT and Innovation (in top 4 in each of them). However, in the category Start-up it ranks a bit lower (in top 7) and achieves a poor result in Human Capital (not even in top 15).

Population: 37,000,000	Population per km ² : 83	Location: North Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 112.9	GDP per Capita: \$3,010	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 3.1%

Tunisia (4) achieves very good results in the categories Start-up, Innovation and ICT (in top 3 in each of them). Concerning the categories Economy and Investment it ranks a bit lower (ranks 6 and 7, respectively) and only achieves an average 11th place for Human Capital.

Population: 12,000,000	Population per km ² : 76	Location: North Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 39.2	GDP per Capita: \$3,320	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 1.38%

Egypt (5) performs very well in the categories Start-up, Investment, and ICT (in top 5 each). However, for Innovation, Economy and Human Capital it ranks lower (ranks 7-8).

Population: 102,000,000	Population per km ² : 102	Location: North Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 363.1	GDP per Capita: \$3,550	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 4.75%

⁴¹ Data is rounded up, based on United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division: [World Population Prospects 2019, Volume I: Comprehensive Tables \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/publications/prospects2019/)

⁴² Data is based on African Union: [Regions of the African Union - List of regions of Africa](https://www.africanunion.org/en/regions/)

⁴³ Data is rounded up, based on World Bank: [GDP data](https://data.worldbank.org/)

⁴⁴ If a country is not ranked in at least 50% of the indexes of one category, it is not included in the category ranking.

Kenya (6) ranks very high for Start-up, Innovation as well as Investment. However, it achieves lower results for Human Capital and ICT (rank 6 and 8, respectively) and specifically for Economy with an average 12th place. In the economy category it particularly scores low in the Index of Economic Freedom.

Population: 54,000,000	Population per km ² : 94	Location: East Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 98.8	GDP per Capita: \$1,840	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 5.62%

Rwanda (7) achieves very high results in the categories Human Capital, Economy as well as Investment (in top 5 for each category). However, for Start-up, Innovation (rank 9 for both) and particularly ICT (rank 14) it is only ranked average.

Population: 13,000,000	Population per km ² : 527	Location: East Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 10.3	GDP per Capita: \$800	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 7.37%

Botswana (8) performs very well in Economy and Human Capital (rank 5 for both). While for ICT (7th place) it achieves a respectable result, for Investment and Innovation, however, only a two-digit rank for each (10 and 11th place, respectively). In the Start-up category it is not included in the top 15 because it was only ranked in 1 of 3 indexes.

Population: 2,400,000	Population per km ² : 4	Location: Southern Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 15.8	GDP per Capita: \$6,710	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 2.6%

Ghana (9) ranks very high for Human Capital (2nd place), however, does not rank in the top 5 in any of the other categories. It can be found most often between rank 6 and 9 (Start-up, Economy, Investment, ICT). Only in the category, Innovation, it performs poorly (14th place).

Population: 31,000,000	Population per km ² : 136	Location: West Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 72.4	GDP per Capita: \$2,330	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 5.27%

Namibia (10) does not perform very high in any of the categories but is mostly ranked in the top 8 (for Start-up, Innovation, Economy, Human Capital), but only achieves an average 11th place for ICT and is not even ranked in the top 15 at all when it comes to Investment.

Population: 2,500,000	Population per km ² : 3	Location: Southern Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 10.7	GDP per Capita: \$ 4,210	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 0.75%

Nigeria (11) performs very well in the Start-up category (5th place). Other than that, though, it achieves ranks 9-12 for Investment, Economy, and ICT. For the categories Human Capital and Innovation, it is not even included in the top 15.

Population: 206,000,000	Population per km ² : 226	Location: West Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 432.3	GDP per Capita: \$2,100	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 1.19%

Tanzania (12) achieves a good 6th place for Innovation. Besides that, it is ranked between 13-15 for the categories Investment, Economy, Human Capital and Start-up. It is, however, not included at all in the top 15 of ICT.

Population: 59,000,000	Population per km ² : 67	Location: East Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 62.4	GDP per Capita: \$1,080	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 6.21%

Algeria (13) performs well for the category ICT (6th rank). For the category Start-up (10th rank) and Investment (13th place) it performs average, while in the categories Economy, Human Capital and Innovation it is not ranked at all in top 15.

Population: 44,000,000	Population per km ² : 18	Location: North Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 145.1	GDP per Capita: \$3,310	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 2.04%

Cote d' Ivoire (14) is ranked rather well in the Economy category with a 7th place. For Start-up it achieves a 12th place, while it barely makes it in the top 15 in the Investment category. In the categories Innovation, ICT and Human Capital it is not ranked at all in the top 15.

Population: 26,000,000	Population per km ² : 82	Location: West Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 61.3	GDP per Capita: \$2,330	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 7.3%

Senegal (15) ranks average for the categories Start-up, Economy, Innovation, and IC (between 10-14 rank). In the categories Human Capital and Investment, it is not included in the top 15.

Population: 17,000,000	Population per km ² : 88	Location: West Africa
GDP (in Bil. \$): 24.9	GDP per Capita: \$1,490	Avg. GDP Growth (2015-2019): 6.15%

Appendix 5 – Gross Expenditure on R&D (GERD) and Government Expenditure on R&D indicators

Table 11: Various Gross Expenditure on R&D (GERD) and Government Expenditure on R&D indicators

Rank	Gross Expenditure on R&D (GERD) (% of GDP)	Government Expenditure on R&D (GOVERD) (% of GDP)	Government Expenditure on R&D (GOVERD) (PPP\$ M)	Government Expenditure on R&D per Capita (GOVERD) (PPP\$)	GERD by Government funds
1	South Africa (0.83)	Tanzania (0.27)	Egypt (2,480.00)	Egypt (26.44)	Nigeria (97%)
2	Kenya (0.79)	Egypt (0.26)	South Africa (1,123.5)	South Africa (20.32)	Egypt / Zambia (95%)
3	Egypt (0.72)	Senegal (0.23)	Tanzania (231.7)	Namibia (16.77)	Togo (94%)
4	Morocco (0.71)	Mali (0.19)	Ethiopia (190.8)	Botswana (10.19)	Lesotho (91%)
5	Burkina Faso (0.70)	Namibia (0.18)	Ghana (91.4)	Eswatini (8.87)	Senegal (85%)
6	Rwanda (0.67)	South Africa / Mozambique (0.16)	Senegal (81.7)	Senegal (5.45)	Mauritius (80%)
7	Tunisia (0.6)	-	Mali (55.7)	Tanzania (4.30)	Tunisia (78%)
8	Gabon (0.58)	Ethiopia (0.15)	Uganda (55)	Ghana (3.31)	Namibia (63%)
9	Senegal (0.58)	Eswatini (0.13)	Mozambique (48.5)	Mali (3.19)	Botswana (60%)
10	Botswana / Algeria (0.54)	Burkina Faso / Ghana / Uganda (0.08)	Namibia (40.8)	Ethiopia (1.91)	Tanzania (58%)
11	-	-	Botswana (22.5)	Mozambique (1.73)	South Africa (47%)
12	Tanzania (0.51)	-	Burkina Faso (22.5)	Uganda (1.37)	Mozambique (43%)
13	D.R. Congo (0.41)	Botswana (0.07)	Angola (20.1)	Togo (0.66)	Uganda (39%)
14	Ghana (0.38)	Togo (0.04)	Eswatini (11.7)	Burkina Faso (0.56)	Kenya (26%)
15	Mauritius / Namibia (0.35)	Rwanda (0.03)	D.R. Congo (10.2)	Rwanda (0.55)	Morocco (24%)

NB: Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria are not included in any GOVERD indicator

Appendix 6 – GII pillars, sub-pillars, and indicators

Here, the pillars are indicated in the headings (with icon), the sub-pillars in light blue rows and the indicators in the white rows.

Institutions

Number	Indicator
1.1	Political Environment
1.1.1	Political and operational stability
1.1.2	Government effectiveness
1.2	Regulatory Environment
1.2.1	Regulatory quality
1.2.2	Rule of law
1.2.3	Cost of redundancy dismissal
1.3	Business Environment
1.3.1	Ease of starting a business
1.3.2	Ease of resolving insolvency

Human capital and research

Number	Indicator
2.1	Education
2.1.1	Expenditure on education, % GDP
2.1.2	Government funding/pupil, secondary, % GDP/cap
2.1.3	School life expectancy, years
2.1.4	PISA scales in reading, maths and science
2.1.5	Pupil-teacher ratio, secondary
2.2	Tertiary education
2.2.1	Tertiary enrolment, % gross
2.2.2	Graduates in science and engineering, %
2.2.3	Tertiary inbound mobility, %
2.3	Research and development (R&D)
2.3.1	Researchers, FTE/mn pop.
2.3.2	Gross expenditure on R&D, % GDP
2.3.3	Global corporate R&D investors, top 3, mn US\$
2.3.4	QS university ranking, top 3

Infrastructure

Number	Indicator
3.1	Information and communication technologies (ICTs)
3.1.1	ICT access (index)
3.1.2	ICT use (index)

3.1.3	Government's online service (index)
3.1.4	E-participation (index)
3.2	General infrastructure
3.2.1	Electricity output, GWh/mn pop.
3.2.2	Logistics performance (index)
3.2.3	Gross capital formation, % GDP
3.3	Ecological sustainability
3.3.1	GDP/unit of energy use
3.3.2	Environmental performance (index)
3.3.3	ISO 14001 environmental certificates/bn PPP\$ GDP

Market sophistication

Number	Indicator
4.1	Credit
4.1.1	Ease of getting credit
4.1.2	Domestic credit to private sector, % GDP
4.1.3	Microfinances gross loans, % GDP
4.2	Investment
4.2.1	Ease of protecting minority investors (index)
4.2.2	Market capitalization, % GDP
4.2.3	Venture capital investors, deals/bn PPP\$ GDP
4.2.4	Venture capital recipients, deals/bn PPP\$ GDP
4.3	Trade, diversification, and market scale
4.3.1	Applied tariff rate, weighted avg., %
4.3.2	Domestic industry diversification
4.3.3	Domestic market scale, bn PPP\$

Business sophistication

Number	Indicator
5.1	Knowledge workers
5.1.1	Knowledge-intensive employment, %
5.1.2	Firms offering formal training, %
5.1.3	GERD performance by business, % GDP
5.1.4	GERD financed by business, %
5.1.5	Females employed w/advanced degrees, %
5.2	Innovation linkages
5.2.1	University-industry R&D collaborations
5.2.2	State of cluster development and depth
5.2.3	GERD financed by abroad, % GDP
5.2.4	Joint ventures/strategic alliances deals/bn PPP\$ GDP
5.2.5	Patent families/bn PPP\$ GDP
5.3	Knowledge absorption
5.3.1	Intellectual property payments, % total trade

5.3.2	High-tech imports, % total trade
5.3.3	ICT services imports, % total trade
5.3.4	FDI net inflows, % GDP
5.3.5	Research talent, % in businesses

Knowledge and technology outputs

Number	Indicator
6.1	Knowledge creation
6.1.1	Patents by origin/bn PPP\$ GDP
6.1.2	PCT patents by origin/bn PP\$ GDP
6.1.3	Utility models by origin/bn PPP\$ GDP
6.1.4	Scientific and technical articles/bn PPP\$ GDP
6.1.5	Citable documents H-index
6.2	Knowledge impact
6.2.1	Labour productivity growth, %
6.2.2	New business/th pop. 15-64
6.2.3	Software spending, % GDP
6.2.4	ISO 9001 quality certificates/bn PPP\$ GDP
6.2.5	High-tech manufacturing, %
6.3	Knowledge diffusion
6.3.1	Intellectual property receipts, % total trade
6.3.2	Production and export complexity
6.3.3	High-tech exports, % total trade
6.3.4	ICT services exports, % total trade

Creative outputs

Number	Indicator
7.1	Intangible assets
7.1.1	Trademarks by origin/bn PPP\$ GDP
7.1.2	Global brand value, top 5,000, % GDP
7.1.3	Industrial designs by origin/bn PPP\$ GDP
7.1.4	ICTs and organisational model creation
7.2	Creative goods and services
7.2.1	Cultural and creative services exports, % total trade
7.2.2	National feature films/mn pop.15-69
7.2.3	Entertainment and media market/th pop. 15-69
7.2.4	Printing and other media, % manufacturing
7.2.5	Creative goods exports, % total trade
7.3	Online creativity
7.3.1	Generic top-level domains (TLDs)/th pop. 15-69
7.3.2	Country-code TLDs/th pop. 15-69
7.3.3	Wikipedia edits/mn pop. 15-69
7.3.4	Mobile app creation/bn PPP\$ GDP

Appendix 7 – Country GII Data

Table 12- African Country Rankings (North and Sub-Saharan)- Global Innovation Index (2021)

Ranking in Africa 2021	Country	Innovation Index Position	Score (1-100)
1st	Mauritius	52	35.2
2 nd	South Africa	61	32.7
3 rd	Tunisia	71	30.7
4 th	Morocco	77	29.3
5 th	Kenya	85	27.5
6 th	Cabo Verde	89	25.7
7 th	United Republic of Tanzania	90	25.6
8 th	Egypt	94	25.1
9 th	Namibia	100	24.3
10 th	Rwanda	102	23.9
11 th	Senegal	105	23.3
12 th	Botswana	106	22.9
13 th	Malawi	107	22.9
14 th	Madagascar	110	22.5
15 th	Ghana	112	22.5
16 th	Zimbabwe	113	21.9
17 th	Côte d'Ivoire	114	21.0
18 th	Burkina Faso	115	20.5
19 th	Nigeria	118	20.1
20 th	Uganda	119	20.0
21 st	Algeria	120	19.9
22 nd	Zambia	121	19.8
23 rd	Mozambique	122	19.7
24 th	Cameroon	123	19.7
25 th	Mali	124	19.5
26 th	Togo	125	19.3

27 th	Ethiopia	126	18.6
28 th	Benin	128	18.0
29 th	Niger	129	17.8
30 th	Guinea	130	16.7
31 st	Angola	132	15.0

